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Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D31: CODECO Federated Cluster Operation Architectural Design

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Executive Summary

D31 provides the final architectural specification of the CODECO Federated Cluster framework. It supersedes D10 and reflects the complete design achieved across the full CODECO project lifecycle (M1–M39). D31 is an additional deliverable proposed by the consortium to the European Commission in support of the open-source publication and long-term reuse of the CODECO architectural design. D31 establishes the three design principles that jointly distinguish the CODECO Federated Cluster architecture from existing approaches. **Data-compute-network co-orchestration** treats networking, data observability, and computation as perspectives that must be jointly considered in every placement and adaptation decision, rather than optimised in isolation. A **hybrid governance model** separates governance centralised at a Hub cluster via Open Cluster Management (OCM) from coordination and execution, which are progressively decentralised toward Managed Clusters, enabling global policy consistency while supporting autonomous far Edge operation during Hub disconnections. **Application neighbourhoods** define bounded, semantically selected subsets of Managed Clusters relevant to a specific application, limiting the scope of monitoring, learning, and scheduling exchanges to provide federation-scale coordination without prohibitive communication overhead. It also analyses federated operation priority areas, namely, control-plane decentralisation, privacy-preserving decentralised AI, semantic abstraction and adaptive networking, and federated scheduling, providing for each a structured analysis of existing approaches, a set of open questions, and the architectural directions adopted in CODECO.

The deliverable then presents the overall CODECO federated architecture, including its three-layer governance model, the OCM-based federation control structure, the application neighbourhood concept, and the AI-driven decision flow. Each of its components is presented, and the single and federated operation is explained: the **CODECO Neighbourhood Composer (CNC)** plugin computes and maintains application neighbourhood definitions, determining the bounded cluster scope for each application's scheduling and monitoring exchanges. **ACM-FC** is the sole user-facing entry point, responsible for application lifecycle management via the CODECO Application Model (CAM), cluster configuration, and coordination of all other components. **PDLC-FC** provides AI-assisted placement recommendations through neighbourhood-scoped federated learning and multi-agent reinforcement learning, keeping raw telemetry local to each Managed Cluster and exchanging only encrypted model artefacts. **MDM-FC** maintains a semantic metadata graph capturing data locality, freshness, compliance, and portability across the federation, enabling data-aware placement decisions. **NetMA-FC** delivers cross-layer network observability through ALTO-based cost maps and passive eBPF-instrumented monitoring and manages secure inter-cluster connectivity through a Layer 2 mesh approach integrated with a hybrid SDN control plane. **SWM-FC** implements a two-layer federated scheduler supporting stateful migration. The most consequential directions for future work, and the Eclipse KUDECO project as the long-term vehicle for CODECO's community development are debated in the final part of the deliverable.

The content of this deliverable is closely aligned with the peer-reviewed system architecture paper "*Towards Scalable Federated Container Orchestration: The CODECO Approach*" [1], published as an arXiv pre-print in January 2026 and currently under peer review, which provides a concise externally validated companion perspective. The CODECO codebase is published under open-source licences through the Eclipse KUDECO project on the Eclipse Research Labs platform, which provides the governance and sustainability framework for CODECO's continued development beyond the project.

Keywords: Edge-Cloud continuum; container orchestration; Kubernetes; federated clusters; AI/ML; context-awareness; privacy-preserving learning; application neighbourhoods; data observability; KUDECO.

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Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, Accounting
ACM	Automated Configuration Manager
AGV	Autonomous Guided Vehicles
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AP	Access Point
API	Application Programming Interface
APOC	Awesome Procedures on Cypher
AR	Augmented Reality
BTLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
CA	Context-awareness
CD	Compute Domain
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CLI	Command Line Interface
CLI	Command Line Interface
CNI	Container Network Interface
CODECO	Cognitive, Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CP	Customer Premises
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CR	Custom Resource
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
CSDG	CODECO Synthetic Data Generator
DEV	Developer
DL	Deep Learning
DoA	Description of the Action
eBPF	Extended Berkeley Packet Filter
EC	European Commission
EDA	Encoder Decoder Architectures
EN	Edge Node
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standards Institute
FaaS	Function as a Service
FaaS	Function as a Service
FC	Federated Clusters
FIDO	Fast Identity Online
FL	Federated Learning
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GENEVE	Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation
GNNs	Graph Neural Networks
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRU	Gate Recurrent
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HE	Horizon Europe
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IDS	International Data Spaces
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force

Acronym	Meaning
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
IPR	Intellectual Property
IPSec	Internet Protocol Security
IPv6	Internet Protocol Version 6
JSON	Javascript Object Notation
K8s	Kubernetes
KCP	Kubernetes like Control Plane
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L2	Layer 2
L3	Layer 3
LPM	L2S-M Performance Measurement module
LS2-M	Layer Two Virtual Private Network Service Model
LSTM	Long-Short Term Memory
LTE	Long-term Evolution
MAC	Media Access Control
MAPE	<i>Mean Absolute Percentage Error</i>
MARL	Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning
MDM	Metadata Manager
MEC	Multi-access Edge computing
MGR	Infrastructure Manager
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Protocol
ND	Network Domain
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
NGIOT	Next Generation Internet of Things
NN	Neural Network
NSM	Network State Management
NUC	Next Unit of Computing
OAS	Open API Specification
OCM	Open Cluster Management
OLM	Operator Lifecycle Management
OS	Operating System
OSS	open-source system
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness
PLS	Programmable Layer 2 Switches
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
RFC	Request for Comments
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RTT	Round Trip Time
SDN	Software Defined Network
STGNN	Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

Acronym	Meaning
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UI	User Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VoIP	Voice over IP
VR	Virtual Reality
VXLAN	Virtual eXtensible Local Area Network
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language
ALM	Application Lifecycle Manager
ALTO	Application Layer Traffic Optimization
AS	Autonomous System
BGP	Border Gateway Protocol
CAM	CODECO Application Model
CNC	CODECO Neighbourhood Composer Plugin
CSV	Comma-separated values
CTDE	Centralised Training/Decentralised Execution
DNS	Domain Name System
EVPN	Ethernet Virtual Private Network
GM	Global Master
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
IDCO	Inter-domain Connectivity Orchestrator
KFP	Kubeflow Pipelines
L2S-M	Link-Layer Secure Connectivity for Microservice Platforms
LM	Local Master
MCC	Multi-Cluster Configuration
MCMF	Minimum Cost Maximum Flow
MDP	Markov Decision Process
NBI	Northbound Interface
NED	Network Edge Device
ONOS	Open Network Operating System
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
PVC	Persistent Volume Claim
SDK	Software Development Kit
SLA	Service Level Agreement
WP	Work package
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol

List of Definitions

Term	Definition
Application	Computer software design to perform a single or several specific tasks, e.g., a calendar. In CODECO, an application is composed by at least one micro-service, i.e., applications are a collection of services that are loosely coupled, highly available, and independently deployable.
Application Neighbourhood	A bounded, semantically defined subset of clusters relevant to a specific application. Neighbourhoods constrain the coordination space for scheduling, monitoring, and learning, limiting the amount of state that must be shared while still enabling cooperative behaviour across distributed environments. Application Neighbourhoods are a CODECO-specific concept introduced to enable federation-scale coordination without prohibitive communication overhead.
Application Programming Interface (API)	Well defined specification used in a software program to access services or resources provided by another software application. Establishes the interface between two different applications.
Cloud	IT environment that abstracts, pools, and shares IT resources across a network. A Cloud is a software-defined environment associated with hyperscale data centres, often far from the data sources or end-user.
Cloud computing	The act of running application workloads on a Cloud.
Cluster	A K8s cluster consists of the components that are a part of the control plane (master nodes) and worker nodes, where containerised applications run. A cluster corresponds to the logical environment where pods run in a way that has been orchestrated by a human operator.
Consumer	See service recipient
Container	Container follows the K8s definition, where it is a package with the overall settings (workload, state, data) to allow execution of an application in an independent way. A container runs logically in a pod.
Container manager	See orchestrator.
Container orchestrator	A tool that assists the setup and lifetime management of containerised applications. Examples of container orchestrators are K8s and Docker swarm.
Context-awareness	The capability of a system to integrate knowledge about its environment into decision-making. In orchestration, this means going beyond static resource thresholds to incorporate dynamic, multi-perspective information about the application, its data, the network, and the user or device generating the workload. In CODECO, context-awareness metrics are categorised as computational, network, application, data observability, and user behaviour metrics.
Co-orchestration	The joint, unified treatment of networking, data observability, and computation as perspectives that must be simultaneously considered in every placement and adaptation decision, rather than optimised in isolation. In CODECO, co-orchestration is implemented through the coordinated operation of ACM (computation), MDM (data), and NetMA (network) components.
CR	From K8s. CRs correspond to new objects (or instances of) defined by CRDs. A custom resource is the API extension mechanism in Kubernetes.
CRD	From K8s. A custom resource definition (CRD) defines a CR and lists out all the configuration available to users of a K8s operator. Written in YAML it has a limit of 1 MiB due to being stored in the K8s etcd, which has been designed to handle small key value pairs typical for metadata. CRDs supply definitions for CRs, thus assisting in creating new types of resources without having to add another API server in K8s.

Term	Definition
Data locality	A property reflecting the physical or logical proximity between data sources and the computational resources that process them. Data locality is a key input to placement decisions in CODECO, and can be captured via MDM.
Data sovereignty	The principle that data generated or collected within a cluster or administrative domain is subject to the laws, policies, and governance of that domain, and must not be shared beyond it without explicit authorisation. Data sovereignty constraints are a primary driver of the privacy-preserving design of CODECO's federated learning and metadata components.
Edge	An IT environment that abstracts, pools, and supplies IT resource sharing in a location close to data sources (e.g., IoT devices, end-user). Place computing resources closer to the user or the device, at the “edge” of the network, rather than in a hyperscale cloud data centre that might be many miles away in the “core” of the network. CODECO adopts the terms supported far Edge and near Edge as in NGIOT [1].
Edge-Cloud continuum	The overall IT environment interconnecting and end-user to services running across the far Edge until the Cloud.
End-user	See User.
far Edge	The notion of far Edge reflects the elements located on customer premises, covering not only the existing cyber-physical systems but also the interfaces to the real-world, as well as context-awareness (e.g., situational awareness) required to perform local/partial decisions (storage, processing, analysis decisions) upon data collected. Hence, the far Edge embodies a full intertwining to the real-world which can only be provided via some form of context-awareness, behaviour inference and learning, i.e., integration of intelligence. Physically, the near Edge integrates the last mile concept. Applications that run on the far Edge are often time-sensitive, require ultra-low latency, high scalability, and high throughput. Examples are AR/VR, Gaming. Other used terms for far Edge are deep Edge, micro-Edge.
Federated Clusters (FC)	A group of Kubernetes clusters spanning one or more administrative domains, coordinated through a shared governance substrate and capable of jointly hosting, scheduling, and adapting distributed applications across the Cloud–Edge–IoT continuum. In CODECO, a Federated Cluster environment consists of one or more Hub clusters and a set of Managed Clusters connected via the OCM hub-and-spoke model.
Governance	The layer responsible for defining and enforcing the authoritative desired state of the federated system, including application intent, organisational policies, regulatory compliance, and auditability across the federation. In CODECO, governance is centralised at the Hub cluster via OCM, while coordination and execution are progressively decentralised toward Managed Clusters.
Greenness	A customisable metric capturing sustainability objectives such as reduced energy consumption and lower CO ₂ footprint. In CODECO, greenness is treated as an optimisation criterion that can be combined with other performance objectives, including latency, resilience, and data locality, and is quantified using node energy, link energy, network energy, and flow energy metrics.
Hub cluster	The cluster that acts as the centralised governance and control point in the OCM hub-and-spoke model. The Hub cluster is responsible for cluster registration, policy propagation, and workload manifest dispatch. In CODECO, the Hub cluster also runs ACM-FC, the Neighbourhood Composer (CNC), and the federation-level scheduling coordinator (SWM-FC).

Term	Definition
Intent	A high-level, declarative expression of application requirements or operational objectives, specified without prescribing the specific resources or mechanisms by which those requirements shall be met. In CODECO, application intent is captured in the CODECO Application Model (CAM) and translated into internal scheduling, networking, and learning decisions by the respective components.
Interconnection	The physical and logical linking of public communications networks used by the same or a different undertaking to allow the users of one undertaking to communicate with users of the same or another undertaking, or to access services provided by another undertaking.
K8s control plane	The control plane is the system that can assist in defining, deploying, and managing the lifecycle of containers in a cluster. It continuously manages object states, responding to changes in the cluster and triggering changes to match a desired performance state. The K8s control plane is made up of three major components: the scheduler (kube-scheduler), the controller manager (kube-controller-manager) and the API server (kube-apiserver). The K8s control plane can run a single master node or can be replicated across multiple master nodes for high reliability.
Last mile	From telecommunications, the last mile corresponds to the final segment between the service provider and the user. Today, the last mile is often based on wireless and cellular communications.
Managed Cluster	A Kubernetes cluster registered with and administered by an OCM Hub cluster. Managed Clusters (also referred to as spoke clusters) host the execution layer, running containerised workloads and local CODECO components for monitoring, learning, and scheduling. Managed Clusters are designed to continue operating autonomously when connectivity to the Hub is temporarily unavailable.
Master node	The K8s node that holds the K8s control plane. The K8s master node holds configuration and state data and manages communication towards worker nodes (via the K8s API), to schedule containers efficiently.
Micro-service	An underlying component service of an application. Each micro-service in an application serves a specific service. An example is an application that integrates a PubSub broker; a database; an object detection application.
Migration	Process of transferring an ongoing application workload between two nodes.
Multi-tenancy	The operation of multiple independent users, organisations, or administrative domains (tenants) sharing the same federated infrastructure while maintaining isolation of workloads, data, and policies. A tenant in CODECO is an entity that owns and manages one or more clusters and exercises governance over the data and workloads within those clusters.
Namespace	From Kubernetes. A mechanism for logically partitioning cluster resources between multiple users or applications. Namespaces provide a scope for resource names and enable resource isolation and access control within a single cluster, and coherence across clusters in a federation.
Near Edge	near Edge is a definition tied to the Edge elements and services that are in the access/core regions of the network, i.e., between the far Edge and the Cloud data centres. The near Edge reflects the integration of ML to best support resource managements and to best orchestrate the applications to be served. An example of a near Edge architecture is the ETSI MEC 136. Near Edge hosts generic services. An example of a near Edge service is CDN.
Network service	Set of operational network functionality needed to sustain user services. Examples of network services in CODECO are resource management, network exposure. For instance, Internet connectivity is a network service

Term	Definition
Network infrastructure	Collection of links and of networking nodes that together enable data transmission between (Internet) users. The links connect the nodes together and are themselves built upon an underlying transmission network which physically pushes the message across the link.
Offloading	Offloading implies moving an application and its micro-services across different environments. Therefore, with offloading, the "old" environment, the application workload and its state are deleted and not simply made inactive; a copy of workload and of state, followed by eventual adaptation of state is done in the "new" environment.
Operator	From K8s. A Kubernetes operator watches a CR type and takes application-specific actions to make the current state match the desired state in that resource. Hence, an operator is a software extension that allows to encapsulate K8s application resources (i.e., pods, Deployments, Daemon sets, Stateful sets, Jobs, Services, ConfigMaps, etc.) by creating a CR and a K8s controller. Operators track cluster events related to specific types of CRs. These CRs can track by default three types of events—add, update, and delete.
Orchestration	The automated management of the full lifecycle of containerised applications across one or more clusters, encompassing deployment, scheduling, scaling, monitoring, adaptation, and termination. In CODECO, orchestration is extended beyond single-cluster Kubernetes to support federated, context-aware, and privacy-preserving operation across the Cloud–Edge–IoT continuum.
Overlay network infrastructure	The software-driven transportation of network traffic, operating over the underlay network and abstracting low-level details of traffic forwarding, from a Kubernetes perspective. It is therefore a virtual network, i.e., provides an abstraction of the resources provided by the underlay network.
Placement	The act of assigning application workloads (micro-services) to specific nodes within a cluster, or clusters within a federation, based on resource availability, application requirements, network constraints, and data locality. Placement is the primary output of the SWM component, informed by recommendations from PDLC.
pod	pod follows also the K8s definition, being a logical wrapper entity for containers to be executed on a K8s cluster. This logical wrapper "holds" a group of one or more containers with shared storage and network resources, and a common namespace, providing a definition to run the containers. pod may hold more than one container. A pod is the unit of replication in a cluster.
Recipient of a service	"Recipient of the service" [2000/31/EC Art.2.d] any natural or legal person who, for professional ends or otherwise, uses an information society service, for the purposes of seeking information or making it accessible.
Replication	Replication implies that an application and its micro-services are copied across different locations, i.e., there are multiple replicas of the application in a system, some active, and some inactive. Replication requires a way to synchronize state across an "old" and a "new" environment where the application is deployed and implies that even inactive applications consume resources (at least storage).
Resources	A physical or virtual element of a global system. For instance, bandwidth, energy, data, devices, are examples of resources in CODECO.
Scheduler	A software-based entity that performs assignment of resources to perform specific tasks. The scheduler performs assignments based on a specific performance target, e.g., load-balancing, bounded latency, low jitter.
Session	Permanent or transient information exchange between two or more devices and/or users.
Stateful applications	Stateful applications keep state on clusters, and require that state (data, status of the application) to be kept.

Term	Definition
Stateless applications	Stateless applications require no data storage to work.
Tenant	See Multi-tenancy.
Underlay network infrastructure	The physical infrastructure that enables frames and packets to be forwarded from one point to another. Comprises the end-to-end physical path equipment, e.g., switches, routers. From an OSI model perspective, comprises the first three layers of the OSI model: physical, data link, and network.
User	A legal entity or individual using or requesting a publicly available electronic communications service for private or business purposes, without necessarily having subscribed to such service. In CODECO, a user can be i) a legal entity or individual (application developer) relying on the CODECO framework to setup and deploy an application across the Edge-Cloud continuum; ii) a legal entity or individual (CODECO service operator) relying on the CODECO framework to manage cluster configuration (setup) and runtime.
User service	A system that fulfils a need from an Internet end-user. For instance, VoIP and CDN are examples of user services.
Worker node	CODECO adopts the K8s worker node terminology. The workers are entities (K8s nodes) that run containerised micro-service. Each cluster has at least one worker node. pods are assigned to worker nodes, where a local daemon (Kohélet) manages the worker nodes life cycle. Kubelet is also the entry point to the K8s control plane.
Workload	An active micro-service and its state. A workload in CODECO is the minimum viable “unit” for migration, as it comprises a micro-service (e.g., storage), its state, and dependencies (e.g., networking resources).

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1 Introduction

The convergence of Cloud, Edge, and IoT infrastructures is reshaping how applications are deployed and operated. The *Cloud–Edge–IoT (CEI)* continuum pushes computation and data processing closer to users and devices, driven by requirements for low latency, resilience, sustainability, and contextual adaptation. Applications such as smart mobility, industrial automation, and immersive media increasingly rely on distributed execution across heterogeneous and often intermittently connected environments.

Despite this evolution, most container orchestration technologies remain largely cloud-centric. *Kubernetes (K8s)*, while widely adopted, assumes relatively stable clusters, centralised control, and homogeneous infrastructure under a single administrative domain. These assumptions become fragile in far Edge and multi-provider settings, where connectivity is variable, resources are constrained, and governance boundaries differ.

Three limitations are particularly relevant in CEI environments:

- **Limited cross-layer awareness:** Orchestration decisions are primarily driven by compute metrics while under-accounting for network conditions and data constraints.
- **Centralised control assumptions:** Existing orchestrators were designed based on models that do not hold under mobility, intermittent connectivity, and autonomous operation at the edge, resulting in low adaptability to dynamic environments.
- **Lack of federated abstractions:** There is an absence of primitives supporting multi-provider collaboration and controlled information exchange across administrative boundaries.

CODECO addresses these gaps by augmenting Kubernetes with federated orchestration capabilities, semantic application abstractions, and AI-assisted decision support. Rather than replacing Kubernetes, CODECO extends it to support context-aware deployment and adaptation of microservices across the CEI continuum.

This deliverable, D31, supersedes D10 [2] as the primary architectural reference for CODECO. D31 has been proposed as an additional deliverable to the EC to provide the comprehensive design specification required for the full federated cluster scope, which D10 addressed only in part.

1.1 Document Scope

This deliverable, D31, consolidates *D10 - CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture and open-source Ecosystem Design* in regard to the CODECO architectural design. D31 is an extra deliverable proposed by the consortium to the EC, to support the full architectural design of CODECO for multi-tenant, federated Cloud–Edge–IoT environments, including the specification of all core components in their *Federated Cluster (FC)* variants, their operational workflows, their placement across the federation, and the interaction patterns that enable co-orchestration of data, compute, and network resources.

The content of this deliverable is closely aligned with the peer-reviewed system architecture paper under publication by the CODECO consortium "*Towards Scalable Federated Container Orchestration: The CODECO Approach*" [1]. That scientific paper provides a concise, externally validated perspective; this deliverable provides the comprehensive design detail required for implementation and evaluation.

1.2 Dependencies

D31 covers the architectural design of the CODECO framework for federated operation. D31 complements D10, which described, among other aspects, the specification of the CODECO

OSS Basic Toolkit (single cluster operation). Finally, for the readers interested in experimenting the CODECO code, Deliverable D12 (CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit) [3] and D14 (CODECO OSS Federated Operation Toolkit v2.0) [4] should be considered (companion report to the existing OSS code)¹.

1.3 Document Structure

Section 2 — CODECO Design Principles and Scope establishes the conceptual and architectural foundations of the framework. It presents the data-compute-network co-orchestration model, the layered federation and governance model comprising governance, coordination, and execution layers, the context-awareness and energy-awareness dimensions that inform orchestration decisions, the mapping of CODECO to the CEI continuum across single-cluster and multi-cluster topologies, and a summary of the key technological enablers.

Section 3 — FC Priorities and Proposed Directions surveys the state of the art and derives the architectural directions for federated cluster operation. It first identifies the main challenges of federated Edge-Cloud orchestration, then addresses four priority areas in depth: control-plane decentralisation, privacy-preserving decentralised AI, semantic abstraction and adaptive networking, and federated scheduling. Each priority is structured around an analysis of existing approaches, a set of open questions that motivated the CODECO design, and the specific architectural directions adopted in CODECO. These open questions are revisited and answered in Section 7.

Section 4 — CODECO Federated Architecture presents the overall federated architecture. It covers the architectural assumptions and requirements, the core component structure and management-function mapping, the three-layer decision timescale model, the OCM-based federation control structure, the application neighbourhood concept and federated partitioning mechanism, the CODECO Application Model (CAM) as the semantic abstraction interface, component placement across the federation, and the AI-driven decision flow connecting all components.

Section 5 — CODECO Workflow Examples illustrates the end-to-end operation of the framework through three representative scenarios: the installation and deployment of CODECO across a federated infrastructure, the deployment of an application across a federated CEI environment, and the continuous management and adaptation of applications during runtime.

Section 6 — Components and their Operation provides the detailed specification of each CODECO component in both single-cluster and federated-cluster configurations. It covers five CODECO components and a plugin: the Neighbourhood Composer (CNC) plugin, ACM-FC, PDLC-FC, MDM-FC, NetMA-FC, and SWM-FC. For each component, the section describes sub-component design, key technologies, metrics, operational interfaces, single-cluster operation, and federated-cluster extensions. The suffix -FC denotes the federated cluster variant of a component; where absent, the description applies to the component in general or in its single-cluster form.

Section 7 — CODECO Answers to Federated Operation Challenges returns to the open questions identified in Section 3 and provides concrete answers for each, grounded in the architectural design and component implementations documented in Section 6. It is organised around the same four priority areas as Section 3: control-plane decentralisation, privacy-preserving decentralised AI, semantic abstraction and adaptive networking, and federated scheduling.

¹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

Section 8 — Summary, Key Takeaways and Directions for Future Work summarises the deliverable, draws the principal conclusions from the design work, and identifies the most consequential research and engineering directions for the Eclipse KUDECO project and the broader research community.

Annex I — Metrics provides the full and most up-to-date specification of the cross-layer metrics collected across the compute, network, and data observability dimensions, as used by ACM-FC, NetMA-FC, and MDM-FC respectively.

2 CODECO Design Principles and Scope

2.1 Network-Data-Compute

CODECO is a containerised application orchestration framework (TRL 4–5), designed to be independent of yet pluggable to K8s. Its core objective is to provide flexible, cognitive orchestration support across heterogeneous CEI infrastructures.

The CODECO infrastructure model integrates three complementary perspectives. The **networking perspective** treats the network as both the underlay and overlay infrastructure required to deploy and interconnect containerised applications across CEI environments. The **data observability perspective** captures the data dependencies that microservices carry, which must be accounted for during both initial deployment and redeployment. The **computational perspective** identifies suitable execution nodes for application components, taking into consideration resource availability, capacity constraints, and energy profiles. CODECO addresses orchestration across all three perspectives in a unified approach termed *data-compute-network co-orchestration*, illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The CODECO data-compute-network approach for CEI.

The motivation for this integrated approach follows directly from the evolving demands of the CEI continuum. Applications and their components must be lightweight, highly portable, and mobile — capable of running anywhere across the continuum. They must handle large volumes of data with heterogeneous characteristics, including stringent low-latency requirements. End-to-end data flows must remain smooth and secure across Edge–Cloud boundaries, and real-time decisions on where to compute and where to store data must be supported dynamically. As a cognitive and decentralised orchestration framework, CODECO embraces a vision in which data and services are stored and processed across the full Internet chain, through holistic cooperation between Cloud and far Edge environments. Microservices reside

in isolated, self-sufficient containers deployable on any underlying environment, interconnected by a flexible and secure networking infrastructure that adapts to the requirements of the services it supports.

2.2 Federation, Autonomy, and Governance Model

CODECO adopts a layered governance model tailored to federated CEI environments, where infrastructure spans multiple administrative domains and connectivity conditions vary over time. Rather than relying on fully centralised or fully decentralised control, CODECO defines a hybrid management model that separates governance, coordination, and execution responsibilities. This separation enables global policy consistency while preserving local autonomy and resilience at the far Edge.

2.2.1 Governance Layer

The governance layer defines the authoritative desired state of the system. It is responsible for expressing application intent, enforcing organisational and regulatory policies, and maintaining auditability across the federation. In CODECO, governance is based on the OCM hub-and-spoke model. In OCM, governance is centralised at a Hub cluster. However, CODECO goes beyond OCM to establish a shared control and governance substrate across spoke clusters.

2.2.2 Coordination Layer

The coordination layer limits the scope of orchestration and information exchange in order to ensure scalability and efficiency. CODECO introduces **application neighbourhoods** as bounded coordination domains that group a subset of Managed Clusters relevant to a specific application. Neighbourhoods define where monitoring data is exchanged, where learning components collaborate, and where scheduling decisions are optimised. By constraining coordination to application-specific subsets of clusters, CODECO avoids global state dissemination while still enabling cooperative behaviour across distributed environments.

2.2.3 Execution Layer

The execution layer resides within spoke (*Managed Clusters, MC*) and is responsible for enforcing placement, migration, and network configuration decisions using locally available context. This layer operates autonomously and continues to function even when connectivity to the Hub is degraded or temporarily unavailable. Scheduling, adaptation, and learning components at this layer consume centrally defined intent and policies but rely on fresh local observations to make timely decisions. This design ensures resilience and responsiveness at the far Edge while preserving convergence toward the desired global state once connectivity is restored.

2.3 Context-awareness and Energy Awareness

Context-awareness refers to the capability of a system to integrate knowledge about its environment into decision-making [5][6]. In orchestration, this means going beyond static resource thresholds, e.g., CPU, memory, network bandwidth, to incorporate dynamic, multi-perspective information about the application, its data, the network, and the user or device generating workload. CODECO introduces context-awareness as a first-class orchestration input, enabling it to respond to conditions that standard Kubernetes schedulers do not observe. To further support dynamic Edge-Cloud environments, container orchestration needs to integrate context-awareness into the offloading process.

A first step towards achieving **context-aware orchestration** is the definition of a basic set of context-awareness parameter categories to consider in the offloading process, how to model

context, and how such modelling can be integrated. In CODECO, the initial proposal derives from prior analysis by partner FOR is to consider the following categories of context-aware metrics [7] as illustrated in Figure 2. The concrete metrics that CODECO monitors are provided in Annex I:

- **Computational metrics** refer to internal parameters of a system and are usually available already to K8s. Examples are CPU, memory, as in K8s. These are currently provided by ACM via Prometheus.
- **Network metrics** relate to both functional QoS requirements (e.g., RTT, latency, allocated bandwidth between worker nodes and the master node); and to non-functional QoS/QoE requirements (e.g., mobility, portability). These are in CODECO provided by NetMA.
- **Application metrics** relate with application QoS parameters. For instance, In the context of Industrial IoT critical applications often require minimum and bounded latency within one msec. Tight time synchronization among devices serving a specific application is often a challenge, due to time-aware queuing disciplines that support the exchange of critical traffic. Non-functional requirements, such as a sensitiveness level of an application, or even certification or compliance aspects, may prevent an application to run under specific conditions on a node. These are provided by ACM, via CAM.
- **Data observability metrics** relate with dataset characteristics, e.g., freshness of the data, compliance verification towards a specific location. These are provided by MDM.
- **User behaviour metrics** relate with the user behaviour as a carrier/controller of applications in the far Edge. A common indicator of user behaviour is user location, which is widely applied. Other forms of user behaviour, including user preferences, have been considered, e.g., social interaction, group formation, and social/physical proximity to improve overall system performance and to provide better support for task offloading across the Edge. These metrics are currently not provided in CODECO but expected to be relevant in the context of use cases. These metrics will be made available by Prometheus, via deployment in the CODECO use-cases.

Figure 2: Examples of context-awareness categories and metrics in CODECO.

From the proposed concept and as shall be explained in section 4, several CODECO components collect metrics:

- **Application and user behaviour/preferences - ACM.** This data is obtained during setup of an application deployment via the *CODECO Application Model (CAM)*, which is being designed to capture functional and non-functional requirements from user DEV.
- **Data/System observability – MDM.** MDM can tag events that relate with data and systems observability, e.g., if a dataset is not updated within a specified time, or if a dataset grows to exceed a specified size, a trigger to be generated to schedule application to handle the condition.
- **Network parameters – NetMA.** Via ALTO, NetMA is expected to collect relevant network parameters that assist in a better definition of the infrastructure, beyond the usual view of resources provided in K8s.

2.4 Energy awareness and Greenness Objectives

Energy-awareness in CODECO is expressed through the notion of greenness, which captures sustainability objectives such as reduced energy consumption and lower CO₂ footprint. Rather than providing a single definition, CODECO allows greenness to be defined through customisable metrics that can be combined with other performance objectives, including latency, resilience, and data locality. Greenness metrics are treated as optimisation criteria rather than hard constraints, enabling trade-offs to be made dynamically based on application intent and operational context. By default, and as a potential example, the following energy-awareness metrics are available in CODECO:

- **Node Energy $ne(i)$:** Energy consumed by node i due to all active processes.
- **Link Energy $le(i,j)$:** Energy consumed by node i for transmitting data across egress link j .
- **Network Energy $Le(i)$:** Total energy consumed across all egress links of node i .
- **Flow Energy $Fe(i)$:** Energy associated with application data flows originating from node i .

In addition, use-cases are exploring other metrics, e.g., CO₂ consumption.

2.5 CODECO Mapping to the CEI Continuum

As an orchestration framework, CODECO is capable of operating at the Edge, Edge-to-Edge, Edge-to-Cloud, and far Edge-to-Cloud. Its operation abstracts the management of an Edge-Cloud infrastructure using K8s principles, extended to accommodate mobile, heterogeneous environments with reach to the far Edge. CODECO can operate within a single cluster or across multiple clusters in multi-tenant environments.

In this context, a *cluster* is an abstraction of the K8s concept that may be mapped to a purely Edge environment (including far Edge), an Edge-to-Edge configuration, or an Edge-to-Cloud span. Each cluster integrates a control plane (K8s master node) and a service plane (K8s worker nodes) and is expected to include at least one Edge node.

Single-cluster operation (Figure 3) illustrates three representative mappings. In Cluster 1, the CODECO control plane (ACM, SWM) co-resides with the K8s control plane in the Cloud, while monitoring sub-components of MDM, PDLC, and NetMA are deployed on far and near Edge worker nodes. Cluster 2 demonstrates a near Edge control-plane placement, with worker nodes also running MDM, NetMA, and PDLC sub-components for local learning. Cluster 3 represents a far Edge deployment on constrained hardware, where only NetMA (network monitoring) runs on worker nodes, other components are co-located with the control plane, and MDM is omitted entirely — reflecting that some CODECO components are optional depending on the optimisation objective.

Multi-cluster operation (Figure 4) supports clusters that may be geographically distributed across far Edge, near Edge, and Cloud regions, or span multiple of these tiers simultaneously. CODECO brings CEI awareness to K8s multi-cluster operation by incorporating data, network, and computational context into placement decisions. This allows CODECO to adapt gracefully to constrained far Edge environments and to react to anomalous conditions, such as a stale data workflow or a temporarily congested inter-cluster link, even when the underlying K8s infrastructure would otherwise remain unaware.

Figure 3: CODECO and relation to the CEI continuum, single cluster representation.

Figure 4: CODECO examples for multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments across the CEI continuum.

2.6 Technological Enablers

This section summarizes the key technological enablers being addressed in CODECO, and the reasons for their application, as stated in Table 1.

Table 1: CODECO Technological enablers.

Technology	Description	Application in CODECO
Decentralised AI (RL, MARL)	Distributed and federated learning approaches for adaptive orchestration across multi-tenant environments	PDLC relies on decentralised AI to produce placement and scheduling estimates; outputs are consumed by SWM and NetMA
Edge computing	Architectural principles of Edge and Fog computing underpin CODECO's orchestration model	The entire flexible orchestration of containerised applications reflects Edge computing abstractions
Cross-layer orchestration	Unified treatment of network, compute, and data as a single managed system	MDM, NetMA, and ACM each monitor one infrastructure dimension; PDLC fuses these inputs; SWM uses them for scheduling
Security and privacy	Automation of privacy and security policy enforcement	ACM enforces user-defined security requirements; PDLC applies privacy-by-design AI; NetMA provides secure inter-service connectivity via L2S-M
Cross-layer recontext-awareness	Integration of device usage, application requirements, mobility, and privacy into container management	PDLC uses context-awareness to tune the CEI environment against user-defined performance profiles such as greenness
Network probing	Extension of CEI infrastructure monitoring to include network-layer observability	NetMA collects network metrics consumed by both PDLC and SWM
Network management	Dynamic, isolated connectivity among workloads within and across clusters	NetMA enables flexible overlay path instantiation over the physical underlay network

Technology	Description	Application in CODECO
FaaS	Function-as-a-Service abstraction supporting joint orchestration of compute and networking resources	Addressed within NetMA for federated cluster operation; challenges include function-chaining overhead and data locality integration
Semantic service composition	Semantic abstraction of application structure and requirements	K8s service composition principles are extended in CODECO through CAM, preserving application security and privacy
Configuration management	Automated installation, configuration, and lifecycle management of heterogeneous distributed clusters	ACM provides a single point of entry for CODECO users, minimising the need for manual intervention

3 FC Priorities and Proposed Directions

3.1 FC, Main Challenges

Deploying container orchestration across a federated Cloud–Edge–IoT (CEI) continuum is substantially more demanding than operating within a single administrative domain. Kubernetes, as currently designed, assumes relatively stable, homogeneous clusters under centralised control — assumptions that break down in far Edge environments characterised by intermittent connectivity, constrained resources, heterogeneous tenants, and mobile workloads [6].

The key words "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are to be interpreted as described in IETF RFC 2119 [9]

Based on a broad survey of the literature and of ongoing standardisation work, five challenges stand out as particularly consequential for federated orchestration at the far Edge:

Decentralisation and self-organisation. A cluster federation operating across the CEI continuum MUST tolerate hub unavailability, adapt to variable connectivity, and avoid single points of failure. This requires rethinking how much of the control plane can be pushed toward the Edge without sacrificing governance consistency [8].

Visibility and resource exposure. Multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments MUST support expressive mechanisms for sharing resource and topology information across administrative boundaries without over-exposing sensitive data. An intent-based semantic abstraction that can describe both computational and network capabilities across clusters remains an open design challenge.

Mobility and adaptive networking. At both intra- and inter-cluster levels, networking MUST accommodate mobility, dynamic topologies, and the boundaries of Internet *Autonomous Systems (AS)*. Static overlay configurations are insufficient; SLA-aware, flexible overlay management is RECOMMENDED [32].

Application-oriented semantic composition. Scheduling and rescheduling decisions in a federated environment MUST be grounded in a rich application model that captures microservice dependencies, data locality requirements, and non-functional intents. This is a prerequisite for coherent placement across clusters belonging to different tenants [33][34].

Proactive rescheduling and migration. Standard Kubernetes approaches rely heavily on replication and horizontal scaling. In mobile Edge-Cloud environments, workload *migration*, i.e., moving a microservice from one cluster or node to another is often more appropriate than replication. The trade-offs between these two strategies in constrained environments are not yet well established.

The mentioned challenges are not independent. A control plane designed for the far Edge must simultaneously address visibility, mobility, and semantic abstraction, and the choice of scheduling architecture shapes how each of these concerns can be handled. The following sub-sections examine the state of the art across four priority areas and identify open questions, as well as CODECO directions for federated orchestration.

3.2 Priority 1: Control Plane Decentralisation

3.2.1 The Centralised Baseline and Its Limitations

The dominant model for multi-cluster Kubernetes management is hub-and-spoke: a central Hub cluster administers a set of managed (spoke) clusters, pushing workload manifests, enforcing policies, and aggregating monitoring data. OCM is the leading open-source implementation of this pattern and provides well-defined mechanisms for cluster registration, identity management, policy propagation, and manifest dispatch.

OCM includes several key functional modules. The **Registration** module manages the lifecycle of Managed Clusters, with a registration controller in the hub and a registration agent in each Managed Cluster. The **Placement** module selects appropriate Managed Clusters for workload deployment based on labels or cluster claims, enabling workload distribution across clusters according to criteria such as resource availability. The **Manifest Work** module facilitates the dispatching of Kubernetes resources from the Hub cluster to Managed Clusters, enabling centralised deployment while maintaining visibility into whether resources are applied correctly. **Add-ons** provide additional capabilities such as policy enforcement and advanced scheduling without altering the core architecture.

OCM policies define the desired state for Managed Clusters, comparing current resource state against a desired configuration and enforcing compliance through mechanisms such as "must have," "must not have," or "must only have" directives. Monitoring is supported through integration with Prometheus and Grafana, enabling centralised visibility into cluster health and workload status. Multi-cluster monitoring at federation scale is supported via Thanos, though this is considered an add-on rather than a core OCM capability.

OCM's hub-centric design is well suited to Cloud-hosted deployments where the hub enjoys high availability and low-latency links to Managed Clusters. However, in far Edge environments where Managed Clusters may be geographically isolated, connected via intermittent wireless links, or operating under strict energy budgets continuous dependence on a reachable hub becomes a reliability liability. Network partitions between a Managed Cluster and its hub will interrupt workload placement, rescheduling, and monitoring, precisely at the moments when autonomous local decision-making is most needed. Baldoni et al. make this case explicitly, arguing that a decentralised control plane is a prerequisite for viable far Edge orchestration [29].

It is also relevant to note that, as a Kubernetes tool, OCM does not directly handle inter-cluster networking. It can rely on approaches such as Submariner to provide IP networking between pods and services interconnected across different clusters. OCM's role is mainly in the placement of workloads, while networking concerns are handled separately through additional tools or plugins.

3.2.2 Directions Towards Decentralisation

Two broad directions have been emerging in the research community: **increasing hub resilience through replication and federation** and **increasing the autonomy of Managed Clusters**.

Multi-hub federation. One approach is to deploy multiple OCM hub instances, each governing a subset of Managed Clusters, and to enable hubs to peer with one another. This reduces

the blast radius of a hub failure and can bring governance closer to Edge locations. The main difficulty is maintaining policy consistency and namespace coherence across hub domains and managing workload scheduling when an application's microservices straddle hub boundaries. Hence, a two-layer peering architecture for OCM is an area worth exploring, though significant challenges remain in terms of scalability and workload management.

Managed-cluster autonomy. An alternative and slightly more disruptive direction is to allow Managed Clusters to operate independently for a defined set of functions when hub connectivity is lost. Larsson et al. propose one such design, based on a shared database of CRDs replicated across federated clusters and a distributed resource scheduling mechanism. This enables continued operation during hub disconnection but introduces synchronisation overhead and potential consistency conflicts, especially for time-series data such as network metrics, which CRD-based state does not handle well.

Hybrid peering models. A middle path, advocated by several recent projects including Ligo [38], is to retain a central hub for governance and policy enforcement while enabling direct peer-to-peer communication between Managed Clusters for operational tasks — specifically, workload-level coordination between microservices that span clusters. Under this model, hub availability determines what *can* be deployed, but not what *continues to run*: microservices already placed across clusters can communicate and reschedule locally without hub involvement, provided the inter-cluster networking layer is in place. The key advantage is that each Managed Cluster operates as a standard Kubernetes cluster, independent from the central hub in terms of its own control plane, master nodes, APIs, and workloads. The hub facilitates deployment and monitoring but does not need to serve as a mandatory intermediary for on-going cluster-to-cluster communication.

3.2.3 Open Questions

The following questions drove the research in CODECO:

- At what granularity should autonomy be granted to Managed Clusters — per-cluster, per-neighbourhood, or per-application? The appropriate scope of autonomy is likely to differ across use-case contexts.
- How should conflicts arising from divergent local state be resolved when hub connectivity is restored? Consistency models from distributed systems research (eventual consistency, causal consistency) are candidate approaches, but their applicability to Kubernetes-native constructs has not been validated at scale.
- What networking primitives are required to support peer-level cluster communication independently of the hub? This question is strongly coupled to the networking design choices discussed in Section 3.4.
- To what extent can OCM's existing extension mechanisms (add-ons, manifest work, placement) be leveraged to implement hybrid models, and where do fundamental architectural changes become necessary?

3.2.4 CODECO Directions

CODECO adopts a **hybrid governance model as its foundation**, retaining OCM's hub-and-spoke model as the authoritative governance substrate while progressively increasing the degree of freedom available to Managed Clusters for application-level operations. Two directions are being concurrently pursued. The first concerns increasing the resilience of the Hub layer itself, by exploring multi-hub peering configurations that allow Hub clusters to communicate and collectively manage sets of Managed Clusters. This aligns with recent Ligo developments and provides a foundation for reducing the single-point-of-failure risk in far Edge deployments.

The second direction concerns enabling Managed Clusters to continue microservice placement, rescheduling, and inter-cluster communication even when the hub is temporarily unreachable. The key insight driving this direction is that direct communication between Managed Clusters, mediated by the inter-cluster networking layer, does not require hub involvement: if the necessary network connectivity is in place, application microservices distributed across clusters can continue to operate and even be rescheduled locally without waiting for hub instructions.

CODECO also introduces the concept of *application neighbourhoods* as a scoping mechanism: a bounded, semantically defined set of Managed Clusters relevant to a specific application. Neighbourhoods constrain the coordination space for scheduling, monitoring, and learning, limiting the amount of state that must be shared while still enabling cooperative behaviour. This concept, elaborated in the architectural design (Section 4), is central to CODECO's approach to federated scalability.

3.3 Priority 2: Privacy-preserving Decentralised AI

3.3.1 The Role of AI in Federated Orchestration

Effective placement and rescheduling of microservices across a federated Edge-Cloud infrastructure cannot rely solely on rule-based policies or static thresholds. The infrastructure is too heterogeneous, too dynamic, and too context-dependent. There is therefore a clear motivation for integrating learning-based decision support into federated orchestration — components that can model infrastructure behaviour, predict resource availability, and recommend placement decisions that balance context-awareness in the form of latency, energy, resilience, and data locality [7].

The challenge is doing so without violating the privacy and data-sovereignty constraints that are inherent to multi-tenant, multi-administrative-domain environments. Raw telemetry collected within a Managed Cluster often cannot leave that cluster without explicit permission from its operator. Any federated AI architecture must therefore exchange only aggregate or protected artefacts, not raw observations [20]. This requirement also has an operational dimension: in far Edge environments with intermittent connectivity, architectures that depend on continuous communication with a central training coordinator will fail precisely when the infrastructure is under most stress.

A further important distinction is between *training* and *inference*. Most existing work on federated learning in orchestration contexts focuses on offline or batch training, where model updates are periodically aggregated and redistributed [28]. For real-time orchestration at the far Edge, *inline* (online) training, adapting models continuously as new observations arrive, is also necessary, and its integration with scheduling workflows raises non-trivial design questions.

3.3.2 Federated and Decentralised Learning

The AI/ML community has developed several architectures for collaborative model training without centralising raw data.

Federated learning (FL) is the most mature architecture. In the standard FL setup, each participating node trains a model locally on its own data and periodically shares only model parameters — or compressed updates — with a central aggregator. The aggregator produces an improved global model, which is redistributed to participants. FL has been shown to be effective in scenarios where data distributions are non-i.i.d. across participants, which is precisely the case in a heterogeneous CEI continuum. Its primary limitation is the continued reliance on a central aggregator, which reintroduces a coordination bottleneck and a potential single point of failure — concerns that are magnified in far Edge deployments.

Decentralised federated learning eliminates the central aggregator entirely. Nodes exchange model updates directly with peers, typically in a neighbourhood-constrained fashion. Convergence is slower than centralised FL, but the architecture is more resilient and avoids any single point of trust. Several variants have been proposed, including gossip-based aggregation, where each node periodically exchanges updates with a randomly selected neighbour, and topology-aware aggregation, where the exchange pattern mirrors the cluster federation structure.

Swarm learning extends decentralised FL by using blockchain-based consensus to authenticate and validate model updates, ensuring that no single node can corrupt the shared model. This provides strong integrity guarantees but at significant energy and latency cost — a meaningful drawback in resource-constrained Edge environments [19].

Split neural networks (SplitNNs) offer a complementary approach: rather than training full models at each node, the model is partitioned across nodes, with each node responsible for forward and backward passes through its assigned layers. This reduces the computational burden on individual nodes and avoids sharing raw data but introduces sensitivity to network latency and requires careful management of the cut layer, particularly under the variable connectivity conditions of far Edge deployments.

3.3.3 Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning for Orchestration

Beyond model training, the orchestration problem itself — deciding where to place workloads, when to migrate them, and how to route traffic — can be framed as a sequential decision problem amenable to reinforcement learning (RL). In federated settings, multi-agent RL (MARL) is particularly relevant: each cluster hosts an agent that observes its local state and takes actions to maximise a shared objective [16].

The key design question is how much agents should communicate with one another. Fully independent agents operate on local observations only and are highly scalable but may reach suboptimal equilibria due to coordination failures. Agents that share full state achieve better coordination at the cost of privacy and communication overhead. A middle ground, explored by several recent proposals, is to share only high-level decision signals, e.g., aggregate cost indicators, binary willingness-to-accept values, or compressed representations of local state — rather than raw observations or full model parameters. This auction-style coordination limits information leakage while enabling meaningful inter-agent cooperation.

An important architectural question concerns the role of centralised components within a MARL system. In many MARL designs, a centralised *critic* is used during training to compute value estimates that account for the joint action of all agents, even though each agent acts based only on its local observations at inference time. This *Centralised Training / Decentralised Execution (CTDE)* paradigm preserves operational decentralisation while enabling richer training signals. Whether a CTDE approach is feasible under the connectivity and privacy constraints of a CEI federation is an open question.

A two-step recommendation process has also been proposed in this context: a first step selects a target cluster based on aggregated cluster-level indicators, and a second step identifies specific nodes within that cluster based on local detail. An alternative single-step approach produces node-level recommendations directly, with cluster membership inferred implicitly. The two-step model is more interpretable and aligns more naturally with a hierarchical scheduling architecture; the single-step model is more compact but requires richer local observations [7].

3.3.4 Open Questions

The following questions are highlighted:

- How can inline (online) training be integrated into orchestration workflows without requiring stable connectivity to a central training coordinator? This is essential for far Edge adaptability but has received limited attention in the existing federated learning literature.
- How should the trade-off between update frequency and communication cost be calibrated in decentralised architectures? More frequent updates improve model accuracy but increase bandwidth consumption and may violate privacy budgets.
- How can formal privacy guarantees — such as differential privacy or secure multi-party computation — be applied to model updates without degrading recommendation quality to the point where the AI component becomes unreliable?
- How should learning components handle cluster topology changes — nodes joining or leaving, clusters becoming temporarily unreachable — without requiring full model re-training?
- To what extent can MARL agents coordinate effectively using only high-level decision signals, and what is the minimum communication required to avoid pathological equilibria such as persistent workload oscillation between clusters?

3.3.5 CODECO Directions

CODECO's approach to AI-assisted orchestration is grounded in the principle of *privacy by design*: raw telemetry MUST remain local to the cluster in which it is collected, and only protected learning artefacts — encrypted model weights, aggregated cost indicators — MAY be exchanged with peer clusters or a hub-level coordinator.

The current CODECO design positions a dedicated learning and context-awareness component within the control plane of each Managed Cluster, operating within the scope of an application neighbourhood. This component aggregates local compute, network, and data metrics into compact cost and stability indicators, which are consumed by the scheduling component to inform placement and rescheduling decisions. The separation between *recommendation* and *enforcement* is deliberate: the learning component produces advisory outputs, while final scheduling decisions remain with a deterministic solver. This decoupling improves stability and auditability and avoids the oscillation risks that arise when learning-based components directly control placement.

For decentralised training, CODECO is exploring neighbourhood-scoped federated learning, where clusters within the same application neighbourhood exchange encrypted model weights at defined intervals. This aligns the learning collaboration boundary with the coordination boundary already established for scheduling and monitoring, minimising the number of distinct trust relationships that must be maintained across the federation.

Decentralised learning in CODECO is therefore not used as the main scheduling mechanism, but as a recommendation layer that informs the scheduling process. This avoids retraining scheduling logic when new objectives or constraints are introduced and improves interoperability with Kubernetes-native schedulers.

3.4 Priority 3: Semantic Abstraction and Adaptive Networking

3.4.1 Application-Level Semantic Abstraction

Multi-cluster orchestration requires a machine-readable representation of applications that is expressive enough to capture cross-cluster constraints such as microservice dependencies,

data locality requirements, latency bounds, energy budgets, compliance restrictions while remaining agnostic to the specific cluster or infrastructure on which the application will ultimately execute.

Kubernetes' native YAML-based objects do not provide this level of abstraction. They describe *how* resources should be configured, not *what* an application needs or *why*. Several community proposals attempt to address this gap.

The *Liqo "Big Node"* abstraction creates virtual K8s nodes that act as gateways to remote clusters, allowing a scheduler to treat a federation of clusters as a single, larger cluster. This simplifies cross-cluster deployment significantly, but the abstraction is coarse: it does not expose inter-cluster latency, bandwidth constraints, or data locality information at the granularity needed for microservice-level placement decisions. For applications composed of fine-grained, interdependent microservices with heterogeneous requirements, the big-node approach provides insufficient resolution.

Work by Zheng et al. on multi-tenant *VirtualCluster* [31] and by Sebrechts et al. on service relationship orchestration [32] points toward richer semantic models that can capture relationships between application components and their infrastructure requirements. Both works highlight the difficulty of maintaining these abstractions consistently across clusters belonging to different administrative domains, a problem compounded when clusters join or leave the federation dynamically.

KubeSlice [39] offers a different angle, applying a network-slicing model to federate clusters along service-oriented dimensions rather than physical proximity. This allows tenants to define logical overlays that span exactly the clusters relevant to a given application, without exposing unnecessary topology information to other tenants. The slicing concept, borrowed from SDN and 5G network management, has potential applicability to service-oriented microservice communication in federated environments, though its integration with Kubernetes scheduling workflows requires further investigation.

3.4.2 Inter-Cluster Networking

The networking layer of a cluster federation must address three interrelated problems: how to expose inter-cluster topology and performance metrics to orchestration components; how to establish secure, isolated connectivity between microservices running in different clusters; and how to maintain this connectivity as workloads migrate and network conditions change.

3.4.3 Topology Exposure and ALTO

The *Application-Layer Traffic Optimization (ALTO, RFC 7285)* protocol [14] provides a standardised mechanism for exposing network cost maps — structured representations of latency, bandwidth, and loss metrics between endpoints or groups of endpoints. In a multi-cluster context, each cluster can host an ALTO agent that aggregates intra-cluster metrics and publishes them to a neighbourhood-scoped cost map, which is then consumed by scheduling and re-scheduling components.

A central ALTO instance can aggregate across agents, though this reintroduces a coordination bottleneck. A fully distributed ALTO deployment, where agents peer directly, is architecturally cleaner but requires careful protocol design to ensure map consistency. The hierarchical organisation of ALTO and the feasibility of synchronising metrics across clusters without a central point remain active areas of debate. One suggested approach involves deploying ALTO instances within each cluster to manage localised data while maintaining a lightweight federation-level component to aggregate cross-cluster metrics, allowing for filtered or partial views for specific clusters as needed.

Historically, internal cluster metrics have not been exposed between clusters due to limited necessity, but multi-cluster scenarios now require exposing interconnection details such as

performance metrics and logical topology. Questions arise regarding how clusters should connect — whether in full mesh, hierarchical, or peer-to-peer configurations — and whether specific worker nodes should be designated as "border nodes" to handle inter-cluster connectivity and probing.

In this context, the Internet routing fabric based on ASes provides a reasonable model for defining the administrative reach of a tenant, where one tenant may hold more than one AS. The Hub cluster for a specific set of Managed Clusters may be placed on one AS, while the Managed Clusters may or may not reside on the same AS. Both inter-domain routing and intra-domain routing requirements therefore need to be considered when defining connectivity and information exposure between hub and Managed Clusters.

3.4.4 Secure Overlay Connectivity

Submariner² is the most widely used open-source solution for establishing IP-level connectivity between Kubernetes clusters. It creates encrypted tunnels between designated gateway nodes and provides cross-cluster service discovery. However, Submariner operates at the IP layer and exposes relatively coarse connectivity primitives; it does not natively expose the latency or bandwidth of established tunnels in a form directly consumable by schedulers.

More recent **Layer 2 secure mesh** approaches operate at a lower level, creating virtualised Layer 2 connections between specific pods in different clusters. This provides stronger isolation and greater flexibility in path selection, allowing pods across different nodes in different clusters to interact without regard to their actual positioning but solely based on application demands. The cost is additional control-plane complexity, particularly around lifecycle management of virtual connections as workloads migrate.

Regarding the SDN controller architecture for managing secure inter-cluster connectivity, three broad options have been considered in the literature. The first involves a single SDN controller co-located with the Hub cluster, overseeing the entire federation network. The second has a separate SDN controller within each individual cluster. The third — and most widely favoured for its robustness and scalability — is a hybrid solution where SDN controllers manage networks within specific clusters while synchronising with one another to ensure cohesive network management across the full system. Distributed consensus algorithms such as Raft [13] are relevant for keeping federation-level controller state consistent in this third model.

3.4.5 Reconciling SDN and Kubernetes

A recurring tension in this space is between the dynamic, intent-driven model of Software-Defined Networking and the declarative, resource-oriented model of Kubernetes. Static constructs such as designated border gateway nodes common in early multi-cluster designs are increasingly seen as unnecessary constraints given the programmability that SDN controllers offer. If sufficient information about inter-cluster connectivity is available, and a mechanism within the networking layer exists to establish end-to-end connections between worker nodes in different clusters, the static border node is not required; dynamic configurations enabled by SDN provide this capability more flexibly.

The application of these approaches needs careful delineation of roles: SDN controllers, ALTO agents, and other networking components must have clearly defined responsibilities to avoid architectural conflicts.

3.4.6 Open Questions

The following questions remain open:

² <https://github.com/submariner-io/submariner>

- How should a comprehensive inter-cluster topology map be constructed and maintained — centralised, for consistency, or distributed, for resilience — and what are the implications of each choice for scheduling quality and privacy?
- Which metrics **MUST** be exposed across cluster boundaries, and which **SHOULD** remain local? Defining the minimal sufficient information set is critical for both scalability and data sovereignty.
- How should inter-cluster overlay connectivity be managed during workload migration? When a pod migrates from one node or cluster to another, the network configurations tied to the original node must be updated to reflect the new location, including configurations managed by L2-level overlay technologies.
- How should inter-domain probing be handled when individual cluster-level components have limited scope and cannot construct a full topology map from local information alone?
- Can the slicing approach of KubeSlice or similar tools be operationally integrated with Kubernetes scheduling workflows, and what is the performance overhead of doing so at CEI scale?

3.4.7 CODECO Directions

CODECO's approach to semantic abstraction starts from a YAML-based application model that specifies microservices, service dependencies, and performance intents, e.g., energy efficiency, level of resilience, security without prescribing the cluster or node on which any component will execute. This model is intentionally agnostic to whether an application is deployed within a single cluster or across multiple clusters, enabling seamless migration from local to federated execution.

For the federation infrastructure layer, CODECO explores semantic abstraction approaches inspired by the Liqo virtual node concept but adapted for microservice-level deployment: rather than abstracting entire clusters as single virtual nodes, the goal is to abstract from the perspective of an application and its microservices, the set of clusters that are most suitable to host specific components. This application-centric cluster abstraction remains in early design stages but presents a promising direction for simplifying cluster management in far Edge environments with constrained and variable resources.

For networking, CODECO addresses exposure and connectivity at two distinct layers aligned with the OCM hub-and-spoke structure: across Hub clusters for inter-hub coordination, and across Managed Clusters for peer-to-peer application-level communication. ALTO-based cost maps are being adopted as the primary mechanism for exposing inter-cluster network metrics, with neighbourhood-scoped agents aggregating underlay and overlay measurements into unified cost representations consumable by scheduling components. For secure connectivity, a Layer 2 secure mesh approach is being pursued to provide isolated inter-cluster communication channels for application workloads, integrated with a hybrid SDN control plane that combines per-cluster controllers with a federation-level synchronisation mechanism. The network management and probing approach follows a progressive design that can accommodate tenant involvement and different administrative domains at an Internet AS level.

3.5 Priority 4: Federated Scheduling

3.5.1 The Design Space

Scheduling in a federated cluster environment differs from single-cluster scheduling in a fundamental way: the scheduler must jointly determine *which cluster* should host each microservice and *which node within that cluster* the microservice should run on. These two decisions are interdependent: a node-level placement that is optimal within a cluster may be infeasible

or suboptimal when the inter-cluster communication requirements of the full application are considered.

A key design difference in this context is the application-centric perspective that a federated orchestration framework must embrace. While K8s is primarily concerned with managing clusters and infrastructure, a framework targeting the CEI continuum must treat applications and their microservices as first-class entities that may be distributed across multiple clusters belonging to different tenants, including clusters at the far Edge that may not be geographically or hop-distance close to one another. This flexibility in cluster operation, where latency and proximity requirements are treated with more nuance than the rigid avoidance of distant clusters typical in standard Kubernetes deployments, is a distinctive requirement of CEI federated scheduling.

Furthermore, in far Edge deployments the scheduler must account for migration as a first-class operation, rather than treating it as an exceptional recovery mechanism. Unlike replication-based scaling, migration moves a workload from one location to another, requiring careful coordination with the networking layer to update connectivity configurations without service interruption. The debate on the relative merits of migration versus replication in constrained CEI environments is ongoing and constitutes an important design question for federated schedulers. Four broad scheduling architectures have been explored in the literature: centralised, hierarchical, decentralised, and hybrid. Each makes different trade-offs between information completeness, scalability, latency, and resilience.

3.5.2 Centralised Scheduling

A centralised scheduler maintains a global view of resources, connectivity, and workload state across all clusters in the federation, and makes all placement decisions from a single point.

Firmament [40] proposed by Gog et al., is the most studied centralised scheduler for large-scale cluster environments. It models the cluster as a directed flow network and uses *Minimum Cost Maximum Flow (MCMF)* to find globally optimal pod placements. Firmament supports multiple scheduling policies, for instance, load-spreading, network-aware placement, and a Quincy-derived data-locality policy, and has been validated on Google production workload traces from 12,500-machine clusters, as well as on local 40-machine homogeneous clusters. Evaluation metrics include scheduling success rate, scheduling time, solution cost, and task response time; Firmament consistently outperforms the Quincy baseline on these metrics. To connect Firmament with K8s, the Poseidon mediator layer translates Kubernetes resource requests into Firmament's flow network format and converts Firmament's placement decisions into Kubernetes pod bindings.

Firmament's limitations are significant in a CEI context, however. It does not natively handle mobility, intermittent connectivity, or geographically distributed micro-clusters. Tasks with dependent placement constraints must be scheduled sequentially, which limits throughput when applications have complex inter-microservice dependency graphs. In a federated Edge-Cloud setting, maintaining the global state required for Firmament's flow network would impose prohibitive communication overhead and would create a single point of failure — the opposite of what far Edge resilience requires.

3.5.3 Hierarchical Scheduling

Hierarchical schedulers decompose the placement problem across levels, each handling a different granularity of decision.

Megha [41] introduces the distinction between a *Global Master (GM)* and *Local Masters (LMs)*. The GM makes cluster-level placement decisions based on periodic updates from LMs, which maintain current knowledge of node-level resource availability within their respective clusters. The GM's view is intentionally stale, capturing the aggregate state of the federation at a

coarser timescale, while LMs enforce decisions locally with up-to-date information. This design elegantly separates concerns: the GM needs only aggregate cluster descriptors, while fine-grained placement is left to LMs who can verify and adapt decisions in real time.

Megha uses a simple round-robin algorithm and bitwise vector operations to match placement constraints and has been evaluated with production workload traces across data centre sizes ranging from 120 to 50,000 nodes. Its virtual partitioning — where each cluster is divided into subsets managed by specific GMs — provides load balancing across GMs and limits each GM's state management scope. The main operational challenge is handling inconsistency: the GM may assign a workload to a resource that the LM subsequently finds unavailable. Megha handles this with a repartitioning mechanism, but conflicts under high utilisation can lead to cascading failures. When a GM assigns a task to a resource that is unavailable by the time the assignment reaches the LM, the LM issues a failure message and provides its current partition state; the overhead of this reconciliation process increases with utilisation.

PHARE [42] addresses multi-component application scheduling across federated edge clusters explicitly. PHARE assigns each microservice an importance factor based on its resource demands (CPU, bandwidth) and inter-service communication requirements and prioritises the placement of the most constrained services first. This greedy-by-difficulty strategy reduces the likelihood of partial placement failures, since the hardest-to-place microservices are handled before easier ones have consumed available capacity. PHARE operates in a decentralised fashion at the cluster level where each cluster scheduler decides independently whether to accept or offload a microservice based on local state and uses peer-to-peer communication for small federations or a centralised metrics aggregation point for larger ones.

It is noted that FluidOS³ is exploring a hierarchical approach with the concept of a super node to address scalability issues, drawing inspiration from PHARE's principles without directly adopting its algorithms. The question of when decentralisation is beneficial and when it introduces unacceptable overhead remains open in this line of work.

3.5.4 Decentralised Scheduling

Fully decentralised schedulers eliminate the global coordinator entirely, relying instead on local decisions and lightweight coordination protocols between peer schedulers.

Sparrow [36] developed at UC Berkeley, employs a sampling strategy based on the "power of two choices" from randomised load balancing: to schedule a workload, a Sparrow scheduler probes a randomly selected subset of worker nodes and places the workload on the least-loaded of the probed nodes using late binding. This approach achieves near-optimal scheduling latency and throughput under high load, with no shared state and minimal communication overhead. Sparrow's limitations in a federated Edge-Cloud context are, however, substantial. It assumes a homogeneous cluster where all nodes are equally accessible; it does not model inter-node or inter-cluster communication costs; and its random probing strategy provides no mechanism for expressing application-level placement preferences such as data locality or latency constraints. It is best understood as an existence proof that decentralised scheduling can match centralised performance on throughput-oriented workloads, not as a complete solution for cross-layer federated orchestration.

Tarcil [35] relies on a hybrid shared-state approach. Schedulers work in parallel, per cluster, and rely on a shared state server and specific resource units. Specific application workloads are assigned to a node by a scheduling agent, and each time a decision is performed, the scheduler informs the control plane. While this design is closely aligned with hierarchical scheduling approaches, conflicts may occur due to data synchronisation across clusters. An

³ <https://fluidos.eu/>

improved version of Tarcil addressing these synchronisation concerns is available from Ungureanu et al. [34].

Pigeon [15] provides decentralised scheduling by dividing worker nodes into fixed resource encapsulations. While offering true decentralisation, this approach may not be readily applicable to frameworks that require joint awareness of compute, network, and data constraints, as the fixed encapsulation model limits the flexibility needed for cross-layer placement decisions. The more fundamental challenge with decentralised scheduling in federated environments is the risk of pathological forwarding behaviour: without any visibility into the state of peer clusters, a local scheduler that cannot satisfy an application request may forward it to a neighbouring cluster, which in turn forwards it further, potentially creating loops or indefinitely deferred placements. Pure blind forwarding, analogous to peer-to-peer networking, is explicitly identified as an approach that **SHOULD NOT** be followed in production federated orchestration due to non-deterministic deployment times and loop risks. Several strategies for mitigating this are discussed in the literature — aggregated cost maps, bounded forwarding horizons, partial topology views — but none has been conclusively validated at realistic CEI scale.

3.5.5 Hybrid Scheduling

Given the limitations of purely centralised and purely decentralised designs, hybrid schedulers have attracted significant interest.

A two-layer architecture is the most common pattern. A lightweight, low-frequency global scheduler handles cross-cluster distribution — deciding which clusters should host which microservices — while per-cluster local schedulers handle node-level placement with full local state. The global scheduler requires only aggregate cluster descriptors (total capacity, available bandwidth on inter-cluster links, compliance labels) rather than per-node detail, substantially reducing state management overhead.

A refinement of this pattern is the **look-ahead** or **probe-based meta-scheduler**: before committing a placement, the global scheduler queries each candidate cluster to report on which subsets of the application it can accommodate given its current state. This eliminates a major source of rescheduling in standard hierarchical designs, where initial placements based on stale aggregate information frequently fail local verification. The cost is an additional round-trip per placement decision; the benefit is a significant reduction in failed placements and the associated rollback overhead.

SDN plays a complementary role in hybrid scheduling designs: by providing the scheduler with high-level network performance metrics (latency, bandwidth) via the networking layer, SDN can reduce the amount of network state the scheduler itself must maintain, enabling informed placement decisions without requiring a complete real-time view of the physical network topology. A fine-tuned interplay between the networking management layer and the scheduler allows the orchestration system to manage network changes without full real-time network visibility, simplifying the scheduling process [30].

3.5.6 Summary and Comparative Assessment

Table 2 summarises the key characteristics of the reviewed scheduling approaches.

Table 2: Federated scheduling, comparison of studied approaches on their characteristics.

Approach	Global visibility	Scalability	Latency	Edge suitability	Application awareness
Firmament (centralised)	Full	Moderate	High	Low	High (multi-policy)
Megha (hierarchical)	Partial (aggregate)	Good	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate

Approach	Global visibility	Scalability	Latency	Edge suitability	Application awareness
PHARE (hierarchical, decentralised)	Partial (peer)	Good	Moderate	Good	High
Sparrow (decentralised, sampling)	None	Excellent	Very low	Moderate	Low
Two-layer hybrid (meta-scheduler)	Aggregate only	Good	Moderate	Good	High (with probe)
Tarcil (hybrid shared state)	Partial (shared)	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate

For a federated orchestration framework targeting the CEI continuum, a two-layer hybrid design appears most promising: it limits the global state that must be maintained, tolerates managed-cluster autonomy during hub disconnections, and can incorporate application-level constraints through aggregate cluster descriptors augmented by on-demand probing. The choice between providing node-level recommendations aggregated into a cluster perspective versus direct cluster-level recommendations ultimately depends on the level of detail needed for each specific workload placement while maintaining manageable data exposure.

3.5.7 Open Questions

The following questions remain unresolved:

- What is the minimal sufficient aggregate cluster descriptor? The descriptor must be rich enough to enable well-informed cross-cluster placement decisions but lean enough to avoid prohibitive communication overhead and data-sovereignty concerns.
- How should the global and local scheduler layers interact when application constraints span inter-cluster communication channels? Validating a channel constraint requires information from both the source and destination cluster, introducing a distributed verification problem.
- To what extent can decentralised scheduling be made loop-free and convergent without reintroducing a centralised coordinator? Partial visibility approaches (aggregated cost maps, bounded forwarding) are promising but have not been formally validated.
- How should migration be treated relative to replication in constrained far Edge environments? The operational cost of migration (network reconfiguration, state transfer) must be weighed against the resource cost of maintaining replicas, and this trade-off is highly context-dependent.
- How can scheduling decisions account for the energy consumption of inter-cluster communication, not just node-level compute energy? This cross-layer awareness is essential for greenness objectives but is not addressed by any of the reviewed schedulers.

3.5.8 CODECO Directions

CODECO's scheduling design follows a **two-layer federated model**. A hub-level scheduler handles cross-cluster workload distribution, using aggregate cluster representations to determine which clusters should host which microservices. Per-cluster local schedulers then handle node-level placement within their respective clusters, using full local state. The hub-level scheduler consumes recommendations from the learning and context-awareness component alongside topology and connectivity information from the networking layer integrating these inputs into placement decisions that respect application QoS constraints, data locality requirements, and greenness objectives.

The separation between recommendation and enforcement is maintained at the scheduling layer as well: the learning component produces cost and stability indicators, while the scheduler applies deterministic placement logic informed by those indicators. This improves auditability and reduces oscillation risk.

To address the probe overhead problem identified in Section 3.5.5, CODECO limits the scheduling search space to a bounded application neighbourhood, computed at deployment time based on application requirements and infrastructure characteristics. Rather than querying all Managed Clusters in the federation, the hub-level scheduler operates only within this bounded scope, reducing both communication overhead and state management complexity. Within the neighbourhood, clusters are ordered based on the availability of learning-layer recommendations and inter-cluster link characteristics, and L2 placement problems are solved sequentially per cluster rather than globally, avoiding the need to maintain a complete, synchronised global state.

Migration is treated as a first-class operation in CODECO: the scheduler handles stateful migration using the same three-phase procedure as initial placement, and reserves resources at the destination before terminating the source instance, enabling fast cut-over and reducing the risk of service disruption. Migration triggers are provided by the learning and context-awareness component based on changes in infrastructure conditions, user-defined performance profiles, or application intent updates.

4 CODECO Federated Architecture

The CODECO federated architecture is designed to support application-centric orchestration across the CEI continuum. Rather than managing clusters as isolated execution units, CODECO treats applications and their microservices as first-class entities that may be distributed, migrated, and adapted across multiple clusters over time.

4.1 Architectural Assumptions and Requirements

The design of CODECO is grounded in a set of architectural assumptions (Table 3) and requirements (Table 4) that define the operational boundaries of the framework and guide its modelling as a flexible, extensible orchestration system.

For the description of the requirements, this deliverable follows following the IETF principles: The key words "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are to be interpreted as described in IETF RFC 2119 [9].

Table 3: List of CODECO architectural assumptions.

Name	Description
A1	The user MUST have a running K8s cluster with at least one master node and two worker nodes.
A2	The master node in the cluster MUST at least have a connection to one worker node.
A3	Prometheus MUST be active in the selected cluster.
A4	The user MUST provide an initial description of the application, based on the CODECO Application Model
A5	Intermittent connectivity may be experienced in the K8s infrastructure e.g., due to mobility or constrained node energy.

Table 4: List of CODECO architectural requirements.

Name	Description
R1	CODECO interfaces SHOULD be based on CRDs.

Name	Description
R2	QoS networking models in CODECO are RECOMMENDED to follow an existing model, e.g., DiffServ
R3	In CODECO, concerning data, the strict rules, and regulations for data due to GDPR MUST be considered.
R4	To run applications, users MUST adapt the CAM to the specific selected application.
R5	It is RECOMMENDED to use the proposed scheduler, SWM.
R6	Connections between micro-services MUST be secure.
R7	CODECO components MUST be built in a modular way, based on containerized micro-services.
R8	The CODECO framework MUST be easily deployed in single and federated clusters.
R9	CODECO MUST be prepared to use heterogeneous networking technologies, e.g., Ethernet, Wi-Fi.
R10	CODECO MUST be user-friendly.
R11	CODECO MUST provide users with the adequate expectations and with feedback on the infrastructure being managed.
R12	CODECO MUST support efficient replication.
R13	CODECO SHOULD support efficient migration.
R14	CODECO MUST be resilient to malicious attacks
R15	CODECO MUST be energy-efficient by design.
R16	The CODECO framework SHOULD be flexible enough to allow for the use of other OSS schedulers

4.2 Core Architecture Components

A functional representation of CODECO and its open-source components is provided in Figure 5. CODECO is structured around five core components, each responsible for a distinct orchestration concern.

ACM (Advanced Configuration and Management) is the sole interface between CODECO and the user. It handles application setup and runtime management across the CEI continuum, from the far Edge to the Cloud. The user — either an application developer (DEV) or a cluster manager (MGT) — submits application descriptions through the CODECO Application Model (CAM), which specifies application requirements, microservice dependencies, and target performance profiles (e.g., greenness, resilience). ACM installs and configures the entire CODECO framework, monitors the computational (system) infrastructure via Prometheus, and exposes this information to other components.

MDM (Metadata Management) provides data and system observability to the rest of the framework, treating data as an integral part of the application workload. MDM integrates observability perspectives from multiple categories — application, system, network — at different points in the CODECO operational workflow, enabling other components to detect and respond to relevant infrastructure changes.

SWM (Scheduling and Workload Migration) handles the scheduling and rescheduling of application workloads based on the requirements expressed in the CAM. SWM relies on a graph-based optimisation approach that, in contrast to the standard Kubernetes filtering-and-scoring mechanism, seeks an optimal match between application requirements and available resources across computational, network, and data dimensions. SWM is a control-plane component co-located with ACM and the Kubernetes control plane.

PDLC (Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness) is at the heart of the CODECO-orchestration logic. Drawing on infrastructure data collected by ACM, NetMA, and MDM, PDLC serves two functions: it produces an aggregated cost view of a target performance profile for the available infrastructure, consumed by SWM for workload placement; and it provides an estimate of overall system stability using privacy-preserving decentralised learning. PDLC is designed to operate on both Kubernetes master and worker nodes.

Figure 5: The CODECO Framework modular and Kubernetes interoperable components.

NetMA (Network Management and Adaptation) provides network awareness to CODECO and manages secure connectivity across pods. Network awareness is delivered via the Network State Management (NSM) sub-component for network probing, and network metric exposure across multi-cluster environments is based on the ALTO protocol [8]. Secure connectivity is provided via L2S-M. NetMA is the component responsible for bridging Software-Defined Networking (SDN) with Kubernetes.

The CODECO components enable a cross-layer observability model: NetMA monitors the networking infrastructure; MDM monitors the data infrastructure; and ACM monitors the computational infrastructure via Prometheus. Each CODECO component is implemented as a set of independent, containerised microservices following a modular architecture, allowing components to work independently or alongside other orchestration frameworks with minimal adaptation. The management functions and their corresponding CODECO components, in the federated cluster (FC) configuration, are summarised in Table 5.

Table 5: Management functions and component mapping.

Management Function	CODECO Components
Intent and Policy Management	ACM-FC (CAM), OCM Hub
Scope and Federation Management	Neighbourhood Composer (CNC), ACM-FC Neighbourhood Manager
Decision Support and Context-awareness	PDLC-FC (CA, GNNs, MARL)
Scheduling and Migration Enforcement	SWM-FC (SWM-L1, SWM-L2)
Network Configuration and Connectivity	NetMA-FC (NSM, Nemesys-FC, Secure Connectivity)
Data Governance and Data Awareness	MDM-FC (Metadata Graph, Connectors, API)

4.3 Management Layers and Decision Timescales

CODECO structures management decisions across three temporal layers, positioning components according to their functional role and the timescale at which they operate.

The **governance layer** operates at long timescales, defining intent, policy, and federation membership. Components operating predominantly at this layer include ACM-FC and the OCM Hub, which establish the authoritative desired state of the system and enforce organisational and regulatory policies across the federation.

The **coordination layer** operates at medium timescales, scoping orchestration through application neighbourhoods. PDLC-FC and SWM-FC span this layer, enabling adaptive behaviour without violating global policies. Neighbourhood composition and learning collaboration occur here.

The **execution layer** operates at short timescales within Managed Clusters, enforcing placement, migration, and network configuration decisions using fresh local context. This layer operates autonomously and continues to function even when connectivity to the Hub is temporarily unavailable.

4.4 Federation Context and Control Structure

CODECO relies on OCM as the foundation for federated coordination. A minimal deployment consists of one Hub cluster, and one or more MCs OCM provides cluster registration, identity management, policy distribution, and manifest dispatch, establishing a common governance layer across the federation.

CODECO does not assume continuous, low-latency connectivity between the Hub and all Managed Clusters. It adopts a hybrid control-plane model: the Hub remains the authoritative source of desired state and policy enforcement, while MCs retain sufficient autonomy to continue microservice placement, rescheduling, and inter-cluster communication during Hub disconnections. This design preserves governance consistency while enabling resilient operation at the far Edge. The positioning of CODECO components across federated clusters, based on the OCM Hub-and-spoke model, is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: CODECO components, positioning across federated clusters based on the Hub-and-spoke model of OCM. Green arrows: user to CODECO logic; red arrows: CODECO observability interfaces; orange arrows: Hub-to-spoke control plane; blue arrows: inter-Managed Cluster communication

4.5 Application Neighbourhoods and Federated Partitioning

To control complexity and improve scalability, CODECO introduces the concept of *application neighbourhoods*. A neighbourhood is a bounded, semantic grouping of Managed Clusters selected for a specific application based on its requirements, performance objectives, and contextual constraints. Each application is associated with a single neighbourhood, while a Managed Cluster may belong to multiple neighbourhoods concurrently.

Neighbourhoods define the coordination scope for scheduling, monitoring data exchange, learning collaboration, and inter-cluster communication. By limiting coordination to application-relevant subsets of clusters, CODECO avoids global state dissemination, reduces overhead, and improves scalability. Neighbourhoods are computed at deployment time and are expected to remain stable during normal operation, although re-evaluation may be triggered by sustained performance degradation, resource depletion, or environmental instability.

To further reduce orchestration overhead, CODECO decouples *space partitioning* from *neighbourhood selection*. Similarity-based clustering of Managed Clusters is performed periodically to establish coarse partitions, while application-specific neighbourhood selection is restricted to the most relevant subset at deployment time. This separation lowers computational and communication costs while preserving adaptivity to changing conditions.

4.6 Semantic Application Abstraction and Observability

Users interact with CODECO exclusively through ACM-FC by submitting applications described using the CODECO Application Model (CAM). CAM is a YAML-based semantic abstraction that specifies microservices, service dependencies, and performance intents — including latency, energy efficiency, resilience, and compliance. It is intentionally agnostic to

whether an application is deployed within a single cluster or across multiple clusters, allowing seamless migration from local to federated execution.

The `spec` section of CAM defines application structure and requirements, while the `status` section is continuously updated by ACM-FC with runtime observability information, providing the user with a consistent view of application and infrastructure state.

4.7 Component Placement Across the Federation

CODECO components are distributed across the federation according to their functional roles and temporal requirements:

- **ACM-FC** runs in the Hub cluster, with lightweight agents deployed in each Managed Cluster.
- **PDLC-FC** instances operate in the control planes of Managed Clusters belonging to a neighbourhood.
- **SWM-FC** is split into a global coordination layer (SWM-L1) hosted in the Hub and local execution layers (SWM-L2) deployed in each Managed Cluster.
- **NetMA-FC** spans the federation, with monitoring agents close to workloads and inter-domain connectivity orchestrated at the Hub level.
- **MDM-FC** is typically instantiated per neighbourhood to manage application-relevant metadata.

This placement ensures centralised governance while keeping monitoring, learning, and execution close to the resources they manage.

4.8 Component Interaction and AI-Driven Decisions

Once a CAM is deployed, ACM-FC orchestrates the activation of all CODECO components. Monitoring data from NetMA-FC, MDM-FC, and ACM-FC is collected and exposed through Prometheus. PDLC-FC aggregates these cross-layer observations and produces context-aware cost and stability estimates, which are delivered to SWM-FC as recommendations.

SWM-FC integrates PDLC-FC recommendations with application constraints and real-time infrastructure conditions to determine placement, migration, and rescheduling decisions. Network configuration instructions are forwarded to NetMA-FC, which establishes secure overlays and exposes updated network metrics. MDM-FC continuously updates data-related constraints and metadata, ensuring that orchestration decisions respect compliance, locality, and data mobility requirements throughout the application lifecycle.

The reference architectures for single-cluster and federated-cluster operation are provided in Figures 7 and 8 respectively.

Figure 7: The CODECO reference architecture, single cluster operation.

Figure 8: The CODECO reference architecture, FC operation.

5 CODECO Workflow Examples

This section aims at describing, from a user perspective, how CODECO is installed, how applications are deployed across a federated infrastructure, and how the system manages applications once they are running. The goal is to provide a concrete, step-by-step picture of CODECO in operation, including the sequence of actions taken by each component and the interactions between them.

Before describing the workflows, it is useful to establish a basic conceptual framing. In a federated cluster environment, the infrastructure consists of multiple independent Kubernetes clusters — groups of computing nodes managed as a unit — distributed across different locations. Some clusters may reside in a data centre (Cloud), others at intermediate network locations (near Edge), and others on constrained devices close to end users or sensors (far Edge), as has been explained in section 2.5. CODECO's task is to take an application described at a high level by its developer and determine how to deploy, monitor, and adapt it across this distributed infrastructure, without requiring the developer to manually manage each cluster.

5.1 CODECO Installation and Deployment

Installing CODECO is itself a multi-step process, because CODECO must be set up not just on a single machine but coordinated across an entire federation of clusters. A developer (**DEV**) retrieves the CODECO open-source software from the official repository and follows the installation guidelines. The prerequisite is an operational OCM environment, that is, at least one Hub cluster (the central coordination point) and one or more MCs holding the nodes where application workloads will eventually run. The installation process unfolds in three sequential phases, illustrated in Figure 9 to Figure 11.

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Phase 1: Operator Deployment

The first phase establishes the governance and control infrastructure across the federation. This is illustrated in Figure 9. The DEV begins by setting up the Hub cluster and registering the Managed Clusters (MC1, MC2, etc) with the Hub via OCM. This registration process is analogous to introducing each cluster to a central registry: the Hub learns of the existence, identity, and initial capabilities of each Managed Cluster, and the Managed Clusters receive the credentials they need to accept instructions from the Hub.

Once the infrastructure is in place, the DEV requests the deployment of the CODECO Operator on the Hub. The CODECO Operator is ACM-FC. It acts as the installation manager for the entire CODECO framework: it knows which components need to be deployed, in which order, and on which clusters. Concurrently, the Hub initialises two key services: the CAM engine (ACM-FC), which is responsible for parsing and validating application descriptions submitted by the developer, and the *Neighbourhood Composer (CNC)*, which will later determine which subset of Managed Clusters is most appropriate for a given application.

At the end of Phase 1, the governance infrastructure is in place: the Hub has authority over all registered Managed Clusters, and the core control services are active.

Figure 9: Sequence diagram: Phase 1, Operator deployment phase across federated clusters.

Phase 2: Component Deployment

The second phase deploys all CODECO functional components across the Hub and the Managed Clusters. This is illustrated in Figure 10, which shows the sequential deployment of each component initiated by the ACM-FC Hub.

The deployment sequence proceeds as follows:

Deploy Scheduler (SWM-L1 at the Hub). The scheduling coordinator is deployed at the Hub level. This is the component that will later make cross-cluster workload placement decisions — determining which cluster should host which part of an application based on resource availability, network conditions, and application requirements.

Deploy NetMA Controller (NetMA IDCO at the Hub). The network management controller is deployed at the Hub. This component will later coordinate inter-cluster secure connectivity and manage the networking overlay that allows microservices running in different clusters to communicate with one another.

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Deploy MDM Core (MDM-FC at the Hub). The metadata management core is deployed at the Hub. This component maintains a graph of metadata structured information about data assets, their locations, freshness, compliance properties, and relationships to running services that will later inform placement decisions.

Connect to Managed Clusters (MC1, MC2). The Hub establishes connections to the registered Managed Clusters, verifying reachability and preparing them to receive component deployments.

Deploy SWM-L2 (at each Managed Cluster). The local scheduling executor is deployed in each Managed Cluster. While SWM-L1 at the Hub makes cluster-level distribution decisions, SWM-L2 at each Managed Cluster handles the fine-grained placement of workloads on specific nodes within that cluster.

Deploy Probes and Overlay (NetMA-FC at each Managed Cluster). Network monitoring agents (probes) and the inter-cluster secure overlay networking infrastructure are deployed in each Managed Cluster. The probes measure network performance metrics — latency, bandwidth, packet loss, and energy consumption — while the overlay establishes encrypted tunnels for secure communication between clusters.

Deploy PDLC (PDLC-FC at each Managed Cluster). The context-awareness and learning component is deployed in each Managed Cluster. PDLC will continuously aggregate local infrastructure metrics and produce recommendations for the scheduler, accounting for compute load, network conditions, data constraints, and user-defined performance profiles.

Deploy MDM Connectors (at each Managed Cluster). Lightweight metadata collection agents are deployed in each Managed Cluster. These connectors feed local metadata, i.e., information about running pods, data assets, compliance status into the Hub-level metadata graph maintained by MDM-FC.

At the end of Phase 2, the full CODECO framework is operational across the federation.

Figure 10: Sequence diagram: CODECO Component deployment phase.

Phase 3: Runtime Monitoring Activation

Once all components are deployed, continuous monitoring loops are activated across the federation. This phase is not a discrete event but an ongoing operational state that persists throughout the lifetime of any deployed application.

NetMA-FC in each Managed Cluster begins publishing network metrics — delay, jitter, and energy consumption — and providing real-time network state information via K8s CRs that

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other components can read. MDM connectors begin pushing metadata updates to the Hub-level metadata graph, which is then exposed for queries by other components. ACM-FC at the Hub begins monitoring user-defined application preferences and behaviours, using this information to adapt CODECO's control logic at runtime. These continuous data streams form the observability foundation on which all subsequent application deployment and adaptation decisions are based.

5.2 Deploying an Application Across a Federated CEI Environment

Once CODECO is installed and the monitoring infrastructure is active, the user DEV can start an application deployment. The DEV does not specify which clusters or nodes should host the application's components, this is CODECO's responsibility. Instead, the developer describes *what* the application needs: which microservices it consists of, how they depend on one another, and what performance requirements must be met (latency bounds, data locality constraints, energy efficiency targets, resilience requirements). This description is expressed in the CAM, a structured YAML document accessible via the CLI or via the CODECO Web-based GUI. The deployment workflow proceeds through the following steps:

Step 1 — Submission and validation of the CAM. The developer submits the CAM to ACM-FC at the Hub. ACM-FC validates the description, checking that it is syntactically correct, that all referenced microservices are properly specified, and that the stated requirements are internally consistent.

Step 2 — Neighbourhood selection. The Neighbourhood Composer (CNC) determines which subset of Managed Clusters — the *application neighbourhood* — is most appropriate for hosting the application. This selection considers the application's requirements (latency, data locality, compliance constraints) alongside the current state of the Managed Clusters (available resources, network connectivity, geographic distribution). The neighbourhood is a bounded, application-specific coordination scope: only the clusters within it will exchange monitoring data and participate in scheduling decisions for this application.

Step 3 — Initialisation of PDLC-FC agents. PDLC-FC instances in the clusters belonging to the selected neighbourhood are activated for this application. They begin aggregating local infrastructure metrics and producing cost and stability indicators that reflect how well each cluster and each node within it could serve the application's requirements. These indicators are expressed in terms of user-defined performance profiles — for example, how green, resilient, or low-latency the deployment would be if a given placement decision were made.

Step 4 — Federated placement and channel assignment. SWM-FC at the Hub, informed by the PDLC-FC recommendations and by the network topology information provided by NetMA-FC, determines the placement of each microservice: which cluster it should run on, and which node within that cluster. SWM-FC also determines the communication channels between microservices — the network paths that will carry traffic between components running in different clusters — and verifies that the bandwidth and latency requirements of these channels can be satisfied.

Step 5 — Network provisioning and secure connectivity setup. NetMA-FC provisions the inter-cluster secure overlay connections required by the placement. Encrypted tunnels are established between the relevant clusters, and network paths are configured to align with the placement decisions made in Step 4. The application microservices are then instantiated as containers (pods) on their designated nodes.

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At the end of this workflow, the application is running across the federated infrastructure, with all components in their assigned locations and all inter-component communication channels secured and operational.

5.3 Management of Applications During Runtime

Once deployed, CODECO does not simply leave the application to run unattended. It continuously observes both application behaviour and the state of the underlying infrastructure and adapts the deployment proactively when conditions change. This continuous management loop is illustrated in Figure 11. At runtime, three streams of observability data flow continuously into PDLC-FC: **Network metrics** from NetMA-FC in each Managed Cluster: real-time measurements of latency, jitter, bandwidth, packet loss, and link energy consumption, published as Kubernetes Custom Resources and via Prometheus. **Metadata updates** from MDM Connectors: compliance status, data locality information, and data freshness metrics, exposed through the metadata knowledge graph. **Application and infrastructure state** from ACM-FC: the current placement of all microservices, resource utilisation on each node, and any changes in user-defined preferences or application intent.

Figure 11: Sequence diagram: Runtime Monitoring Loop.

PDLC-FC continuously processes these inputs and maintains up-to-date cost and stability estimates for the current deployment. Under normal operating conditions, these estimates confirm that the deployment is performing within the required parameters and no action is taken.

When a triggering condition arises, for example, a network link becomes congested, a node becomes overloaded, energy consumption on a cluster exceeds a greenness threshold, or the developer updates the application's performance requirements, ACM-FC signals the need for re-evaluation. This trigger initiates a rescheduling cycle: **PDLC-FC** updates its cost estimates based on the new conditions and publishes revised placement recommendations. **SWM-FC** receives these recommendations and initiates a new placement computation. It determines whether the existing deployment can be adjusted with minor changes or whether one or more microservices need to be migrated to different nodes or clusters. If migration is required, **SWM-FC** follows the same three-phase procedure as initial placement: it reserves resources at the

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new target location, establishes any new inter-cluster network channels required, then terminates the old instance. Reserving resources before terminating the old instance ensures fast cut-over and minimises the risk of service interruption. **NetMA-FC** reconfigures the network overlay to align with the updated placement, establishing new secure channels and releasing those no longer needed.

Throughout this process, all coordination between components occurs through K8s *Custom Resources (CRs)*, i.e., structured objects in the K8s API rather than through direct control dependencies. This design means that no component needs a persistent, low-latency connection to any other in order to continue functioning: each component reads the CRs relevant to it and acts accordingly, tolerating temporary unavailability of other components or of the Hub itself.

ACM-FC aggregates the current system and application state and makes it available to the developer through dashboards and APIs, providing continuous transparency into the deployment and enabling informed oversight while CODECO manages the application lifecycle autonomously.

6 Components and their Operation

This section provides the detailed design specification of each CODECO component in both single-cluster and federated-cluster configurations. The components described here realise the three-layer governance model and the data-compute-network co-orchestration approach introduced in Sections 2 and 4 and collectively implement the four federated orchestration priorities discussed in Section 3.

Five components and a plugin are covered. The **CODECO Neighbourhood Composer (CNC)** plugin is responsible for computing and maintaining application neighbourhood definitions — the bounded coordination scopes that constrain scheduling, monitoring, and learning exchanges to the subset of Managed Clusters relevant to a given application. **ACM-FC** is the sole user-facing entry point to the CODECO framework; it validates and manages application lifecycle through the CODECO Application Model (CAM), governs cluster configuration, and coordinates the activation of all other components. **PDLC-FC** provides AI-assisted placement recommendations by aggregating cross-layer observability data through privacy-preserving, neighbourhood-scoped federated learning and multi-agent reinforcement learning, keeping raw telemetry local to each Managed Cluster. **MDM-FC** maintains a semantic metadata graph capturing data locality, freshness, compliance, and portability across the federation, enabling data-aware placement decisions. **NetMA-FC** delivers cross-layer network observability via ALTO-based cost maps and eBPF-instrumented monitoring and manages secure inter-cluster connectivity through a Layer 2 mesh approach integrated with a hybrid SDN control plane. **SWM-FC** implements a two-layer federated scheduler — a Hub-level coordinator for cross-cluster workload distribution and per-cluster solvers for node-level placement — treating migration as a first-class scheduling operation.

For each component, the description covers key technologies, sub-component design, single-cluster operation, and the extensions introduced for federated cluster operation. Where applicable, the interfaces between components are specified and the component's role in the AI-driven decision flow described in Section 4.8 is made explicit. Furthermore, throughout this section, the suffix **-FC** (e.g., ACM-FC, PDLC-FC, MDM-FC) denotes the federated cluster variant of a component; where the suffix is absent, the reference applies to the component in general or in its single-cluster form. Both designations refer to the same component, with **-FC** signalling that the federated cluster extensions described in Section 4 are in scope.

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6.1 CNC: CODECO Neighbourhood Composer Plugin

To orchestrate an application, it is assumed that CODECO will check possible resources across all Managed Clusters handled by a Hub cluster. It has also been discussed, and considered for future work, the possibility of integrating MCs handled by other Hub clusters. In other words, CODECO currently considers that the neighbourhood of an application just includes clusters managed within a Hub, which aligns well with the notion of intra-AS on the Internet.

Each time a new application is deployed, a unique set of clusters is selected. If multiple applications—say, x —are deployed every few hours, then running expensive operations like clustering and optimization each time becomes unsustainable, risking both scalability and performance. A more efficient strategy is to perform clustering less frequently such as once per day to partition the large space into smaller, similarity-based groups. Then, for each application deployment, neighbourhoods can be selected only within the most relevant subgroups. This significantly reduces computational load by separating space division (through clustering) from the more dynamic task of neighbourhood selection, making the system more scalable.

An important consideration is how much neighbourhoods are expected to change over time. The consortium determined that once defined, neighbourhoods should remain relatively stable. However, changes could be triggered by specific conditions such as performance degradation beyond a certain threshold, resource depletion, or environmental instability.

The mechanism responsible for triggering and recalculating neighbourhoods would reside outside the core orchestrator but would communicate closely with the ACM. When necessary, the ACM could call upon a dedicated neighbourhood definition service to reevaluate and update clusters based on current system conditions and predefined policies. This externalized design keeps the core orchestration lightweight while still allowing adaptive behavior when needed. A key scalability challenge in federated CEI orchestration is limiting the search and coordination space without sacrificing adaptivity. CNC is designed to separate two tasks that otherwise become expensive at scale:

- **Space partitioning:** Groups clusters into coarse similarity classes at a slower timescale.
- **Neighbourhood selection:** Chooses a bounded set of candidate clusters for a specific application at deployment time.

This separation reduces repeated global optimisation and limits monitoring and learning exchanges to application-relevant clusters. CNC separates coarse-grained cluster partitioning (performed infrequently) from application-specific neighbourhood selection at deployment time. Given a CAM and target performance profile, it outputs a bounded neighbourhood specification consumed by ACM-FC and disseminated via OCM.

6.2 ACM-FC

ACM-FC is the governance-facing entry point of CODECO and is primarily deployed at the Hub cluster. In a federated setting, ACM-FC fulfils three main management responsibilities:

- **Platform configuration across the federation:** Including onboarding of new clusters and enforcement of baseline configuration required by CODECO components.
- **Intent and lifecycle coordination:** By validating the CODECO CAM and translating application intent into internal representations consumed by scheduling, networking, and learning components.
- **Observability integration:** Aggregating monitoring information from the federation and reflecting application and infrastructure status back into CAM.

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Figure 12: ACM and relation to other CODECO components.

ACM-FC (Figure 12) provides methodologies and tools that support the CODECO automatic configuration, regarding application setup and deployment across Edge-Cloud, for single and multi-cluster environments. ACM is based on the OCM community driven project which is the upstream project for Red Hat *Advanced Cluster Management*⁴. The CODECO ACM component contemplates the CODECO integration into embedded and small footprint nodes; the development of K8s operators (and if required, additional semantic interfaces) that extend the ACM operation towards the other CODECO components; automated configuration and user interfacing, to support operations across multi-cluster (federated clusters) in a way that is transparent to the user; autoscaling. Furthermore, ACM addresses security focusing on attack mitigation and detection across multi-cluster (distributed environments). At deployment time, ACM-FC validates CAM, triggers neighbourhood selection (via CNC or policy-driven mechanisms), and coordinates the activation of CODECO components for the selected neighbourhood. During runtime, ACM-FC maintains application lifecycle state (updates, rollback, removal) and ensures that monitoring data collected from the federation is exposed to users in a consistent manner. Figure 13 shows the different interaction points between ACM-FC and the other CODECO components in a multi-cluster environment.

⁴ <https://www.redhat.com/en/technologies/management/advanced-cluster-management>

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Figure 13: ACM-FC deployment across one Hub and two Managed Clusters.

Since ACM-FC is the integration point towards the user, it is also in charge of the system installation - the user can install the CODECO framework by installing the CODECO meta-operator (which is part of ACM-FC), where this process triggers the installation of the entire CODECO system on the cluster to be managed and configured. In addition, there may be the explicit need to export more information from the CODECO system to the cluster control plane and towards the users. This task also falls under the ACM-FC umbrella. Since the CODECO meta-operator is the only operator exposed towards the users, it is therefore in charge of the entire CODECO system installation, including the installation of all its components and their operators (MDM, PDLC, SWM and NetMA).

The CODECO ACM-FC operation considers three main categories of aspects that address the integration of CODECO across the overall Edge-Cloud infrastructure:

- **Integration points between users and applications.** Mechanisms for users (e.g., user DEV) to control and change configuration of the applications to be run across the CEI continuum.
- **CODECO configuration.** A specific user request during application deployment setup or application runtime implies activation and eventual configuration of CODECO components, e.g., NetMA, PDLC. This can be done, for instance, by enhancing the K8s API with CRDs and adding operators to monitor the changes in the CRs, reacting accordingly.
- **Cluster/federated cluster configuration.** The user in this case is a user MGT, handling the K8s infrastructure. A specific change to the CODECO configuration (for instance, increase or decrease in the application workload due to dataset changes) may imply the need to install, configure (for example, policy configuration, CODECO components deployments), or reconfigure a cluster.

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6.2.1 Key Technologies

The following list contains the main technologies in ACM:

- **K8s API extensions** via CRD/CRs and respective operators.
- **Prometheus**⁵ and exporters such as the *Kubernetes-based Efficient Power Level Exporter*, *Kepler*⁶, as well as new Prometheus operators to support new monitoring plugins provided in the different CODECO components, supporting the integration of new metrics in K8s.
- **Multi-cluster/federation management based on OCM** (to be developed during the second phase of CODECO, M19-M36).
- **Knative**⁷ to support serverless deployment of containerised applications across Edge-Cloud.
- **Lightweight K8s distribution solutions** such as K3s⁸, Microshift⁹, for far Edge integration.
- **Integration with non-K8s far Edge nodes** based on solutions such as Flotta¹⁰.
- **Secure onboarding of devices**, considering *Fast Identity Online (FIDO)* and *Trusted Execution Environments (TEE)* approaches.
- **Fast provisioning of K8s clusters** on remote worker nodes via solutions such as Hypershift¹¹.
- **Ansible**¹², to support the automated deployment of CODECO.
- **Thanos**¹³ to extend the monitoring framework and facilitate a highly available Prometheus setup with a global query view and the possibility for long term storage.

6.2.2 ACM CODECO Metrics

ACM is responsible for bringing computational metrics to CODECO. The minimum subset of CODECO computational metrics currently being considered are provided in Annex I. These metrics are provided via CAM.

6.2.3 Sub-components

Internally, ACM-FC comprises a *Neighbourhood Manager*, an *Application Lifecycle Manager (ALM)*, *Multi-Cluster Configuration (MCC)* which together reconcile CAMs, deploy CODECO services across clusters, and maintain neighbourhood definitions.

6.2.3.1 The ACM-FC Neighbourhood Manager

The Neighbourhood Manager (Figure 14) operates as an internal subcomponent of ACM-FC. Its primary responsibility is to manage the lifecycle of neighbourhood definitions associated with applications. Once a neighbourhood is produced (by CNC or by policy), the Neighbourhood Manager creates a corresponding Kubernetes resource capturing membership and constraints and disseminates it to the relevant MCs through OCM ManifestWork. This enables

5 <https://prometheus.io/>

6 <https://sustainable-computing.io/>

7 <https://knative.dev>

8 <https://k3s.io/>

9 <https://github.com/openshift/microshift>

10 <https://project-flotta.io/>

11 <https://github.com/openshift/hypershift>

12 <https://www.ansible.com/>

13 <https://thanos.io/>

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other CODECO components (e.g., PDLC-FC and SWM-FC) to discover neighbourhood membership locally without requiring continuous interaction with the Hub cluster.

The Neighbourhood Manager maintains neighbourhood consistency over time through reconciliation. Cluster lifecycle events (join or leave) and relevant metadata changes (e.g., labels or claims) can trigger updates to the neighbourhood resource and its redistribution.

Figure 14: ACM-FC and the Neighbourhood Manager.

6.2.3.2 ALM: CODECO User API and CAM

The user API corresponds to the entry point of CODECO. The API relies on CAM, for which a representation is provided in Figure 15. The figure represents different specifications for applications, services, and channels, while it also outlines the metrics for assessing the status and performance of these entities. The structure supports the aggregation of metrics at multiple levels, ensuring detailed insight into the operational aspects of the system.

The API does not require extra privileges for managing the cluster and is used for deploying a single application composed of multiple micro-services as a single entity. CAM is an extension to the K8s pod-based model designed to manage and monitor distributed, multi-pod applications as a whole, emphasizing both specification and status aspects. Each application can consist of multiple services (micro-services in CODECO), defined by the *ServiceSpec*

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class, detailing resource usage at a computational (CPU, memory), network (latency, bandwidth, energy spent during transmission), and data (freshness, age of information) level.

Each micro-service is implemented as a pod. Communication between micro-services is facilitated by the Channel and *AdvancedChannelSettings* classes, which outline the communication pathways and additional channel configurations. The *podSpec* class links services to K8s pod specifications, ensuring deployment consistency. On the status side, the *AppStatus* class aggregates runtime metrics, captured in the *AppStatusMetrics* class, e.g., pod count, memory and CPU usage, network load, and associated costs. The model also includes *NodeStatusMetrics* to monitor node-specific performance and reliability, and *ServiceStatusMetrics* to track service-level metrics on nodes. This structure allows for detailed, hierarchical monitoring and management of applications, ensuring efficient resource utilisation, performance tracking, and compliance adherence across distributed systems.

Figure 15: Logical representation of the CODECO Application Model.

6.2.3.3 ACM-FC Monitoring Framework

The monitoring in CODECO (Figure 16) is based on Prometheus as the de facto K8s metrics server. Most of the monitoring work is done by direct integration of the CODECO components with Prometheus. In addition to this, ACM provides some additional functionality for Monitoring tasks:

- **Slow-paced metrics**, such as an averaged metric over a time window of one or five minutes, relevant to the user, are populated in the **status** part of the CRD. As a result, the ACM operator runs on a timely manner (once a minute) and not only when an application resource is changed (as is the default behaviour for K8s operators).

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- **A mechanism for no code addition of Prometheus rules was added** (a central place for managing and deploying Prometheus Rules) so that the components can export their rules and make them visible to the other components in a managed and centralised process. This mechanism can export non-trivial metrics (one that requires a query) by the metric owner to the metric users.

Figure 16: Monitoring architecture in CODECO [2].

6.2.4 Single Cluster Operation

In a single-cluster deployment, ACM-FC operates in a simplified configuration that does not require the federation control plane components active at the Hub level. DEV or MGT user interacts with CODECO exclusively through ACM-FC, which serves as the single point of entry for both application deployment and cluster-level configuration.

The single-cluster workflow proceeds as follows. The user first installs the CODECO Operator via ACM, which handles the installation and sequential configuration of all CODECO framework components. Once the operator is active, the user describes an application via a CAM specification, defining microservice composition, performance requirements, and operational constraints at computational, network, and data levels. ACM validates the CAM, resolves service dependencies, and coordinates the activation of PDLC, MDM, NetMA, and SWM for the cluster.

The monitoring framework in single-cluster operation, is Prometheus-based and managed through a Kubernetes Operator pattern. ACM draws on three categories of metric sources. First, **Node Exporter** provides host-level and OS-level metrics, Kubernetes process metrics, and energy consumption data collected via eBPF hooks instrumented through Kepler. Second, the **Kubernetes API** supplies cluster-level resource state, enabling Service Discovery to dynamically identify monitoring targets as pods are created, updated, or removed. Third, **Prometheus-format metric endpoints** are exposed by all CODECO components — PDLC, MDM, and NetMA — in a standardised format collected by the Prometheus Server through its Retrieval subsystem. The Prometheus Server stores collected metrics in its *Time Series Database (TSDB)* and exposes them via an HTTP Server supporting PromQL queries, which

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Observability Dashboards consume for real-time visualisation of cluster health and workload status. The Alert Manager receives alert rules managed by the Prometheus Operator and handles threshold-based notifications. The Prometheus Operator governs the full lifecycle of monitoring resources through dedicated Kubernetes CRDs — Prometheus, *AlertManager*, *AlertManagerConfig*, *ServiceMonitor*, and *PodMonitor* — ensuring that monitoring configuration remains consistent with cluster state without manual intervention. A centralised *PrometheusRule* mechanism allows each CODECO component to export its alerting rules into the shared Prometheus configuration.

ACM exposes the collected computational metrics to PDLC and SWM via these Prometheus endpoints, which consume them to inform placement and rescheduling decisions. The CAM status section is continuously updated by ACM with runtime observability information, providing the user with a consistent view of application and infrastructure state throughout the cluster lifecycle.

6.2.5 Federated Operation

Figure 17: ACM-FC operation, considering an environment involving multiple OCM instances (multiple Hub clusters).

In a federated cluster environment, ACM-FC extends its single-cluster responsibilities to encompass governance, neighbourhood management, and inter-hub coordination across multiple administrative domains. Figure 17 illustrates the multi-hub configuration, which represents the most complex federated scenario: two Hub clusters, each running its own ACM-FC instance, jointly governing a set of five Managed Clusters (MC1–MC5) organised into two application Neighbourhoods (N1 and N2).

Hub structure and ACM-FC distribution. Hub 1 operates as the primary governance point and runs the full ACM-FC stack: UI, App Controller, Monitoring, Neighbourhood Manager, MC Config, and the OCM Policy/Placement engine. Users submit application descriptions via CAM exclusively through Hub 1's ACM-FC. Hub 2 runs a lighter ACM-FC instance, currently exposing the UI layer, and acts as a resilience peer, ensuring that federation governance can continue in the event of Hub 1 unavailability. The two hubs synchronise via a bidirectional channel carrying Managed Cluster Data and Hub resilience state, allowing neighbourhood definitions and cluster membership information to remain consistent across both governance points.

Neighbourhood formation and cluster assignment. The Neighbourhood Manager within Hub 1's ACM-FC is responsible for computing and maintaining neighbourhood definitions. In

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the configuration shown, Neighbourhood 1 groups MC1 and MC2, while Neighbourhood 2 groups MC3, MC4, and MC5. Neighbourhood boundaries define the coordination scope for scheduling, monitoring, and learning: only clusters within the same neighbourhood exchange observability data and participate in joint placement decisions for a given application. Neighbourhood definitions are propagated to Managed Clusters via OCM *ManifestWork*, allowing each cluster to discover its neighbourhood membership locally without requiring continuous hub interaction.

Managed Cluster components. Each Managed Cluster runs an ACM/OCM Agent, which maintains the cluster's registration with its governing hub and enforces manifests dispatched from the Hub's OCM Policy/Placement engine. A local SWM-L2 instance handles node-level placement decisions within the cluster, consuming application specifications received from Hub 1's ACM-FC and reporting CAM status back to the hub. PDLC is deployed selectively — currently present in MC1 and MC3 — providing AI-assisted placement recommendations and context-aware cost estimates within each neighbourhood scope. The asymmetric deployment of PDLC across Managed Clusters reflects the optional nature of the learning component depending on the cluster's role and resource profile.

Scheduling across hubs. Hub 1 hosts a hub-level SWM-L1 instance responsible for cross-cluster workload distribution decisions within its governed neighbourhoods. The interaction between SWM-L1 and ACM-FC is bidirectional: ACM-FC forwards application specifications to SWM-L1, which returns scheduling assignments that ACM-FC then propagates to the relevant Managed Clusters via OCM.

Open design questions. As annotated in Figure 17, several aspects of the multi-hub configuration remain open. The responsibility for neighbourhood formation in a multi-hub environment — specifically, which hub holds authoritative neighbourhood state and how global cluster visibility is maintained — is an open question. The impact of cross-hub neighbourhoods on the SWM-L1 scheduling layer is also unresolved: it is not yet determined whether each hub requires a dedicated SWM-L1 instance or whether a shared scheduling coordinator spanning hubs is preferable. These questions are identified as directions for further development in the CODECO open-source roadmap, as the new Eclipse KuDECO¹⁴ project advances.

6.3 PDLC-FC

PDLC-FC, represented in Figure 18, provides AI-assisted decision support for federated orchestration by analysing cross-layer observability data and producing placement and migration recommendations. It operates in a decentralised and privacy-preserving manner, keeping raw telemetry local to each MC and exchanging only protected learning artefacts within application neighbourhoods. PDLC-FC does not enforce decisions; instead, it supplies cost and stability indicators that are consumed by SWM-FC. PDLC-FC considers the following modules:

- **Data Preprocessing (PDLC-DP):** the subcomponent that acts as an input interface of PDLC with all other CODECO components. Responsible for obtaining all necessary data and performing the needed pre-processing operations (cleaning, normalization, etc.) for the data to be ready for use by the other subcomponents.
- **Context-Awareness (PDLC-CA):** the subcomponent responsible for data gathering, integration and pre-processing (PDLC-DP) to generate exploitable context information and performance profiling (PDLC-PP).

¹⁴ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.kudeco>

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- **Decentralised Learning (PDLC-DL):** the subcomponent responsible for exploiting the context information provided by PDLC-CA through decentralised learning models to add an additional intelligence layer to the operations of CODECO. It currently contains two models, a *Graph Neural Network (GNN)* and a *Reinforcement Learning (RL)* agent. Furthermore, this sub-component will include *Machine Learning Operations (MLOps)* pipelines to orchestrate the (re)training process of the mentioned models.

The role of each CODECO component towards PDLC is as follows:

- **ACM:** PDLC relies, similarly to other CODECO components, on the CRs managed by ACM. These CRs will provide all the necessary information about the CODECO applications through the CODECO application model, providing both specs and status updates. ACM will also potentially receive output from PDLC-CA in the form of recommendations about initial cluster configurations, once enough historical data has been gathered, and learning models have been trained.
- **MDM:** provides additional data information to PDLC related to data-related issues that may impact orchestration decisions. For instance, if an application requires access to large data sets, depending on network bandwidth and latency constraints, it may be necessary to constrain where the data is processed to achieve performance requirements. MDM provides a complete set of metadata describing the data (e.g., location, size, classification, policy evaluation) to assist CODECO in making orchestration decisions that are cognizant of data constraints.
- **NetMA:** provides network-layer metrics that are used by PDLC-CA and PDLC-DL in conjunction with the metrics combined from ACM and MDM to generate performance profile heuristics and pod placement recommendations. This will include both underlay and overlay network metrics and will be provided through the NetMA CR files.
- **SWM:** the main component to receive output from PDLC, both in the form of performance profiling as well as behaviour estimation and optimization. Crucially, SWM might need to provide feedback to PDLC about the decisions it makes based on the provided output, which would allow PDLC-PP and PDLC-DL to compare their suggestions with the taken actions and use that feedback to improve.

6.3.1 Key Technologies

- **TensorFlow**¹⁵ and **Pytorch**¹⁶ for the training and development of the PDLC-DL models, both the GNN model and RL agent.
- **Kubeflow**¹⁷ for the implementation of the MLOps pipeline.
- **Prometheus**, **Kepler**, and new Prometheus CODECO operators, to observe and provide metrics to PDLC.
- **Python** and its main libraries such as **numpy**¹⁸, **pandas**¹⁹ for the processing and manipulation of the data throughout the PDLC sub-components.

¹⁵ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

¹⁶ <https://pytorch.org/>

¹⁷ <https://www.kubeflow.org/>

¹⁸ <https://numpy.org/>

¹⁹ <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

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Figure 18: Functional, high-level representation of the PDLC sub-components across a federated environment and of their interactions.

6.3.2 Sub-components

6.3.2.1 PDLC-DP: Data Preprocessing

PDLC-DP retrieves cross-layer metrics from Prometheus, normalises them, and maintains a local telemetry store for PDLC sub-components. Each PDLC-FC instance operates exclusively on locally collected data, avoiding shared storage dependencies and preserving data sovereignty. PDLC-DP's objective is to deliver high-quality, interpretable data, continuously collected from ACM, MDM and NetMA CRs. This data is then provided to other PDLC sub-components, namely PDLC-CA and PDLC-DL, for further processing. The PDLC-DP architecture includes two main modules:

- **The Gatherer:** an entity that is responsible for collecting real-time data (cross-layer metrics) from all the aforementioned CODECO components through their predefined CRDs.
- **The Pre-processing Module (PP module):** in which data derived from the Gatherer are delivered and a collection of pre-processing operations is utilized to provide clean and

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correct-formatted data before being delivered to the other internal CODECO-PDLC sub-components.

The PDLC-DP architecture and its internal functionality is represented in Figure 19. As can be observed, the preprocessing module gathers stream-oriented data, (currently, recorded every minute by default) and then executes various processing operations tailored to each sub-component. However, these operations are performed concurrently to minimize execution time.

Figure 19: PDLC-DP internal functionality and steps.

The **gatherer module** is responsible for gathering all the metrics provided by the other CODECO components with their corresponding metadata (from CAM, status section), saving them in memory for PDLC-DP to use and then destroying them when they are not needed anymore. Another responsibility of the Gatherer is the continuous validation and recreation of the cluster topology from the topological information provided by NetMA. The cluster topology, provided by NetMA, is described by the Gatherer in an adjacency matrix for the rest of the PDLC subcomponents to use. This procedure is happening in a configurable amount of time in order to easily fit with PDLC needs.

The **pre-processing module** is responsible for cleaning, curating, and preparing the data provided by the Gatherer. This module encompasses various operations, including data validation, transformation, normalization, integrity checks, and quality assurance processes. When the processing operations are completed, the processed data are stored in different CSV files - each one to serve the subcomponents functionalities and declares again its availability to the gatherer in order to start receiving new data.

In the FC phase, PDLC-DP component preserves its core functional architecture while introducing a significant enhancement: the integration of InfluxDB as a dedicated time-series database. This shift from Kubernetes-native PVCs to standalone database instances improves component autonomy, enforces stronger data isolation, and enhances privacy by ensuring that all processed data remains self-contained. Each PDLC instance is provisioned with its own InfluxDB instance during deployment, instantiated and initialized by the Gatherer module. This module also generates the required credentials (username, password, access token), which are securely stored using Kubernetes Secrets. Only designated sub-components—PDLC-CA, PDLC-DL-GNNs, and PDLC-DL-RL (MARL)—are granted access for read/write operations. The Gatherer continues to collect metrics, particularly those defining the network topology (overlay and underlay). However, due to the structured nature of these metrics, they

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are stored in a Kubernetes ConfigMap rather than InfluxDB, which is optimized for time-series data. Figure 20 depicts the PDLC-DP functional architecture.

Figure 20: PDLC-DP functional architecture supporting SC and FC phases.

Figure 21 represents the operational workflow of the PDLC-DP component during the FC phase. In this workflow, the PDLC-DP component engages in continuous interaction with CODECO components ACM, MDM, NetMA, to retrieve relevant cross-layer metrics presented in Annex I. These interactions are managed by the PDLC-DP *Gatherer* module. Once data is acquired, it is handed off to the PDLC-DP pre-processing module, where it undergoes transformation to align with the pre-processing requirements demanded by the other PDLC sub-components (PDLC-CA, PDLC-DL-GNNs, PDLC-DL-RL-MARRL). The resulting data then securely persisted in a dedicated time-series database (InfluxDB), which is provisioned as part of each PDLC deployment. This ensures that all processed data remains isolated and cluster specific. In parallel, network topology information is stored in Kubernetes-native resources (K8s config file) to preserve its hierarchical and strongly typed nature. Access to the storage systems is tightly controlled and limited to authorized PDLC sub-components, reinforcing the privacy-preserving design of the overall architecture.

In the federated cluster phase, PDLC-DP replaces the earlier use of shared persistent storage with a dedicated, per-instance time-series database (InfluxDB). Each PDLC-FC instance is provisioned with its own database, ensuring that pre-processed metrics remain cluster-specific and isolated, reinforcing the privacy-by-design principle that raw or processed telemetry does not leave the cluster in which it is collected. The *Gatherer* module is entrusted with the full automation of this integration. Upon the initial deployment of the PDLC component, the *Gatherer* provisions the InfluxDB instance deployed as a dedicated pod within the PDLC-managed infrastructure and programmatically performs its configuration using the InfluxDB REST API.

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This process includes the dynamic creation of all required elements: organization, bucket, measurement, username, password, and access token. These credentials are securely stored in Kubernetes Secrets to ensure strict access control, allowing only designated PDLC sub-components to interact with the database. Measurements are tailored to individual PDLC sub-components, enabling structured, secure, and efficient access to relevant data. This architecture not only improves data management and operational scalability but also enhances the privacy-preserving nature of PDLC-DP by ensuring greater data isolation and minimizing reliance on shared Kubernetes resources. The overall approach embodies a shift toward a more autonomous, modular, and secure data handling paradigm.

Figure 21: Sequence Diagram and Operational Workflow Detailing the Internal Processes of the PDLC-DP Component.

6.3.2.2 PDLC-CA: Context-awareness

The metrics pre-processed by PDLC-DP are aggregated by PDLC-CA based on specific target performance profiles provided by the user via CAM. PDLC-CA therefore relies on CODECO metrics (e.g., computational parameters such as CPU, memory; network parameters such as bandwidth, latency, link energy; data metrics such as data compliance, data size) and is also prepared to consider metrics from Prometheus.

The existing parameters are combined to provide nodes with a **data-network-compute** cost (aggregated cost) that provides a measure on how “well” the node is behaving for a specific performance profile selected by the user. For instance, assuming the user would select as performance profile “*resilience*”, then PDLC-CA would create a node cost that **embodies node resilience and network (link) resilience**. Assuming the user DEV has opted to optimize the available infrastructure to reduce energy consumption, PDLC-CA considers energy consumption at a node level, and energy consumption during packet transmission (all links of a node) to provide an **aggregate resilience score** for the node.

The aggregated approach provided by PDLC provides a way to feed a finer-grained level of context to CODECO, while still reducing the information to be passed, and eventually reducing the number of operations to be required in the scheduling and re-scheduling process. The PDLC-CA communication sequence is provided in Figure 22. As represented, periodically,

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components NetMA, ACM, MDM monitor specific metrics as detailed in Annex I. These metrics are made available to PDLC-DP, which cleans, processes them, and normalizes them based on the specific needs of each PDLC sub-component.

For PDLC-CA (represented as CA controller), the metrics are periodically fetched from the treated data provided by PDLC-DP. Then, aggregated costs based on specific target profiles are computed to all available nodes in a cluster. The resulting scores are then written as a CR, which is available for PDLC-DL.

PDLC-CA supports predefined and user-defined performance profiles by aggregating normalised metrics into compact node and cluster scores. Developers may define custom profiles by mixing normalised CODECO metrics with newly registered custom metrics.

Figure 22: PDLC-CA Communication sequence diagram.

Assuming for instance, that a user would select resilience as a target for optimizing the overall system performance, the scheduler would have to handle resilience at a node level and resilience at a networking level. This would imply having to integrate multiple parameters, and at the same time, increase the number of operations required to ensure the computational resilience and then the networking perspective resilience. By using a data aggregation approach to **score nodes based on specific performance target profiles**, CODECO expects to achieve the following:

- A significant reduction in the number of parameters having to be passed to a K8s scheduler.
- A better abstraction for schedulers (where aggregated costs are attributes of nodes), thus allowing for an easier introduction of new metrics.

The current approach to data aggregation in CODECO is statistical and intentionally designed as an initial, agile implementation — one that establishes a functional baseline while leaving room for improvement in future iterations. For multi-cluster, multi-tenant environments, this approach is expected to be superseded by a more robust multi-objective weight aggregation strategy, capable of modelling aggregated performance profile node scores across the heterogeneous conditions that characterise federated CEI deployments.

The model for the aggregated node score provided by PDLC-CA is as follows. A score (w) for a target performance profile (t) of a node i , represented as $w_t(i)$ is based on a set of cross-

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layer parameters \mathbf{P} : p_1, \dots, p_n related with: i) data being kept on the node for a specific application; ii) network link performance for the links; iii) computational resources (e.g., CPU, memory).

A generic score would be computed as in Equation 1, where the specific cross-layer parameters p_j are combined and weighted based on w_j . The weight w_j for each parameter can be set based on the level of importance that a specific infrastructure perspective has, and the sum of all w_j is 1. For instance, parameters related with networking may be more relevant than parameters related with data observability for a specific application. Currently, the specific weight to be set has not been analysed and hence, all parameters are equally weighted.

$$w_t(i) = \sum_j^n p_j w_j \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

The node score $w_t(i)$ is computed for each iteration with PDLC-DL. In the future, for the scheduler, the aim is to provide $w_t(i)$ as a target performance score, that SWM (or any other scheduler) can use as a node attribute, to rank the nodes.

6.3.2.2.1 Performance Target Profile Greenness Examples

A first performance target profile implemented in CODECO concerns “**greenness (g)**”. By greenness it is meant that the aim is to ensure that the overall application deployment can reach a lower (ideally, lowest possible) energy consumption. For greenness, different instantiations of $w_t(i)$ can be built, $w_g(i)$. An example currently available in CODECO is provided via Equation 2, based on the following purpose and rationale:

- **Purpose:** to provide nodes with a higher score that can contribute to achieve an infrastructure (for an application group) that has the least energy expenditure possible.
- **Rationale:** the lower the node energy expenditure; the higher the available bandwidth; the higher is the node greenness.

$$w_g(i) = \frac{1-n_e(i)}{n_e(i)} b(i) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

In Equation 2, $n_e(i)$ corresponds to the energy expenditure in the node (between 0 and 1), and $b(i)$ corresponds to the available bandwidth of the node, computed as the sum of available bandwidth on all egress nodes of node i . $n_e(i)$ is provided via ACM/Prometheus, based on the Keppler plugin²⁰. The node available bandwidth is based on the aggregated available bandwidth provided by the CODECO component NetMA. Another potential formulation of a greenness node score is provided in Equation 3:

- **Purpose:** to provide nodes with a higher score that can contribute to achieve an infrastructure (for an application group) that has the least energy expenditure possible.
- **Rationale:** the lower the node energy expenditure; the lower the energy expenditure across the node egress links; the higher is the node greenness.

$$w_t(i) = \left(\frac{1-n_e(i)}{n_e(i)} \right) \left(\frac{1-l_e(i)}{l_e(i)} \right) \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

In Equation (3), $n_e(i)$ corresponds to the energy expenditure in the node (between 0 and 1), and $l_e(i)$ corresponds to the energy expenditure across all egress links of the node, computed as the averaged sum of energy expenditure across all egress links on the node, based on an

²⁰ <https://sustainable-computing.io/design/metrics/>

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energy expenditure model per packet. $n_e(i)$ is provided via ACM/Prometheus, based on the Kepler plugin²¹. The link energy expenditure is provided via the CODECO component NetMA (netma-nsm-mon monitoring approach).

6.3.2.2.2 Performance Target Profile Resilience Examples

Another potential target profile being analysed and implemented in CODECO concerns resilience of the overall system. Currently, a resilience score $w_r(i)$ is focused on the selection of nodes that will maximise the resilience of the infrastructure, being provided in Equation 4:

- **Purpose:** Nodes are weighted for their contribution to resilience of the selected infrastructure.
- **Rationale:** the higher the number of link failures associated with the node; the smaller the node_degree; the lower is the resilience of the node

$$w_r(i) = n_f(i) \left(\frac{1}{d(i)l_f(i)} \right) \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Where $n_f(i)$ corresponds to the number of failures of the node (provided by ACM/Prometheus), $d(i)$ corresponds to the node degree (provided by NetMA, nsm-net-mon), and $l_f(i)$ corresponds to the sum of link failures computed by NetMA (rf. to nsm-net-mon in section 6.5.3.3.2).

6.3.2.3 PDLC-FC-MARL

In the FC phase, this component is extended to support the MARL paradigm, enabling operation across a multi-cluster environment. In this setting, multiple independent RL agents function within distributed clusters across the federated infrastructure. These agents exchange workload-related information—secured through additional encryption mechanisms—and concurrently enhance their local models via online learning. This approach facilitates adaptive, collaborative workload optimization in a decentralized and dynamic context. Figure 23 illustrates the conceptual architecture of the PDLC-DL-MARL component in the FC phase. This design extends the original PDLC-RL component to support federated, multi-agent reinforcement learning while preserving its core functionalities. The enhancements target three main areas:

- integration of an online training mechanism via the Training Controller,
- secure and efficient data ingestion through InfluxDB, replacing previous csv file methods, and
- implementation of a MARL-based inference mechanism in the Inference Controller, enabling collaborative decision-making across multiple clusters.

All input data for this component is sourced from an InfluxDB instance provisioned by the PDLC-DP sub-component. Upon data ingestion, the system supports both training and real-time inference, allowing reinforcement learning agents to be trained and deployed dynamically for optimized pod allocation in the cloud. At the core of the architecture lies the RL Controller, which orchestrates the interaction between the Training and Inference Controllers. This controller handles security verification, manages inter-component connectivity, and facilitates

²¹ <https://sustainable-computing.io/design/metrics/>

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transitions between training and inference modes. Additionally, model artifacts are stored in a centralized Model Bucket for reuse across components.

Figure 23: Subcomponents of PDLC-DL MARL and their interactions with other components of PDLC.

The design reflects a scalable and modular approach, positioning PDLC-DL-MARL as a fully integrated, federated learning solution within the broader PDLC framework. The PDLC-DL-MARL (in the FC phase) architecture is divided into three primary components: i) **RL Controller**: The main component responsible for controlling the various functionalities and capabilities. ii) **Inference Controller**: Manages both single and multi-cluster inference processes. iii) **Training Controller**: Handles the model's operation during the online training phase.

The general controller determines the operational mode, which can be changed based on user needs and model performance. In this deliverable, a complete framework is provided that integrates with InfluxDB and includes a synthetic data mode. This setup allows for comprehensive testing of the pipeline while integration with other CODECO components is finalized.

PDLC-FC-MARL enables neighbourhood-scoped inter-cluster recommendation through a MARL design. Agents run in the control plane of MCs and operate without a central coordinator, sharing high-level decision values rather than raw state or full model parameters.

PDLC-FL MARL component retrieves the collected data provided by the PDLC-DP which is stored in the PDLC-DB RL bucket (under the measurements: “*test_integration_metric*”, “*test_node_metric*”). The process begins with the entry point of the PDLC-DL RL MARL Controller, which performs initial configuration tasks required to set up the environment. Then the system branches into one of two operational paths based on its current mode: **Training** or **Inference**.

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Figure 24: PDLC-DL-MARL communication sequence.

In the **training mode**, the Controller initiates the setup of an online training environment by instantiating a reinforcement learning (RL) model along with its associated environment. Once initialized, the system enters a continuous loop where the training component regularly retrieves input data from the DB (InfluxDB). This data includes metrics normalized by PDLC-DP, performance scores calculated by PDLC-CA, and predictive insights generated by PDLC-GNNs. These inputs collectively form the basis for updating the agent's learning policy. Following each action—such as a workload placement decision—the system monitors outcomes and gathers feedback, potentially through the SWM and CA components. This feedback is then used to refine the model parameters, enhancing the agent's decision-making over time.

At the end of each training cycle, the updated workload placement recommendations are written to a CR, where they become accessible to CODECO-SWM.

In **inference mode**, the Controller initiates the inference pipeline by activating the inference component, which in turn loads and initializes the pre-trained RL model. Once operational, the system enters a data-driven decision loop, continuously retrieving real-time metrics from the DB (InfluxDB). These metrics—originating from sources such as PDLC-DP, PDLC-CA, and PDLC-GNNs—are used by the inference engine to assess the current cluster state. Based on

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this information and the learned policy embedded in the model, the system provides the workload placement recommendations at the node level, ensuring that decisions align with current performance conditions and optimization targets.

6.3.2.3.1 MARL Communication Aspects

Figure 25 illustrates the communication workflow of the MARL model. Upon the arrival of a new pod, each RL agent within the local neighbourhood independently computes a Q-value corresponding to its optimal allocation decision. These Q-values are then encrypted and multicast to all neighbouring agents. Once all values have been exchanged, the agent associated with the highest Q-value proceeds with the pod allocation, ensuring a decentralized yet coordinated decision-making process.

Figure 25: Sequence Diagram Illustrating the Execution Flow and Internal Interactions of PDLC-DL-RL MARL subcomponents in the FC phase.

6.3.2.3.2 MARL Foundational Elements

All the RL agents developed or deployed within this framework conform to a unified base modeling paradigm, regardless of the specific training objectives they pursue. The core decision-making problem is formally modelled as a *Markov Decision Process (MDP)*, defined by three key elements: the **State Space** (or Observation Space), the **Action Space**, and the **Reward Function**.

State Space: The state encapsulates a real-time snapshot of the system at a given timestamp and comprises all the contextual information required for informed decision-making. This includes the resource demands of the incoming pod—specified in terms of required processing

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units and memory—and the available resources on each node within the cluster (i.e., available CPU/GPU millicores and RAM). In addition, the state incorporates three performance scores generated by the PDLC-CA component: *greenness*, *resilience*, and a *user-defined metric*. It is important to note that the term "processing units" may refer to either CPU or GPU millicores, depending on the specific deployment context. Formally, the state S at time t is defined as in Equation 5:

$$S_t = \left(R_t^{\text{pod}}, \{ (R_{n,t}^{\text{node}}, M_{n,t}) \mid n \in N \} \right) \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

Where:

$$R_t^{\text{pod}} = \left(\text{CPU}_t^{\text{pod}}, \text{RAM}_t^{\text{pod}} \right)$$

$$R_{n,t}^{\text{node}} = \left(\text{CPU}_{n,t}^{\text{avail}}, \text{RAM}_{n,t}^{\text{avail}} \right)$$

$$M_{n,t} = \left(\text{greenness}_{n,t}, \text{resilience}_{n,t}, \text{custom}_{n,t} \right)$$

Action Space: The action space delivers the complete set of possible decisions that an agent may undertake within the environment, given a state S . In the context of this framework, each action corresponds to the assignment of a workload to a specific node within the cluster. Upon receiving an allocation request—processed sequentially—the agent produces an action indicative of the selected node. Node recommendations are subsequently derived by interpreting the output of the SoftMax layer (representing the agent's action probabilities) prior to the application of the argmax operation, which finalizes the discrete action choice.

To improve computational efficiency and simplify the re-training, a key architectural refinement has been made: the exclusion of the previously implemented "*Fake*" node. This node was originally intended to model delayed allocation scenarios by simulating deferred deployment. However, empirical evaluation revealed that such deferral strategies provided minimal performance benefits while substantially increasing the dimensionality and complexity of the problem. As a result, the action space has been streamlined to focus solely on immediate allocations to physically available nodes. Furthermore, to support dynamic constraint handling, an action masking mechanism has been introduced. Under this scheme, an action is considered valid if it belongs to the set of all theoretically possible actions but does not simultaneously appear in the set of contextually invalid actions.

Formally, let A_p denote the complete set of possible actions and A_i the subset of invalid actions for a given state. The set of valid actions, A_v , is defined as the set difference in Equation 6:

$$A_v = A_p - A_i \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

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This can also be expressed for each individual action a:

$$\text{is_valid}(a) = \begin{cases} \text{True,} & \text{if } a \in A_p \text{ and } a \notin A_i \\ \text{False,} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This mechanism produces a Boolean mask that enforces action constraints by restricting the model's selection to the subset of valid actions at each decision step.

Reward: The reward function is the core assessment mechanism of the RL paradigm; it serves as the guiding mechanism for the agent's training process. In the initial FC phase, the focus has been on developing a reward formula specifically tailored for optimizing performance profiles during Online Training. The core concept is to provide users with a foundational base model, which can subsequently be refined and optimized based on the reward structure detailed in this section.

The design principles for this reward function prioritize scalability, extensibility, and user interpretability within the training framework. While the reward functions are designed to be highly parameterized for maximum flexibility, users with sufficient Python knowledge can modify and substitute them at their own discretion.

Based on these principles, the reward function is formally defined as the weighted sum of the average *greenness*, *resilience*, and the *user-defined* performance calculated profiles across all nodes in the cluster, as reported by the PDLC-CA component:

$$\text{Reward}_t = w_G \cdot \frac{1}{|N|} \sum_{n \in N} G_{n,t} + w_R \cdot \frac{1}{|N|} \sum_{n \in N} R_{n,t} + w_U \cdot \frac{1}{|N|} \sum_{n \in N} U_{n,t} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

Weights are defined based on the user preferences (depending on which metric they want to optimise), by default the model will optimise greenness (in terms of energy optimization). As we anticipate extensive real-time testing of our models within the CODECO environment, it is recognized that experimentation results may necessitate minor adjustments to the proposed modeling approach. These iterative refinements are crucial for optimizing performance and achieving superior outcomes.

Specifically, modifications are expected in both the **state definition** and the **reward function**. These changes will primarily focus on incorporating feedback provided by **SWM solver**. The integration of this feedback is expected to significantly enhance the overall robustness and adaptability of the model, allowing it to better respond to dynamic real-world conditions and further improve decision-making capabilities.

6.3.2.4 PDLC-DL-GNN: Graph Neural Networks

In the FC phase, the PDLC-DL-GNNs sub-component introduces a decentralized, privacy-preserving *Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network (STGNN)* designed to predict node-level CPU and memory utilization. These forecasts, stored in InfluxDB, serve as critical input for the PDLC-DL-RL (extended to MARL) module to enhance workload placement decisions.

PDLC-DL-GNNs comprises three core elements as represented in Figure 26:

- **Decentralized Federated Training**, which enables secure, peer-to-peer model updates across clusters without centralized data sharing,

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- **the Controller**, which orchestrates periodic data retrieval and inference and,
- **the Inference API**, responsible for producing multi-horizon forecasts using both temporal patterns and cluster topology.

Figure 26: PDLC-DL-GNN and its sub-components.

By integrating localized inference with federated learning, this enhanced architecture supports adaptive, distributed resource management while preserving data privacy. Figure 27 provides the conceptual architecture of the PDLC-DL GNNs functionality along with its functionalities.

Figure 27: Internal architecture of the PDLC-DL-GNN sub-component along with PDLC-FC sub-components interaction.

The main functionality consists of two crucial operations: **i) the model's collaborative training part** and **ii) the re-training procedure** where online learning takes place. The system setup begins by defining a global data graph $G = (V, E)$, where V represents the set of all nodes (i.e., clusters), and E denotes the edges capturing communication links between them. The entire system is partitioned into a set of clusters, P , with each cluster assigned a unique identifier i . Each cluster i maintains a local subgraph $G_i = (V_i, E_i)$, which is a subset of the

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global graph. V_i refers to the nodes within cluster i , and E_i includes the edges connecting those nodes internally. To facilitate inter-cluster communication, a separate communication graph is defined as (V, A) , where V again represents the set of clusters, and A is a matrix that determines the strength of communication between neighbouring clusters in a decentralized fashion.

The training workflow begins with each cluster i initializing its own trainable model weights W_i and the shared communication graph (V, A) , which governs connectivity and influence among clusters. Each cluster proceeds to train its local GNN model using only its private subgraph G_i , ensuring that raw data remains confined within each cluster.

To protect communications during model exchange, clusters employ the Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol. All clusters agree on public parameters—a large prime number p and a generator g . Each cluster generates a private key a , which is kept confidential, and computes a corresponding public key using $A = g^a \text{ mod } p$. These public keys are exchanged among clusters, allowing each to compute a shared secret key with its peers using its private key and the received public key: $sk_{ij} = B^a \text{ mod } p = sk_{ji} = A^b \text{ mod } p$. This ensures both clusters derive the same shared key without revealing their private keys. With these shared secrets in place, clusters securely mask their local model weights before transmitting them to near clusters, thereby enabling privacy-preserving federated learning. The formula used to mask the local's model weights prior the propagation to the near clusters is defined as in Equation 8.

$$W_i = W_i + \sum_{i < j} \text{PRG}(sk_{ij}) - \sum_{i > j} \text{PRG}(sk_{ij}) \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

This asymmetric summation ensures that, when all masked weights are collectively aggregated, the introduced random noise cancels out. As a result, no individual cluster can infer another's true model parameters, while the global average remains accurately recoverable. The masked model parameters W_i are transmitted to the neighbouring clusters of node i . Upon receiving masked weights from its neighbours, cluster i proceeds to perform model aggregation which is defined as:

$$W_{i,t+1} = \sum_{j \in P} [W_j] \cdot A_{i,j} \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

The train-and-aggregate process is repeated multiple times, allowing each cluster to improve its local model by learning from its neighbours. Regarding the re-training procedure, as part of the system's ongoing evolution, the MLOps component is set to incorporate automated model re-training, guided by continuous evaluation. This mechanism will track both model performance indicators and system resource consumption. When specified thresholds are exceeded—such as declining accuracy or heightened resource usage—the system will autonomously initiate re-training to adapt the model to evolving data patterns or operational conditions. This closed-loop feedback process is intended to maintain long-term model accuracy and adaptability, reducing reliance on manual intervention. It is designed to strengthen the robustness of the PDLC-DL-GNNs framework in dynamic, real-world scenarios. However, this functionality remains under active development and is not included in the current release. Full integration into the MLOps pipeline is planned for a future version, pending the completion and validation of the necessary monitoring, alerting, and automation infrastructure.

The GNN models can provide predictions for the monitored metrics of a cluster's nodes. The models take as input historical timeseries data of each node (e.g., CPU or memory usage), as

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well as information about the cluster's topology, so that they can consider the spatial, as well as the temporal dependencies of the nodes and provide predictions about the aforementioned parameters in future timesteps. These predictions can be fed as input features to the RL models of PDLC-DL to enhance their performance and help them provide an improved pod allocation plan to SWM.

The *Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network* can predict future values of nodes' metrics based on historical observations, by modelling both spatial and temporal dependencies among nodes. The nodes' topology is mapped into a Graph structure, and the model consists of a Graph Convolution Layer and a Recurrent Neural Network layer.

The Graph Convolution Layer applies graph convolution to the input to get the nodes' representations over time, so that for each time step, a node's representation is informed by its neighbours' representations. The Graph Convolution is calculated according to Equation 10:

$$h_i^{(l+1)} = \sigma \left(b^{(l)} + \sum_{j \in N(i)} \frac{1}{c_{ij}} h_j^{(l)} W^{(l)} \right) \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

where $N(i)$ is the set of neighbors of node i , c_i is the product of the square root of node degrees (i.e., $c_{ij} = \sqrt{|N(i)|\sqrt{|N(j)|}}$), and σ is an activation function.

The nodes' representations are computed by multiplying the input features by the node's own weight and then each node's updated value is calculated by aggregating the neighbours' representations and then multiplying the results by the node's weight. The output of the layer is computed by combining the nodes representations. Based on the input, the graph convolution layer produces new tensor that captures the representations of nodes over time. To process the nodes' representations over time, a Recurrent Neural Network layer is utilized, in this case a *Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)* layer [17][18].

The workflow that is associated with the GNN models in PDLC is handled, as illustrated in Figure 28, by a controller, which includes the GNN orchestrator and the Inference service. The GNN orchestrator is responsible for continuously reading data provided by the PDLC-DP subcomponent.

Periodically, the aim is that the GNN orchestrator can therefore read information about the nodes in the cluster. Currently, it considers only CPU and memory (rf. to D14 for implementation details). However, the aim is to allow the orchestrator to consider any CODECO metric that PDLC may be relying upon. It then creates the appropriate request body and sends an API request to the Inference service every minute. The Inference service continuously reads the given cluster topology and when an inference request is received, it selects the appropriate pre-trained model based on the number of nodes, the requested CODECO metrics, and the requested forecast horizon (e.g., minutes, hours, days). Results are kept in a transient repository (currently, csv format) to be available to PDLC-DL-RL. The model's training procedure follows a decentralized-oriented learning approach. Specifically, each cluster trains its local GNN model on private data and exchanges encrypted model weights with the near clusters. This iterative, peer-to-peer process ensures privacy-preserving learning across the federation without centralizing raw data.

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Figure 28: PDLC-DL-GNNs sequence diagram.

6.3.3 Single-cluster Operation

The current operation of PDLC for a single cluster is represented in Figure 29. For a single cluster operation, PDLC has been devised to work in a centralised way (control plane of CODECO). PDLC sub-components are available in a modular way (docker container) and currently consider a common shared volume to store, access and modify the common data files generated by PDLC-DP.

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Figure 29: Deployment diagram of PDLC within a single CODECO cluster.

These data files are periodically generated by polling the CRD and API endpoints of components that provide CODECO metrics via ACM. Once new data is detected, PDLC-DP processes it and generates the output to be used by the PDLC subcomponents for their respective objectives. PDLC-RL provides node estimations and updates the respective CR of SWM with node recommendations once the entire processing pipeline is done.

Figure 30 shows a sequence diagram of the interactions between the different PDLC sub-components in a single-cluster operation.

Figure 30: Sequence diagram of PDLC and its subcomponents within a single CODECO cluster.

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6.3.4 Federated Operation

Several enhancements have been introduced across PDLC components to support scalability, distributed intelligence, and improved data management. The **PDLC-DP** component now performs enhanced storage capabilities, and preprocessing. Specifically, instead of storing the cross-layer time-series data in a PVC as in the Single Cluster operation phase, now it stores the formatted data in the newly introduced database enabling structured, scalable storage. The DB itself is a new component designed to manage and data efficiently while enforcing robust privacy-preserving mechanisms for initialization, read/write operations, and secure intra-cluster sharing. The **PDLC-CA** component has evolved to support advanced analytics by leveraging data from DB and enabling user-defined custom metrics, allowing more sophisticated performance profiling based on aggregated cluster state. For forecasting, **PDLC-DL (GNNs)** now supports dynamic model selection, adapting to varying numbers of nodes in the federated environment, and retrieves network topology from a configuration YAML file, more than that it efficiently performs distributed learning parameters aggregation in a secure manner by employing encryption techniques, to achieve collaborative learning . Finally, **PDLC-DL (RL)** extends its capabilities to a MARL framework, introducing decentralized RL agents and incorporating an Auction-Based Algorithm to recommend optimal workload placements across federated clusters.

Figure 31, depicts the operational workflow of the PDLC component in the FC phase, beginning with the **PDLC-DP** sub-component, which is responsible likewise the Single Cluster phase, for the real-time acquisition of cross-layer metrics from the CODECO components—**ACM**, **NetMA**, and **MDM**. These components respond with context-rich cross-layer metrics (compute, network, data), encapsulated as CRs. Following a sequence of sophisticated preprocessing steps, the structured data is ingested by the **PDLC-DP** to the newly added DB, which serves as the responsible, privacy-aware data repository that resides within the PDLC component.

Figure 31: Operational workflow of the PDLC component during the FC phase.

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The DB that has been selected in InfluxDB, a proper DB for storing and handling large scale time-series data, which provisions this curated data to both the **PDLC-CA** and **PDLC-DL (GNNs)** sub-components. The former applies advanced context-awareness analytics to generate energy and resilience and custom-metric performance profiles (**CAResults**), while the latter employs Graph Neural Network models to forecast future CPU and memory utilization (**GNNResults**). Together, these outputs offer a multidimensional situational assessment of the cluster's present conditions and anticipated resource demands. Building on this setting, the **PDLC-DL (RL)** module is activated. It integrates performance insights from **PDLC-CA**, predictive analytics from **PDLC-DL (GNNs)**, and the necessary pre-processed metrics from **PDLC-DP**, to drive a decentralized, inference-based decision-making pipeline. The embedded RL agent—operating under a MARL paradigm—coordinates with peer agents across other federated clusters. This collaborative mechanism enables distributed evaluation of inter-cluster workload placement opportunities using an auction-based algorithm. Upon deriving optimal workload recommendations, the module communicates them to the **CODECO-SWM** component, which governs their execution across the federated edge–cloud infrastructure. The continuous-loop architecture—encompassing data collection, model learning, and adaptive decision-making—underscores the iterative and self-refining nature of the PDLC. This dynamic and decentralized design ensures real-time responsiveness, robust situational awareness, and seamless coordination across diverse, multi-tenant environments, thereby enhancing resilience and resource optimization in the federated operation phase.

6.3.5 PDLC-FC: Security, Resilience, and Scalability

The federated cluster phase introduces challenges that are structural to distributed, multi-tenant environments. PDLC-FC addresses three of the most consequential: security, resilience, and scalability. Each is treated as a design principle rather than an add-on, shaping the architecture of the component from the ground up.

6.3.5.1 Security

Security encompasses the mechanisms that ensure information exchanged among clusters remains protected against intrusion and unauthorized access. Even though the exchanged data is not directly user-related, it may still reveal sensitive patterns or insights, particularly when learning parameters or model weights are shared. To mitigate the risk of potential data leakage, numerous privacy-preserving techniques have been proposed, focusing on securing the training process and parameter exchange. Moreover, privacy concerns extend to the data collection process itself. For instance, a malicious or compromised node could inject manipulated or falsified data with the intent of poisoning the learning workflow or corrupting the global model. Such scenarios highlight the necessity of robust data validation mechanisms and anomaly detection. In addition, the system must be safeguarded against adversarial attacks, such as man-in-the-middle attacks, where unauthorized entities attempt to intercept, manipulate, or inject information during inter-cluster communication. Ensuring secure, authenticated, and encrypted communication channels is thus paramount for maintaining the integrity of the collaborative learning process.

Thereby, PDLC incorporates a set of robust mechanisms designed to enhance both privacy and security throughout its operational workflow. Privacy is reinforced at multiple levels of the system architecture, ensuring comprehensive protection of data and communication.

At the access level, when the cross-layer metrics data are collected via CRs, privacy is safeguarded through the application of RBAC policies within the PDLC-FC component. This means that the read and write permissions are given only to the CODECO core components

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(ACM, NetMA, MDM, PDLC, SWM), ensuring that only trusted and authorized entities can access or modify sensitive information.

At the database layer, strict isolation is maintained. Tokens and access credentials remain inaccessible to unauthorized parties. Only relevant sub-components (PDLC-DP, PDLC-CA, PDLC-DL GNNs, PDLC-DL RL) are permitted to interact with the InfluxDB, with tokens being dynamically generated and securely managed through Kubernetes Secrets, thereby preserving confidentiality during all read and write operations on the InfluxDB instance.

Regarding the information exchange among the clusters, in order to further mitigate the risk of information tampering during inter-cluster communication, the system employs a security-enhanced approach by prefixing exchanged data with encryption mechanisms that ensure both integrity and authenticity. This design effectively protects against threats such as man-in-the-middle attacks, preserving the trustworthiness of the data exchange process.

It is important to emphasize that the PDLC-FC component is inherently privacy-preserving by design, as it operates exclusively on data generated and stored within its newly integrated database, located within its own cluster. It does not require or rely on external data sources, thereby minimizing exposure to external privacy risks.

6.3.5.2 Resilience

Resilience in PDLC-FC is achieved through a fully distributed, autonomous architecture in which an independent PDLC instance is deployed within each member cluster of the federation. Each instance operates exclusively on locally generated and maintained data, with no operational dependency on peer clusters. This architectural decoupling ensures that the failure, instability, or compromise of one or more clusters has no direct impact on the PDLC instances residing in unaffected clusters: each continues to perform data processing and produce placement recommendations independently, without requiring coordination or recovery from the rest of the federation.

This design eliminates the fragility associated with centralised or hierarchical resilience models, where the loss of a coordinating node can cascade into system-wide disruption. By treating each cluster as a self-sufficient unit, PDLC-FC guarantees a baseline level of orchestration intelligence even under partial federation failure.

6.3.5.3 Scalability

PDLC-FC's fully decentralised architecture directly addresses two scalability challenges inherent to large, federated environments: latency propagation and single-point-of-failure risk.

In federations spanning many clusters, broadcasting information globally introduces significant communication overhead and degrades system responsiveness. PDLC-FC eliminates this by operating independently within each cluster, with no reliance on a central coordinating entity. This removes potential bottlenecks and ensures that the computational and communication load does not grow with the size of the federation in a way that would compromise performance.

Scalability is further reinforced at the collaborative learning level. Rather than communicating with all clusters in the federation during model exchange, each PDLC instance selectively interacts only with clusters belonging to the same application neighbourhood. This neighbourhood-scoped communication strategy confines latency and overhead to local coordination groups, preventing the propagation of synchronisation costs across the full federated system and allowing CODECO to scale to larger federations without architectural change.

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6.4 MDM-FC: Metadata Manager

The CODECO MDM component aims at supporting real-time Edge applications and in achieving a higher degree of efficiency in Cloud-Edge operations. The MDM is a new system that integrates three novel aspects: i) a semantic data catalogue including a rich set of metadata providing a complete cross-domain view of data, systems and software; ii) metadata discovery, aiming at enriching the collected metadata, including input provided by other CODECO components (via CRDs) and learnings derived from the multi-cluster operation; iii) data orchestration support, to assist CODECO in making orchestration decisions that are cognizant of data constraints (e.g., performance issues if there are frequent accesses to remote data or compliance issues that may preclude copying data).

The MDM graph information can encompass attributes and properties such as data source, semantic description, classification, identification; data structure (e.g., data type, schema); application-specific information (e.g., data analysis, curation aspects); network specific information (e.g., access latency, bandwidth). The catalogue is populated continuously, based on a pull or push model whenever new information is available. It is therefore populated via the Kubernetes API, directly via data-sources, or via the ACM (user input) through Prometheus metrics, for example. MDM keeps track of the meta-data and provides a common platform where all metadata (multi-cluster) can be shared across multiple domains.

Example entities in a K8s and CODECO setting include “pods”, “namespaces”, “worker nodes”, as well as “datastore”, “file”, etc. Relationships are also typed and connect exactly two entities. Relationships have a direction. For example, the relationship “contains” may be used to express that a namespace contains a set of pods.

MDM and its sub-components are illustrated in Figure 32. MDM collects metadata from any “native system” that has information on the data, software and systems, including data stores, Kubernetes, or any other relevant system. For this purpose, MDM relies on **connector interfaces** for each specific data type.

Figure 32: MDM interfaces to other components.

Semantic Metadata Model: MDM represents metadata as a typed property graph, where entities and relationships can carry arbitrarily defined attributes. This model enables rich queries that derive application- and infrastructure-level metrics directly from the graph. Typical properties include data source and semantics, schema and data structure, application-specific

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characteristics (e.g., analysis or curation stage), and system-level attributes such as compliance or observed performance. The catalogue is populated continuously using both push and pull mechanisms. Metadata may be ingested directly from Kubernetes APIs, external data sources, or user input propagated through ACM-FC and Prometheus metrics. MDM maintains this information as a shared abstraction layer, allowing metadata originating from multiple clusters and domains to be reasoned about in a uniform way.

To decouple metadata ingestion from storage and querying, MDM relies on an event-driven architecture based on Apache Kafka. Metadata changes are represented as events (insert, update, delete) affecting entities or relationships. These events are logged and selectively materialised into the metadata graph to satisfy the needs of other CODECO components, notably PDLC-FC.

Entities, Relationships, and Extensibility: Example entities in a CODECO/Kubernetes environment include *Pods*, *namespaces*, *worker nodes*, as well as data-related objects such as *datastores* or *files*. Relationships are typed, directional, and connect exactly two entities — for example, a *contains* relationship linking a namespace to its pods. New entity and relationship types can be defined using a flexible JSON Schema DSL. This extensibility allows MDM to integrate metadata from arbitrary native systems without requiring changes to the core data model. An MDM connector interfaces to a native data system or CRD and pushes metadata into a knowledge graph through the native (internal) MDM API. By adding new connectors or expanding the graph model, the system can be extended to collect any required metadata.

MDM is event-based, relying on Apache Kafka²². MDM relies on the Kafka event queue, a log of metadata events that occur for an Edge-Cloud setting managed with CODECO. Events describe changes that have happened and correspond to insert/update/delete of metadata entities and relationships. MDM materializes (subsets of) the event queue in the knowledge graph to meet the needs of other CODECO components. MDM is implemented by three components:

- **MDM API:** Implements the REST APIs that allow metadata to be pushed into the graph database and the graph to be queried.
- **Graph Database:** Stores the metadata graph.
- **Connectors:** They gather metadata and push it into the Graph Database using the MDM Controller APIs.

6.4.1 Key Technologies

The MDM metadata collection has materialized in data systems that make it convenient to manage and exploit the metadata. The key technologies used in the current MDM implementation include:

- **Apache Kafka:** Distributed event store and stream processing.
- **Apache ZooKeeper**²³, for the overall Kafka management and coordination (e.g., configuration information, naming, providing distributed synchronization).
- **Python 3.9** or higher for the implementation of the APIs and the interaction with Kafka and the Graph database.
- **OpenAPI 3.0** as the standard for the REST API for both input and output

²² <https://kafka.apache.org/>

²³ <https://zookeeper.apache.org/>

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- **IBM Pathfinder SDK²⁴**: Provides YAML-based configuration and the base communication means for the connector to send metadata events to the MDM API
- **Kubernetes watcher API**: This allows the Kubernetes connector to receive as events all the entities created in the Kubernetes cluster, including but not limited to pods, CRDs, deployments.
- **Kubescape**: Kubescape is an open-source technology that performs a number of tests (controls) following compliance rules from well-known security and compliance frameworks. By default, the MITRE and NSA frameworks are enabled²⁵, which perform controls on configuration of worker nodes, K8s API, etc, and provide a level of coverage as a percentage.
- **Neo4j 4.4 or higher**.
- **Neo4j APOC**: *APOC (Awesome Procedures on Cypher)* is an add-on library for Neo4j that provides hundreds of procedures and functions adding a lot of useful functionality.
- **Cypher Graph Query language**: Cypher is a declarative graph query language that allows for expressive and efficient data querying in a property graph. It is the query language for Neo4j and the language openCypher is based on.
- **JSON Schema**: It is used to define the entities, their properties and relationships among them in a language-independent manner. The schemas are available online.

6.4.2 MDM CODECO Metrics

MDM is responsible for bringing data workflow level metrics to CODECO. The minimum subset of CODECO data metrics currently being considered are provided in Annex I.

6.4.3 Sub-components

6.4.3.1 Graph Database

The Graph Database is the backend storage of the MDM component. The metadata events from all MDM connectors are consolidated here, making it possible for other components to extract insights from the distributed system from a single pane of glass. It is of course possible to request information by directly querying the database using cypher, but other than during development or exploration of the metadata the MDM component is designed to offer this functionality through the MDM API.

6.4.3.2 Connectors

Connectors send metadata to MDM in the form of events. Events are structured JSON documents. Users of the CODECO framework can install any connectors they develop or use the MDM APIs to provide metadata into the system to compute metrics or other information for their own purposes. Out of the box, CODECO provides three connectors that provide the metadata for certain metrics that are used by the scheduling mechanism in PDLC to decide on the placement of the CODECO application.

²⁴ <https://pypi.org/project/ibm-pathfinder-sdk>

²⁵ <https://kubescape.io/docs/frameworks-and-controls/frameworks/>

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6.4.3.2.1 Kubernetes connector

Information about the Kubernetes environment managed by CODECO is essential to provide meaningful decisions as to how to schedule CODECO applications. Using as input the events obtained by watching the Kubernetes API, the Kubernetes connector provides metadata about all Kubernetes entities in the MDM graph, together with the relationships among them. The Kubernetes connector collects among other data the number of restarts of a pod, which is used as a proxy for the portability metric of that pod running in that cluster and namespace.

6.4.3.2.2 Prometheus connector

CODECO components and use-cases may use Prometheus as a means to make certain metrics available. The MDM Prometheus connector obtains configured metrics from Prometheus to enrich entities in the metadata graph with those values. In particular, the “freshness” metric is captured such that if a CODECO application is to be scheduled according to that particular metric, making it available in CODECO’s Prometheus will make it possible for PDLC to schedule the application to optimize the “freshness” of the data being processed. The Prometheus service needs to be integrated with Kubernetes so the association between the metric and the pod producing it can be obtained and reflected in the Knowledge Graph.

6.4.3.2.3 Compliance connector

The level of compliance of a Kubernetes environment managed by CODECO is another metric required to schedule CODECO applications. The Compliance connector uses Kubespace to obtain a metric of compliance of the cluster and adds that information to the MDM metadata graph.

6.4.3.3 MDM API

The MDM API is based on OpenAPI REST (OAS REST API) and integrates five endpoint groups, illustrated in Figure 33:

- **Publish** which is the endpoint for connectors writing to the MDM.
- **Events** which is the endpoint to get events from MDM.
- **Graph** gets information by querying the data projection. Initially this would allow for Cypher queries to be performed on the knowledge graph. If because of the experience gained with partners the set of queries required for the CODECO operation can be defined in a closed set, they can be incorporated to this API at a later stage.
- **PDLC** is the end-point where the PDLC component can query the graph for specific metrics related to the pods in the CODECO application.
- **Storage Metadata** is the end-point where properties of the storage available on the Kubernetes clusters in use by CODECO applications is available.
- **MDM** is the system information endpoint for getting status and resets or other system relevance functions.

All endpoints are protected and authorized usage enabled. The MDM API implements both the interface used to communicate with PDLC and the interface used by connectors to bring metadata into the graph database.

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Publish		^
POST	/publish/event send data to kafka	∨
Graph		^
POST	/graph/cypher execute a read only cypher and get the result	∨
GET	/graph/entity/attributes/{entitytype} get list of all possible attributes of the entity	∨
GET	/graph/entity/type get list of entity types	∨
POST	/graph/entity/type/{entitytype} get list of entities	∨
GET	/graph/path/{edf_id} get graph node relation by hops	∨
PDLC		^
GET	/pdlc get PDLC MDM properties	∨
Storage Metadata		^
GET	/storage/class get pvc and storage class of the pod	∨
GET	/storage/pvc get pvc and storage class of the pod	∨
MDM		^
GET	/mdm get system info	🔒 ∨
DELETE	/mdm/clean delete all Projection and data	∨
GET	/mdm/state get MDM system state	∨
Events		^
GET	/events/sse ServerSideEvent	∨

Figure 33: MDM API and its endpoints.

Figure 34 shows how the different MDM subcomponents interact with ACM, PDLC, Kubernetes and Prometheus. ACM deploys MDM by provisioning the subcomponents (Kafka, Zookeeper and Neo4j for the Graph database), as well as the controller, MDM API and the MDM connectors. ACM provides MDM with the relevant configuration via the CAM. The MDM connectors interact with the Kubernetes API and the Prometheus API to obtain relevant metadata as provided by the MDM API to send events that populate the Graph database. PDLC then can query the metrics required, based on the specific CAM requirements.

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Figure 34: Interaction of the MDM sub-components with ACM, PDLC and external metadata sources.

6.4.3.4 MDM Interfaces

MDM provides access to different metadata categories, creating K8s infrastructure knowledge graphs that can integrate data-network-compute awareness. At the current stage of architectural development, MDM interacts with two additional CODECO components, ACM and PDLC. For MDM, the possibility to further understand relevant metadata also derives from the CODECO use-cases. Hence, the interfaces will also be designed taking into consideration data requirements from the use-cases (WP5).

Table 6: MDM interfaces.

ID	Description	Type	Direction
I-MDM-E-1	This interface is used by all MDM connectors to provide metadata into the Graph database.		Input
I-MDM-PDLC-1	This interface is used by PDLC to obtain the metrics computed by MDM from the metadata gathered by the connectors.	OAS REST	Output
I-MDM-ACM-1	This interface defines the information provided by ACM to MDM	CRD (Helm)	Input

6.4.3.4.1 I-MDM-E-1

This interface is used by all MDM connectors to provide metadata into the Graph database.

POST /publish/event

Accepts in the body a JSON structured event. The event payload object could be an entity or relationship structure. An event contains the following elements:

1. The event type, either “insert” or “delete”.
2. An identifier that uniquely identifies the connector that issued the event.
3. A timestamp.

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4. The payload, i.e., the metadata.

Metadata is sent as entities and relationships. MDM imposes a basic structure on both entities and relationships to ensure that metadata can be stored as a graph. Entities must have a globally unique identifier and a type. It is the task of the connector to assign these. In addition, entities contain arbitrary numbers of attributes. The mandatory elements of a relationship are source and target entity identifier as well as a type. Relationships do not carry attributes.

MDM does not define or enforce a static data model. Instead, the graph data model is defined by the structure of the entities and relationships that are inserted into MDM. MDM expects a set of rules to be followed by entities and relationships:

- Connectors assign a universally unique identifier to each entity that they insert. The UUID is deterministically computed from properties of the entity. For example, the UUID of an entity representing a Kubernetes pod is computed using the cluster ID, the namespace, and the pod name.
- Connectors “own” the entities that they insert. A connector that inserts an entity has the rights to update and remove it again.
- Connectors cannot change or delete entities that have been inserted by other connectors.
- Connectors use a consistent method for computing the entity IDs. This enables connectors to integrate the entities that they produce into the graph by creating relationships to existing entities.
- A relationship defines how an entity is related to another entity. The connector computes the relationships’ endpoint IDs using the same deterministic method that is used for computing the entity IDs.
- Connectors own the relationships that they insert. A connector has the right to remove its own relationships again. Since relationships do not have properties, they cannot be changed.
- Connectors cannot overwrite relationships that have been inserted by other connectors.

6.4.3.4.2 I-MDM-PDLC-1

This interface is used by PDLC to obtain the metrics computed by MDM from the metadata gathered by the connectors.

GET /pdlc

This endpoint gets the metrics associated with the pods required by PDLC following a CRD format. The parameters are as follows:

- *cluster*: The name of the cluster where the pod is running.
- *namespace*: The namespace where the pod is running.
- *pod*: The name of the pod.
- *rnd*: (optional) If this is set to “true”, the API provides random values for all metrics.

The result is provided in JSON as a K8s CR. The output properties are, as described in Annex I:

- *pod_name*: The name of the pod, as provided as input
- *freshness*: How fresh the data processed by pod is (see Prometheus connector below)

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- *compliance*: Level of compliance of the pod given where it's running (see Compliance connector below)
- *portability*: A metric of how robust the execution of the pod is where it's running (see Kubernetes connector below).

6.4.3.4.3 I-MDM-ACM-1

This interface defines the information provided by ACM to MDM. Explicitly, ACM provides MDM with the following parameters at deployment time:

- **storageclassName**: provides the storageclass to be used for volumes in Kubernetes, such as those used to store the Graph database or the Kafka log.
- **crawler.K8s.api_url**: The URL of the Kubernetes API for the cluster being monitored.
- **crawler.K8s.sa_token**: If the connector is not running under a sufficiently privileged service account, the token with sufficient permissions to obtain configuration information through the Kubernetes API must be provided in this parameter.
- **crawler.prometheus.server.url**: The hostname of the Prometheus query API.
- **crawler.prometheus.server.port**: The port of the Prometheus query API.
- **crawler.prometheus.metric**: The name of the metric to capture (default is *CODECO_freshness*).
- **crawler.prometheus.entity**: The name of the entity in the metadata graph to attach the metric to.
- **pathfinder.url**: The URL of the MDM API.

These parameters may be provided by cluster in a multi-cluster environment, which each set of values provided to the corresponding connector.

Implicitly, it provides the MDM Kubernetes connector with a service account with sufficient privilege to access the Kubernetes API, where the Kubernetes connector is able to gather all relevant information about pods, workers nodes, and any CRDs available.

6.4.4 Single Cluster Operation

MDM interfaces to ACM to collect K8s infrastructure data (I-ACM-MDM-1) required for deployment and configuration of the MDM API, Graph database and connectors. Connectors interact with other data sources (Prometheus, Kubernetes API) and send the metadata to MDM (I-MDM-E-1). The collected metadata is then stored and processed into the Graph database, to provide complete data observability in the cluster. The MDM knowledge graph links all the collected information to create additional value since attributes like data lineage are shown explicitly and attributes like data classification can be derived. For example, assuming the appropriate connectors are running, Personal Information coming from a video feed that is processed in the cloud and stored in an S3 bucket would make in turn the contents of the S3 bucket Personal Information. As illustrated in Figure 35, in each cluster MDM connectors interface to local components, including Kubernetes (through the K8s API) and other CODECO components such as Prometheus, and collect relevant information. If the data source has an event interface it will trigger the information update and otherwise the collector will poll the source and generate an event to MDM. The new or updated information is added to MDM's knowledge graph, and if events have been subscribed to, an event will be generated to the relevant component.

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Specific metrics computed from the generated knowledge graph with all associated metadata are made available through CRDs to other CODECO components (mainly PDLC) as described above. Exploration of the Knowledge Graph is always possible through the exposed Graph Query endpoint in the MDM API.

Figure 35: MDM single cluster operation.

The data requirements of the application workload can be exposed as part of its definition (CODECO Application model, cf. to section 3.3.1.3.4.2). The CODECO PDLC component integrates the information provided by MDM with the other information it collects regarding the state of applications and systems to create and evaluate models to predict their future performance. PDLC leverages the MDM knowledge graph through the MDM API to obtain the metrics described above. The scheduling in SWM can also leverage this information (derived from PDLC).

6.4.5 Federated Operation

MDM-FC enables data-aware orchestration in CODECO by providing a unified, semantic view of data, applications, and infrastructure across CEI environments. MDM represents metadata as a typed property graph and relies on an event-driven architecture based on Apache Kafka to decouple metadata ingestion from storage and querying. MDM-FC is designed to operate efficiently in federated environments without requiring tight coupling between clusters. While a fully symmetric federation with global metadata replication is conceptually possible, CODECO adopts a neighbourhood-scoped deployment model that aligns with its bounded coordination principle, and MDM-FC is deployed in each neighbourhood, as represented in Figure 36.

Within a neighbourhood, a single cluster acts as the MDM hub, hosting the graph database and MDM API for that neighbourhood. Connectors deployed on MCs report metadata to the hub instance, and PDLC-FC instances query the hub to retrieve data-related metrics relevant to the applications deployed in the neighbourhood. This avoids maintaining a global metadata view when it is not required for orchestration. If a Managed Cluster leaves a neighbourhood, its metadata simply stops being updated. If the MDM hub becomes unavailable, ACM-FC can redeploy the MDM instance on another cluster and reconfigure connectors accordingly. Although this failover scenario is supported by design, it is not considered part of the standard operational workflow.

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Figure 36: MDM-FC operation.

When clusters participate in multiple neighbourhoods, MDM-FC must avoid deploying a separate metadata stack for each neighbourhood on the same hub. A limited number of MDM instances hosted on Hub clusters can jointly support multiple, potentially overlapping neighbourhoods by consistently mapping neighbourhood identifiers to MDM instances. Connectors can be configured to report to multiple MDM instances, allowing a single connector deployment per cluster to serve several neighbourhoods and reducing overhead. For large-scale deployments, Hub clusters may maintain a *distributed hash table (DHT)* to manage neighbourhood-to-MDM mappings efficiently.

In the general case though, a cluster may be part of multiple neighbourhoods, and the previous approach will not work. This can be generalized if the MDM instance used by the clusters in the neighbourhood is decoupled from the Hub cluster managing those clusters. Assuming there is still an MDM instance per Hub cluster, and that each neighbourhood has a unique identifier, a mapping between neighbourhoods and MDM instances (Hub clusters) can be constructed through the use of a hash table. Given a neighbourhood with identifier N_y , a hash function $\text{Hash}(N_y)$ will map consistently the neighbourhood to a Hub cluster Hub_x . Given that, PDLC in a neighbourhood can be given the MDM API URL of the corresponding Hub cluster, and connectors for those clusters can be deployed to feed the MDM instance in that same Hub cluster.

6.5 NetMA-FC: Network Management and Adaptation

NetMA is the CODECO component responsible for network observability, secure connectivity, and adaptive network management across the CEI continuum. It provides CODECO with the cross-layer network awareness required for informed placement and rescheduling decisions, and with the connectivity infrastructure needed to sustain application microservices as they are deployed, migrated, and adapted across single-cluster and federated cluster environ-

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ments. NetMA bridges SDN with Kubernetes, operating at both the underlay and overlay layers and exposing a standardised northbound interface consumable by ACM, PDLC, and SWM. Its sub-components and interfaces are represented in Figure 37.

NetMA comprises three sub-components. **Secure Connectivity (L2S-M)**²⁶ provides link-layer virtual networking within a cluster and, in the federated cluster phase, extends this to inter-cluster secure overlay connectivity. In the FC variant, L2S-M introduces a distributed SDN control plane built on ONOS and coordinated through RAFT-based IDCO provider instances, a set of *Network Edge Devices (NEDs)* that terminate the intra-cluster L2S-M fabric and stitch it to peer clusters via IPsec/GENEVE tunnels, and an inter-cluster LPM (i-LPM) extension that continuously measures the performance of wide-area overlay links. Inter-cluster network monitoring further extends NSM's probing capability to federated scenarios, enabling on-demand cross-cluster measurements to support pre-orchestration decision-making.

Network State Management (NSM) handles active network probing at underlay and overlay levels, collecting metrics including bandwidth, latency, jitter, packet loss, node degree, link failures, and link energy across all worker nodes in the cluster. NSM is realised through two complementary implementations: *netma-nsm-npp*, an ICMP-based probing plugin designed for flexibility and lightweight deployment, and *netma-nsm-mon*, a node-oriented monitoring approach built on K8s netperf and extended with iPerf3, ICMP Ping, and TCPdump for comprehensive per-link and per-node visibility.

Nemesys acts as the northbound interface of NetMA, consuming the underlay and overlay metrics collected by NSM and integrating them into a coherent topological view exposed as a Kubernetes CRD to ACM and Prometheus.

Figure 37: NetMA, sub-components, interfaces.

26 <https://github.com/Networks-it-uc3m/L2S-M>

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6.5.1 Key Technologies

- The **ALTO**²⁷ **protocol and framework**, as the basis for building a network capability exposure mechanism. This protocol has a TRL of 3-5 being the protocol tested in relevant scenarios but the current implementation to be used is still under development.
- **L2S-M**²⁸ as mechanism for providing link-layer secure connectivity for microservice platforms, for creating and managing virtual networks in K8s clusters. This component has a TRL of 5-6 as has been tested before in simulated scenarios both in European projects and academical tests.
- **Netperf**²⁹ as IP monitoring key enabler. This technology is the basis for the netma-nsm-on, one of the NetMA sub-components related with underlay probing. One of the advantages is its flexibility in integrating new metrics to be monitored in K8s worker nodes. It currently has a TRL of 4-5.
- **ONOS**³⁰ as the SDN controller for transport network management in the creation and use of the network overlay. This component has a TRL of 7-8 as it has already been used in real scenarios in other projects.

6.5.2 NetMA Metrics

Current NetMA metrics are provided in Annex I, Table 9.

6.5.3 Sub-components

6.5.3.1 L2S-M: Secure Connectivity

L2S-M provides the secure overlay connectivity layer for CODECO, operating at OSI Layer 2 to create and manage isolated virtual networks within and across Kubernetes clusters. It complements the CNI plugin approach by equipping each workload with a secondary network interface handled by an SDN controller, ensuring that all application traffic is isolated from the standard Kubernetes overlay and that QoS guarantees can be enforced at the link layer. L2S-M operates in both single-cluster and federated cluster contexts; the multi-cluster variant extends the intra-cluster fabric with inter-cluster overlay stitching and a distributed control plane.

Single-cluster design. The single-cluster L2S-M architecture, illustrated in Figure 38, is structured across two planes. The **Control Plane** consists of the SDN Controller (the L2S-M Control Plane), an LPM Collector responsible for aggregating link-layer performance measurements, and a CR/CRD-type interface that exposes two categories of plugin endpoints to the CODECO components — *Plugins (requests)*, through which ACM, SWM, and PDLC request the creation or modification of virtual networks, and *Plugins (exposure)*, through which measured performance data is published back to those components. The SDN Controller governs all data-plane elements over the SDN Control Network. The **Data Plane** comprises compute nodes distributed across one or more network locations (A, B, C in Figure 38), each equipped with a *Programmable L2 Switch (PLS)* and an LPM agent. The PLS instances are interconnected by overlay links managed by the SDN Controller, forming the programmable link-layer substrate on which virtual networks are instantiated. The LPM agent at each node continuously measures the performance of the overlay links it participates in and feeds those meas-

²⁷ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/alto/about/>

²⁸ <http://l2sm.io>

²⁹ <https://github.com/HewlettPackard/netperf>

³⁰ <https://opennetworking.org/onos/>

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urements to the LPM Collector. Importantly, compute nodes of a single cluster may be physically distributed across different network locations, and L2S-M provides transparency with respect to the underlying transport technology and independence from IP addressing in this scenario.

Figure 38. NetMA Secure Connectivity Design.

Multi-cluster extension. The federated cluster variant of L2S-M, illustrated in Figure 39, retains the full single-cluster design within each cluster and introduces three additional elements to stitch the per-cluster fabrics into a federation-wide secure overlay. First, each cluster hosts a *Network Edge Device (NED)*, a virtual SDN gateway that terminates the intra-cluster L2S-M fabric and establishes IPsec/GENEVE tunnels to the NEDs of peer clusters, creating the inter-cluster overlay. The inter-cluster overlay links (shown in green in Figure 39) inherit the per-flow QoS guarantees, encryption, and multi-tenant isolation already enforced inside each cluster by L2S-M. Second, an *inter-cluster LPM (i-LPM)* instance is co-located with each NED, measuring the performance of the VxLAN tunnels it terminates, including delay, available bandwidth, and link-failure counters, and feeding those measurements into the local Prometheus pipeline. Third, an *Inter-Cluster Performance Metrics* block (NSM, Network Exposure) aggregates the topology and performance views contributed by each cluster, exposing them northbound via ALTO and HTTPS-based interfaces. The SDN Control Network governs all NEDs across the federation, and northbound CRs make the aggregated view available to ACM, SWM, and PDLC for placement and rescheduling decisions.

Distributed SDN control plane. To manage the inter-cluster overlay at federation scale, L2S-M introduces a distributed SDN controller built on the ONOS framework, with one instance deployed per Hub cluster. Each instance acts as an *Inter-Domain Connectivity Orchestrator*

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(IDCO) provider. IDCO instances coordinate via the Raft consensus algorithm providing election safety, log consistency, and state machine safety with Raft-based state sharing and leadership elections managed through the Atomix framework.

The relationship between NEDs and SDN controllers is **many-to-one** (one controller manages multiple NEDs); the relationship between neighbourhoods and SDN controllers is **one-to-one** (one controller instance per neighbourhood). IDCO providers synchronise virtual link definitions, NED metadata, and translated flows across the federation.

When a workload is deployed or migrated across clusters, the originating Hub's IDCO provider shares connection details with peer providers, which configure the corresponding flows and intents on their NEDs using the OpenFlow protocol, compiling *Vlinks* into intents and intents into forwarding rules. Failover mechanisms ensure that if a Hub or its SDN controller becomes unavailable, the affected NEDs automatically reconfigure to follow another active controller instance.

Figure 39: NetMA-FC operation, with focus on L2S-M aspects.

Inter-cluster overlay topology. The inter-cluster overlay can be established using one of two approaches. In the *pre-created topology* approach, VXLAN tunnels between clusters are established at Secure Connectivity installation time, providing an immediately available substrate for virtual network creation at the cost of upfront planning. In the *on-demand topology* approach, NED connections are created only when workloads requiring secure inter-cluster connectivity are scheduled: a Kubernetes ConfigMap is updated to describe the required inter-cluster links, NED file-system watchers detect the change, and the corresponding tunnels are built or torn down dynamically. The on-demand approach is more flexible but requires additional control-plane logic for lifecycle management.

i-LPM: Inter-Cluster Link Performance Measurement. The i-LPM extends the intra-cluster LPM capability to the inter-cluster VXLAN tunnels. Each i-LPM instance is deployed as an independent Pod co-located with its NED, reads the current inter-cluster overlay topology at startup, and monitors all relevant tunnel links using iPerf and Ping for active measurements.

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Metrics are registered in Prometheus, and the monitoring endpoints are reconfigured dynamically via Kubernetes ConfigMap updates as the overlay topology evolves, without requiring redeployment.

Federated network monitoring. As illustrated in Figure 40, the federated monitoring architecture extends NSM's netma-nsm-npp probing capability across cluster boundaries. Within each cluster, NPP instances are deployed on every worker node and operate in a full mesh, where each NPP instance probes all others within its cluster, providing complete intra-cluster measurement coverage. Cross-cluster connections are established between selected NPP instances in peer clusters, enabling on-demand inter-cluster measurements to be issued before orchestration actions are taken. This design allows CODECO to validate network quality assumptions, avoid scheduling under degraded path conditions, and improve placement resilience through informed, measurement-driven resource selection.

Figure 40: CODECO approach for federated network monitoring.

6.5.3.2 NSM: Network State Management

NSM is being designed to support multiple networking probing approaches (for potential probing tools and their implementation, please refer to D14). CODECO networking metrics are provided at an overlay and underlay level, at a node and application perspective. Examples of networking metrics being considered (rf. to Annex I, Table 12) are: throughput, latency, packet loss, link failure, and link energy, which are important for evaluating network performance.

NSM is currently based on two different approaches, described next. **Netma-nsm-npm** relies on ICMP and sockets to bring information at a networking level. **Netma-nsm-mon** considers a node-oriented approach to collect networking metrics and is based on an existing network probing aggregation approach, K8s netperf. These two approaches are explained next, with the caveat that the aim in CODECO is to provide flexibility to allow different network probing solutions to be integrated, based on a common abstraction.

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6.5.3.2.1 netma-nsm-npp

netma-nsm-npp is based on ICMP Echo Requests and is aiming at allowing a high degree of flexibility in design. Netma-nsm-npp is an example of a network probing plugin which considers availability of metrics to meet expected QoS requirements. Currently, it provides throughput, latency, and packet loss.

The design of netma-nsm-npp emphasizes flexibility, allowing it to adapt to various network environments and requirements. Users can configure the tool to measure different metrics by setting appropriate flags during execution.

- **Throughput:** The tool measures the data transfer rate between the source and destination. This is done using the measure throughput function, which sends a large amount of data over a TCP connection and calculates the rate of data transmission.
- **Latency:** The time taken for a packet to travel from the source to the destination and back is measured using the ICMP Echo mechanism. The *measure_latency* function captures this delay, providing data into the responsiveness of the network.
- **Packet Loss:** The *measure_packet_loss* function sends multiple packets and calculates the percentage of lost packets, indicating the reliability of the network connection.

The tool supports integration with various data communication platforms, and data are exposed via Prometheus on real-time. This allows for seamless data transmission and real-time monitoring. The Nemesys subcomponent listen to specific designed port to gather the measurement results.

The netma-nsm-npp probe is deployed as a DaemonSet in K8s, ensuring that each node within the cluster runs a replica of the probe. This deployment strategy guarantees that every node continuously measures the network performance to all other nodes in the cluster. When new nodes are added to the cluster, new replicas of the probe are automatically created to maintain coverage. The probes operate asynchronously, performing measurements every 120 seconds by default, with each measurement cycle taking approximately 4 seconds. This setup ensures real-time, distributed monitoring of network metrics across the entire Kubernetes cluster, facilitating efficient and scalable network performance management.

6.5.3.2.2 netma-nsm-mon

netma-nsm-mon is the node-oriented network monitoring sub-component of NetMA, responsible for collecting underlay network metrics across the cluster through a combination of active probing and eBPF-based passive instrumentation. It extends the open-source K8s netperf tool (Apache 2.0³¹) with additional metrics and a flexible architecture that allows new measurement capabilities to be integrated without structural changes. netma-nsm-mon collects the following metrics: **bandwidth, latency, packet loss, jitter, node degree, link failures, link energy, and flow energy**. These are relevant to compute greenness targets via the PDLC-CA node scoring mechanism and inform placement and rescheduling decisions in SWM.

Deployment model. As illustrated in Figure 41, netma-nsm-mon follows a distributed deployment in which one agent instance runs per worker node, as a K8s Cronjob. Each agent is responsible for all measurements originating from its node. Results are published via two

³¹ K8s Netperf is a benchmarking tool designed to measure various aspects of networking performance, focusing on bulk data transfer and request/response performance using TCP or UDP with the Berkeley Sockets interface. It supports tests over IPv4 and IPv6, and can be used on multiple platforms, including Unix, Linux, and Windows. It provides a simple way to test network performance between pods using various metrics

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channels: per-node K8s ConfigMaps, updated at the end of each measurement window, and a gRPC interface to a cluster-scoped aggregation controller.

Figure 41: netma-nsm-mon deployment model.

Measurement dimensions. Each monitoring round executes four measurement tasks concurrently, each targeting a distinct network observable:

Bandwidth and link energy are derived from eBPF byte-counting chains attached to each inter-node link. For each remote node, the agent reads cumulative received and transmitted byte counts from the eBPF data structures and computes throughput rates over the elapsed interval. Link energy is estimated from these byte counts using the linear power model of Feeney et al. [32], applied separately to the receive and transmit directions with empirically calibrated coefficients ($P_{rx} = P_{0,rx} + a_{rx} \cdot S$; $P_{tx} = P_{0,tx} + a_{tx} \cdot S$, where S is packet size in bytes). Total link energy per interval is the sum of receive and transmit energy contributions. This approach provides continuous, zero-overhead energy estimation without requiring specialised hardware.

Packet loss is estimated from TCP socket retransmission statistics, queried from the kernel's TCP state tables. For each active TCP connection between monitored nodes, the ratio of retransmitted segments to total transmitted segments is computed in both directions; the per-link loss rate is the mean of the two directional estimates. This method provides a passive, application-layer view of loss that captures the effective reliability experienced by TCP flows rather than probe-specific loss.

Node degree and link failure are derived from the kernel's ARP neighbour table. A node is considered reachable if its ARP entry is in one of the states {REACHABLE, STALE, DELAY, PROBE}; node degree is the count of such neighbours. Link failure is quantified as the elapsed time since a neighbour last appeared in a reachable ARP state, providing a soft failure indicator that reflects ARP-level connectivity without requiring active probing.

Latency and flow events are derived from *evolved Passive Ping (ePPing)*³², an eBPF-based passive RTT estimation tool. ePPing attaches to the TC ingress hook in kernel space and passively monitors TCP traffic, using TCP timestamp fields (TSval/TSecr) as flow identifiers to match outgoing packets with their replies and compute per-flow RTTs entirely within the kernel, without copying packets to user space. The per-window output is a stream of per-flow RTT samples in JSON format, from which the agent computes P90 RTT per destination as

³² <https://research.redhat.com/blog/article/passive-network-monitoring-with-ebpf/>

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the latency estimate. ePPing is configured with a per-flow sample rate limit and a maximum sample count per window to bound measurement overhead; the RTT type (minimum or exponentially smoothed) is user-configurable.

Flow energy. Beyond link-level energy, netma-nsm-mon computes energy at the application flow granularity. Each flow identified by ePPing carries byte-count information that allows the Feeney model to be applied at the flow level, producing a per-flow energy estimate that reflects the transmission cost of an individual application data stream rather than the aggregate activity on a physical link. Flow energy and per-flow RTT statistics are written to a dedicated flow-event ConfigMap, providing PDLC-CA with energy-aware observability at the microservice communication level.

Metrics summary. The per-node ConfigMap produced at the end of each window encodes the following metrics for each directed link (*src, dst*): P90 latency (ms), transmit bandwidth (Mbps), packet loss rate, link energy (microwatt-seconds), and link failure duration (seconds). The flow-event ConfigMap additionally encodes per-flow RTT distributions and flow energy estimates.

Federated cluster pipeline. The per-node collection described above feeds into a cluster-wide aggregation pipeline, illustrated in Figure 42. The pipeline involves two roles: the per-node ePPing agent and a cluster-scoped **nsm-controller** acting as a gRPC server. At the end of each measurement window, each agent serialises its full local link state and pushes it to the nsm-controller as a NodeReport message carrying node identity, timestamp, serialised link state, and the count of observed flows. The nsm-controller address is resolved dynamically at each reporting cycle by probing known node addresses for the controller port, removing the need for static configuration. The nsm-controller applies **barrier synchronisation**, deferring cluster-level aggregation until reports from all nodes in the cluster have been received. Once the barrier is satisfied, the controller applies the user-configured aggregation strategy to the collected per-node states and writes a unified cluster-level ConfigMap representing a temporally consistent snapshot of cluster network state. This snapshot is the primary input consumed by PDLC-FC and SWM-FC for cross-cluster placement and rescheduling decisions.

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Figure 42: netma-nsm-mon federated operation. the passive monitoring is provided per cluster and then aggregated for federated clusters.

Cluster-level aggregation. The nsm-controller implements a two-level hierarchical aggregation that reduces the full set of per-link, per-node measurements to five cluster-wide scalar metrics: latency, packet loss, failure time, network energy, and total bandwidth. Aggregation is controlled by a user-configured strategy (*AGG_MODE*), with two options: **FAIR** (unweighted arithmetic mean, treating all links and nodes equally) and **WEIGHTED** (bandwidth-weighted mean, giving higher weight to links and nodes with greater throughput capacity).

Level 1: per-node reduction. When a node report arrives, the controller reduces the full set of directed link measurements from that node to a single per-node state vector. For each outgoing link to a remote node, the controller extracts latency, bandwidth, energy, failure time, and packet loss. Under FAIR mode, each link contributes equal weight; under WEIGHTED mode, the link's transmit bandwidth serves as its weight. The result for node *n* is provided in Equation 11:

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$$\text{metric}_n = \frac{\sum_{j \in \text{links}(n)} w_j \cdot m_j}{\sum_j w_j} \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

where $w_j = 1$ (FAIR) or $w_j = \text{bw}_j$ (WEIGHTED), for each metric m . Total bandwidth is summed rather than averaged, preserving the aggregate capacity of the node across all its outgoing links.

Level 2: cluster reduction. Cluster aggregation is deferred until the barrier condition is satisfied: the set of nodes that have submitted reports in the current window must be a superset of the set of currently Ready K8s nodes, determined by querying the cluster's node registry at controller initialisation. Only when this condition holds does the controller perform the second aggregation pass, reducing the per-node state vectors to cluster-wide scalars using the same *AGG_MODE* strategy, this time with each node's total metric as its weight under WEIGHTED mode. The five resulting values are computed via Equation 12:

$$\text{metric}_{\text{cluster}} = \frac{\sum_{n \in \text{nodes}} w_n \cdot \text{metric}_n}{\sum_n w_n} \quad \text{Equation 12}$$

with cluster bandwidth as the exception, being the sum $\sum_n \text{bandwidth}_n$ representing total cluster network capacity.

Output: The five aggregated scalars are written atomically to the cluster-metrics Kubernetes ConfigMap in the NetMA namespace. Once the cluster ConfigMap is committed, both the accumulated node state and the set of received reports are cleared, so each measurement window produces an independent, temporally consistent cluster snapshot. The cluster ConfigMap is the primary network state input consumed by PDLC-FC for node scoring and by SWM-FC for cross-cluster placement decisions.

Design rationale. The two-level structure separates link-level variance (absorbed in Level 1) from node-level variance (absorbed in Level 2), producing a scalar cluster summary that is compact enough for low-overhead inter-component consumption while remaining sensitive to the distribution of network quality across the cluster. The WEIGHTED strategy encodes the intuition that high-bandwidth links and nodes carry disproportionately more application traffic and should therefore dominate the cluster-level estimate; FAIR mode provides a uniform baseline appropriate when link capacities are homogeneous.

6.5.3.3 Nemesys-FC: Network Exposure

Nemesys is the component that works as a *North-bound interface (NBI)* for NetMA. It extends the single-cluster Nemesys component to operate across administrative boundaries, acting as a peer in a P2P mesh of Nemesys instances — one per cluster — that collectively maintain a federation-wide, multi-metric network view. Its primary responsibilities are ingesting local underlay and overlay measurements, constructing a unified multi-metric graph, exchanging topology information with peer instances, and exposing the resulting federated network state to PDLC-FC and SWM-FC as K8s CRs.

As illustrated in Figure 43, Nemesys-FC comprises four internal modules organised around a central ALTO Core. The **Prometheus Module** ingests underlay metrics produced by the federated NSM components (*netma-nsm-mon* and *netma-nsm-npp*), reading formatted underlay measurements, e.g., latency, bandwidth, packet loss, node degree, link failure, link energy, and flow energy, from the cluster's Prometheus instance, to which the monitoring agents publish their output.

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Figure 43: Nemesys-FC interactions within NetMA.

The **CR Module** ingests overlay metrics produced by L2S-M-FC, reading formatted overlay measurements from the Kubernetes CR interface exposed by the Secure Connectivity component. These include per-tunnel performance characteristics of the inter-cluster VxLAN overlay managed by the NED layer.

The **ALTO Core** is the computational centre of Nemesys-FC. It receives formatted underlay metrics from the Prometheus Module and formatted overlay metrics from the CR Module and integrates them into two graph structures. The **local graph** represents the network topology and multi-metric state of the local cluster, built entirely from locally observed measurements. The **federated graph** extends the local graph by incorporating remote topology information received from peer Nemesys instances, producing a unified view of the reachable inter-cluster network. The ALTO Core implements an ALTO server conformant with RFC 7285, generating cost maps over these graphs using Dijkstra's shortest-path algorithm and supporting multi-cost maps that capture multiple metrics simultaneously within a single map structure. The resulting integrated topology is published as a NetMA-FC CR, consumed directly by the local (in cluster) PDLC-FC agent for multi-objective placement and rescheduling decisions.

The **federated API** mediates the exchange of topology information between the local Nemesys-FC instance and its peers in the federation. It exposes the locally integrated metrics outward and receives remote metric listings from peer instances, forwarding them to the ALTO Core for incorporation into the federated graph. This exchange follows a P2P pattern in which each instance periodically broadcasts its local view and assembles the federation-wide view incrementally as peer updates arrive, without requiring a central aggregation point.

This architecture provides three key properties for federated orchestration. Firstly, each cluster's Nemesys-FC instance maintains topological knowledge of all participating clusters, enabling cross-cluster awareness without centralised state. Secondly, the multi-cost map structure allows the ALTO Core to compute optimal inter-cluster paths simultaneously across multiple metrics — latency, bandwidth, energy — supporting the multi-objective placement deci-

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sions required by PDLC-FC and SWM-FC. Thirdly, unified graph spanning underlay and overlay layers across cluster boundaries provides the observability foundation required to orchestrate distributed microservices across the full Edge–Cloud continuum.

Information flow. The end-to-end flow within Nemesys-FC proceeds as follows. Underlay probes (FC) publish raw measurements to Prometheus; the Prometheus Module reads and formats these into the internal metric representation. L2SM (FC) publishes overlay measurements as Kubernetes CRs; the CR Module reads and formats these. The ALTO Core integrates both streams into the local graph and combines local and remote data into the federated graph. The federated API simultaneously exports the local integrated view to peers and imports their views, with received remote metrics listed and passed to the ALTO Core for federated graph updates. The ALTO Core periodically serialises the current state of the federated graph as a NetMA-FC CR, making it available to PDLC-FC for consumption.

6.5.4 Single Cluster Operation

During the setup of an application deployment NetMA is activated by ACM and triggers the definition of the network overlay through the policies and requirements received (ACM, SWM), passing the overlay information to SWM (IP, DNS/namespace configuration). This information and the underlay one, will be sent also to PDLC to perform its initial multi-objective estimations, which it will be passed to the SWM to perform the initial configuration process readjustments.

Once this phase is complete, the system enters in the cluster runtime phase. In this phase, SWM readjusts the configuration according to the input it receives, activating NetMA to perform a readjustment of the connectivity between nodes. This will be an iterative process that will be performed periodically as needed by the system, adjusting the behaviour according to the readjustments to be considered at each moment of operation. To enable this readjustment, NetMA will monitor periodically the state of both overlay (L2S-M) and underlay (Network State Monitoring) and exposing the information obtained to SWM (overlay information) and PDLC (overlay and underlay). Once with this information and the forecasted metrics provided by PDLC, SWM will calculate such readjustments. In the initial configuration phase (single cluster), the Secure Connectivity sub-component (i.e., L2S-M) will provide secure connectivity among pods deployed across worker nodes within the cluster, regardless the specific compute nodes involved in the workload deployment. To this purpose, Secure Connectivity supports the flexible creation of virtual networks in the cluster, and the attachment of workload to those virtual networks. Likewise, Secure Connectivity will support the connectivity of workloads towards external networks, i.e., the Internet. This workflow is represented in Figure 44, where both initial configuration and runtime activity is represented, showing also the main interactions between the three main sub-components of NetMA (considering SDN Orchestrator and Secure Connectivity an integrated module).

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Figure 44: NetMA single cluster operations workflow.

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Also, within a single cluster it is expected that NetMA has components on the control-plane of CODECO (secure connectivity, Nemesys), and others residing in the service plane at worker nodes (the LPM pods, a sub-component inside Secure Connectivity module and the different instances of NSM), as represented in Figure 45.

Figure 45. NetMA single-cluster deployment view.

6.5.5 Federated Operation

In a federated cluster environment, NetMA extends its single-cluster functions — underlay and overlay monitoring, secure connectivity, and northbound exposure — across multiple administrative domains. As illustrated in Figure 46, the federated architecture is structured across three tiers connected by four distinct link types, each with a clearly defined scope and function.

Hub control plane (H1, H2). Each Hub cluster hosts two control-plane components: an **Atomix** instance providing the distributed state management substrate for RAFT-based consensus, and a **NetMA IDCO provider** (SDN controller built on ONOS) responsible for orchestrating inter-cluster overlay connectivity. Hub clusters do not run data-plane workloads; their role is exclusively to manage the federation's network control state. Where resilience demands it, an additional Atomix instance can be co-deployed at the Hub (shown as optional in Figure 46), increasing fault tolerance of the consensus group without altering the control architecture. Two link types operate at the Hub level. **Link I2** interconnects the Atomix instances of peer Hub clusters, providing the Raft consensus channel over which IDCO state, e.g., virtual link definitions, NED assignments, forwarding intents, which is synchronised across hubs. **Link I3** carries IDCO control-plane directives from each Hub's SDN controller down to the Managed Clusters it governs, installing and updating flow rules on NEDs via the OpenFlow southbound API.

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Figure 46: NetMA federated operation.

Each Managed Cluster hosts three NetMA components. The **netma-ned** (NED) acts as the cluster's overlay gateway: it terminates the intra-cluster L2S-M fabric and, via IPsec/GENEVE tunnels, stitches that fabric to the NED of every peer cluster within the same application neighbourhood. **I2sm** provides the link-layer virtual networking substrate within the cluster, as described in Section 6.5.3.1. The **netma-msn** component (**netma-nsm-mon**) performs continuous underlay and overlay monitoring within the cluster. Two link types operate at this tier. **Link I1** connects NED instances across clusters — these are the data-plane inter-cluster overlay links over which application microservice traffic flows with the per-flow QoS, encryption, and tenant isolation enforced by L2S-M. **Link I4** connects **netma-msn** instances across clusters, establishing the inter-cluster monitoring channel through which the federated NSM passive pipeline (Section 6.5.3.2.2) performs on-demand cross-cluster measurements and exchanges network state reports.

The Nemesys component (**netma-nmx**) operates at the application neighbourhood scope rather than at the individual cluster level. As shown in Figure 46, a single **netma-nmx** instance is positioned at the neighbourhood boundary (N1), aggregating topology and metric information from all Managed Clusters within that neighbourhood and exchanging it with peer **netma-nmx** instances in other neighbourhoods via **link I3**. This neighbourhood-scoped exchange produces the local and federated multi-metric graphs maintained by the ALTO Core and serialised as NetMA-FC CRs for consumption by PDLC-FC and SWM-FC.

Day-to-day lifecycle management of the data-plane components (NED, L2SM, **netma-msn**) is handled by each cluster's Kubernetes control plane, with operators instantiated by ACM and updated by NetMA's own controllers. The Hub-level IDCO providers manage the inter-cluster

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overlay cooperatively: when SWM-FC records a placement or migration intent in the AssignmentPlan CR, the Hub translates it into network intents, distributes them to the relevant IDCO instances via the I2 consensus channel, and the receiving IDCOs install the corresponding flows on their managed NEDs via I3 control links. Security key rotation for inter-cluster tunnels is handled by FIDO-based certificates issued by ACM's security service and applied to the NED layer without requiring Hub involvement in the data path, ensuring that a temporary Hub outage does not interrupt active inter-cluster traffic flows.

6.6 SWM-FC: Scheduling and Workload Migration

The CODECO SWM component handles the initial deployment, monitoring, and potential migration of application workloads within a single cluster and across multi-cluster environments. This implies assisting the efficient (low latency, lower energy consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) placement of applications and their containers across Edge-Cloud, derived from the information provided by PDLC (e.g., device and node availability; container centrality; network characteristics). The SWM handles, for instance, the “best” placement (based on context-awareness indicators) for the containerised components of an application to be deployed in a cluster, dealing with dynamic properties of available infrastructure, including physical/virtual machines as well as network nodes and links. Further, this placement shall be dynamically adaptable, which implies achieving the efficient (low latency, lower energy consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) migration of containerised micro-services of an application, including their state, across Edge and Cloud, derived from the information provided by PDLC (device and node availability; container centrality, network aspects). SWM provides the following main functionality:

- **Initial placement of workloads based on the application/user QoS requirements.** SWM performs a decision for each application deployment on which workload (pod, Container) should run on which node in a cluster, while fulfilling the QoS requirements of the application. The requirements are expressed by the user DEV via ACM, using the CODECO Application Model, and available to all CODECO components.
- **Dynamic placement of application workloads (re-scheduling).** SWM makes a new decision on placement of workloads whenever conditions change (e.g., new applications/components added, applications/components removed or changed, infrastructure conditions changed, change of QoS requirements by the user).
- **Application workload deployment and re-deployment.** SWM takes care that the workloads are executed on the selected nodes and takes remedial actions in case of failure, using native K8s mechanisms.
- **Application workload migration.** SWM manages moving a workload already running on a compute node to another compute node. This may be implemented in different qualities and steps:

SWM , its sub-components and interfaces are represented in Figure 47.

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Figure 47: SWM sub-components and interfaces.

6.6.1 Key Technologies

The initial design and components of SWM is based on the SIE existing background implementation of “Seamless Computing” [22]. The “Seamless Computing Orchestrator” is built as an extension to the K8s control plane, making use of new CRDs/CRs and respective controllers and operators. Main technologies in SWM are:

- K8s, the K8s control plane and the K8s extended API (all TRL 9); the controller and scheduling frameworks (TRL 9).
- Google Remote Procedure Call (gRPC, TRL 9) and Protocol Buffers (Protobuf, TRL 9).
- Go programming language (Golang, TRL 9).

The QoS Scheduler is currently available for CPU architectures AMD64 and ARM64.

6.6.2 Sub-components and CRDs

A very basic concept that is integrated in SWM is the so-called SWM QoS model. It is a formal model to describe application requirements provided by the user (a translation is performed from the CAM by ACM into the SWM Application model) and the infrastructure (*Infrastructure Model*). SWM resides on the control plane of K8s. It extends the K8s resource model by some CRs, making use of the K8s controller pattern to implement controllers for those resources.

SWM implements the following CRs, as represented in Figure 48 and described next:

- **ApplicationGroup**: Bundles a set of *Applications* that shall be placed/scheduled together. Using this construct, users can explicitly control the granularity and sequence of placement decisions. Has been extended for FC operation with two fields, *neighbourhood* and *single-cluster* (see section 6.6.2.1).
- **Application**: Bundles a set of *Workloads* and *Channels* that belong to a (modular and distributed) application. Has been extended for FC operation with two fields, *cluster* and *single-cluster* (see section 6.6.2.1).

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- **Workload:** Represents a component of an *Application*, is defined by a *Workload* spec that is an extension of the K8s pod spec. Typical characteristics of a *Workload* are compute, memory, and storage requirements. Has been extended for FC operation with a *cluster* pinning field (see section 6.6.2.1). In FC operation, a workload's tuple is extended with an optional cluster identifier. If present, the solver constrains the workload to nodes within the named cluster only.
- **Channel (object):** Represents an explicit, unidirectional communication relation of a *Workload* to other *Workloads*. Current attributes of a *Channel* are bandwidth and latency (in the sense of requirements of the application). These attributes are used by the Workload Placement Solver to match with the available network infrastructure capabilities and conditions when deciding on the placement of the *Workloads*. In CODECO, the Channel CR is expected to integrate additional attributes to further strengthen the network awareness, and to integrate a broader notion of context-awareness, as being defined in CODECO.
- **Channel (CR):** Each *Channel* object will be mapped to a *Channel* CR that represents an explicit communication service in the network infrastructure. Depending on the underlying network technology and service class, it may be possible or required to setup communication services to reserve network resources and to guarantee certain QoS requirements for *Channels* between *Workloads* that are placed on different nodes. The *Channel* resource keeps track and manages the lifecycle and states of such a communication service, handling the required interactions with the respective service endpoints of the network infrastructure. As the QoS guarantees in CODECO are provided via NetMA with a new level of sophistication, this CR may or may not have a strong relation to network resources handled by NetMA.
- **NetworkTopology:** Represents a compact description of the overall network that is available for the *Channels*, i.e. for explicit communication between *Workloads*. It is used by NetMA to communicate and update the available network resources to SWM. The NetworkTopology consists of nodes (compute nodes, network nodes), network links, and network paths (optional). For better internal handling, SWM translates the NetworkTopology into own internal CRs: NetworkEndpoint, NetworkLink, NetworkPath. There is a separate NetworkTopology per so-called network implementation. In CODECO, currently two network implementations are used: K8s-network and L2S-M-network. While the K8s-network uses the standard K8s overlay network for best effort communication, the L2S-M-network uses the NetMA Secure Connectivity (L2S-M) for network services with dedicated QoS. Reused without schema change for inter-cluster networks in FC operation (see Section 6.6.2.1).
- **NetworkEndpoint:** Represents worker nodes in the cluster. It covers aspects of the nodes that are not covered by the K8s standard resource *Node*. Currently, it is used to keep information about network interfaces and related addresses (IP and MAC) on the nodes. Additional aspects and information related to the worker nodes may be added to the *NetworkEndpoint* CR, e.g., information on its specific energy consumption, availability (current and projected). It is envisioned that the *NetworkEndpoint* CR may be controlled by another CODECO component (e.g., ACM).
- **NetworkLink:** Represents the links of the underlying communication network that interconnects the compute nodes of the cluster. Current attributes of a *NetworkLink* are bandwidth, available bandwidth, and latency. Network awareness shall be further extended in CODECO, being currently envisioned that the *NetworkLink* CR will be controlled by another CODECO component, NetMA. A first sub-set of attributes is provided in Annex I. A

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NetworkLink connects a *NetworkEndpoint* or *NetworkNode* with another *NetworkEndpoint* or *NetworkNode*.

- **NetworkPath:** Besides the physical network topology, the paths (or routes) that can be used to transmit data between any pair of endpoints are relevant to decide on usage and/or allocation of network resources. In the current implementation, *NetworkPaths* are calculated by SWM from the existing network topology. As part of the scheduling decision, each Channel is assigned a *NetworkPath*. For the L2S-M-network, SWM requests a reservation for a *NetworkPath* for each Channel from the NetMA component.
- **AssignmentPlan:** CR that contains the result of the placement decision, as returned by the Workload Placement Solver. This includes for an *ApplicationGroup*: for all *Workloads* the *Nodes* they shall be placed on, and for all *Channels* the *NetworkPath* that shall be used. In FC operation, the *AssignmentPlan* additionally carries the intra-cluster latency contribution for each cross-cluster channel, which is propagated into the subsequent cluster's L2 problem.

Figure 48: SWM CRs and objects.

As illustrated in Figure 48, SWM is composed of the following components:

- **Extended K8s API/ CODECO CRs.** The main API of SWM is the (extended) K8s API. It serves as an API to users of SWM (e.g., to deploy applications, or to request status information about them), but also as a system interface towards the compute infrastructure via the Kubelets running on the worker nodes (e.g., to update resource information about the compute nodes, or to instruct the deployment of pods on a worker node). It is also via this API that SWM interacts with other CODECO components. The interfaces to other CODECO components are implemented as CRs, either as an extension of the existing SWM CRs, or as new ones.
- **QoS model.** The QoS Model is used by SWM to decide on the placement of workloads of an application. It is not a component, but a data model that is used in different places, as explained in subsection 6.6.2.2 (SWM QoS Model).

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- **SWM controller-manager.** The SWM controller-manager bundles a couple of SWM custom controllers that manage SWM CRs. In FC operation, the controller for groups is extended with a **Federated Placer** that orchestrates the sequential L2 problem-solving process across Managed Clusters. An additional controller for Cluster resources is also introduced, tracking cluster reachability.
- **QoS Scheduler.** The QoS Scheduler is a custom scheduler that is built using the K8s scheduling framework³³, it runs as a pod in the K8s cluster, and it registers as scheduler to the K8s control plane. It implements the so-called scheduling plugins for certain phases of the K8s scheduling lifecycle. While the K8s standard scheduler schedules each pod individually, one of the specific mechanisms of the QoS Scheduler is that it decides on the placement of all pods of an *ApplicationGroup* at once. This is required to consider dependencies between the pods (e.g., communication relations and QoS), and to treat the pod placement as a graph problem, rather than a sequential, linear problem. The deployment of the pods within an *ApplicationGroup* is held back, until the placement decision is taken, and all communication resources have been confirmed (if applicable). In FC operation, node recommendations from PDLC originate in MCs and are forwarded to the Hub's SWM-L1 instance with node names stripped. The extension mechanism itself is unchanged; the anonymisation occurs at the forwarding layer.
- **Workload Placement Solver.** The Workload Placement Solver (see 6.6.2.3) is called by the SWM controller-manager to determine the placement of the workloads of all Applications in an *ApplicationGroup*. There can be different implementations of Workload Placement Solvers. The API uses gRPC, where the QoS Model (call of Workload Placement Solver) and the placement decision (returned result) are described as Protobuf. The Workload Placement Solver is deployed as a pod in K8s. In CODECO, an implementation of the QoS Solver is provided as source code and could also be used as blueprint to implement further solvers, optimizers, or heuristics (e.g., learning-based implementations). A more sophisticated optimizer is available as container image for use by the CODECO partners within the CODECO project. The solver interface is extended for FC operation (see Section 6.6.2.1).
- **Cluster.** A new resource type introduced in SWM-FC. Holds aggregated and administrative information about a cluster in the neighbourhood, including reachability state. Cluster resources are used exclusively by the SWM-L1 instance on the Hub cluster; Managed Cluster SWM-L2 instances require no cluster resources.

6.6.2.1 FC Extensions to Custom Resources and Solver Interface

SWM-FC reuses the CRD set of the single-cluster SWM without breaking backward compatibility. All FC-specific fields are additive extensions: a CR submitted to SWM-FC is a valid CR for SWM, with the new fields treated as unknown and ignored. This means a single application description can be submitted to either a single-cluster or a federated SWM instance without modification; federation-aware behaviour activates only when the FC-specific fields are present.

ApplicationGroup. The *ApplicationGroup* resource gains two new fields. The *neighbourhood* field specifies the ordered list of cluster names across which the group's workloads may be placed. This list defines the scheduling scope: SWM-L1 considers only the clusters named in the neighbourhood when solving the placement problem, and the neighbourhood must not be modified once placement has begun — it is immutable for the lifetime of an active group. The

³³ <https://github.com/kubernetes/enhancements/tree/master/keps/sig-scheduling/624-scheduling-framework>

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single-cluster flag, when set, constrains all workloads of all applications in the group to reside in the same cluster, effectively reducing the problem to a single-cluster placement despite the federated context. Placement does not begin until sufficient applications are present in the group and status information is available for every cluster in the neighbourhood.

Application. The *Application* resource gains a *cluster* field that pins all workloads of the application to a named cluster. SWM-FC enforces this constraint strictly: if no cluster with the specified name exists in the neighbourhood, the application cannot be placed. A *single-cluster* flag is also added, operating at application granularity to constrain all of that application's workloads to a single cluster while allowing other applications in the same group to be distributed freely.

Cluster. The *Cluster* resource is a new type introduced by SWM-FC with no equivalent in the single-cluster CRD set. It holds aggregated and administrative information about a cluster in the neighbourhood including reachability state and aggregate resource availability and is stored in SWM-FC's namespace on the Hub cluster. Cluster resources are used exclusively by the SWM-L1 instance; SWM-L2 instances running in Managed Clusters require no cluster resources, as all information needed to solve an L2 problem is provided directly in the scheduling request. This design preserves cluster privacy: no internal topology, node names, or link identifiers leave the cluster.

NetworkTopology. The *NetworkTopology* resource, already used to describe intra-cluster network structure, is reused without schema change to represent inter-cluster networks. For an inter-cluster network, clusters themselves serve as the "worker" nodes in the topology graph, i.e., each cluster is represented as a node, and NED-to-NED links between clusters are the edges. Network name matching is the mechanism by which SWM-FC stitches together intra-cluster and inter-cluster networks: if a network named *l2sm* exists within two clusters and an inter-cluster link of the same name connects them, SWM-FC treats them as the same logical fabric and allows channels to span the boundary. This name-based stitching eliminates the need for any explicit cross-cluster network configuration beyond the shared name.

Workload. The *Workload* resource gains a *cluster* field that pins the workload to a specific named cluster. As with the application-level cluster constraint, SWM-FC enforces this strictly: if the named cluster is unavailable or not in the neighbourhood, the application fails to place.

Solver interface extensions. The interface between SWM-FC and the Workload Placement Solver is extended in two respects. First, all new CR fields described above are propagated into solver requests, allowing custom solver implementations to access neighbourhood membership, cluster constraints, and single-cluster flags when computing placements. Second, a *latency* field is added to the channel assignment result: when an L2 problem is solved in the first cluster of the sequence, the solver returns the intra-cluster latency contribution for each cross-cluster channel alongside the node assignment. This value is injected into the L2 problem of the subsequent cluster, enabling end-to-end latency verification across the cluster boundary without requiring any direct communication between the two clusters' solvers. The extended interface is backward compatible: a solver written for the single-cluster SWM can participate in federated scheduling by ignoring the new fields, using the standard node assignment logic for intra-cluster workloads.

6.6.2.2 State Diagrams for CRDs

6.6.2.2.1 ApplicationGroup

Figure 49 shows the state diagram of the SWM CRD *ApplicationGroup*. In single-cluster operation, the *ApplicationGroup* transitions from *Waiting* to *Optimizing* when the minimum number of applications are present. **In FC operation, an additional condition applies: status**

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information must be available for every cluster in the neighbourhood before placement begins. If a cluster in the neighbourhood is unreachable (e.g., its SWM-L2 instance does not respond to a ping command), it is excluded from scheduling; if this makes placement impossible, the group remains in Waiting. Triggered by that condition, the state progresses to “Optimizing”, and the Workload Placement Solver is called to calculate the placement for the Workloads and Channels for all applications in the ApplicationGroup. Depending on the outcome, the ApplicationGroup either enters the state “Failed” or “Scheduling”. In the state “Scheduling”, the Channels for all Applications are established and the pods corresponding with the Workloads of all Applications are scheduled. Once all Applications are running, the ApplicationGroup returns to the “Waiting” state.

Figure 49: SWM CRD ApplicationGroup state diagram.

6.6.2.2.2 Application

Figure 50 shows the state diagram for an Application CR. Once created, the Application is in the state “Waiting”, where it waits for the trigger from the ApplicationGroup to start scheduling pods for its Workloads.

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Figure 50: SWM CRD Application state diagram.

As soon as some pods are in the state Pending, the Application also moves to this state, until all pods are running (the Application transitions into “Running”) or at least one pod or Channel fails (the Application transitions into “Failing”).

6.6.2.2.3 Channel

Figure 51 shows the state diagram for a Channel CRD. This state diagram provides a generic model to implement even complex network interactions. The states represent the different steps for reserving resources locally as well as in the network, getting acknowledgement from the network, as well as observing QoS during operation, and freeing resources when cancelling or deleting a Channel.

In summary, the following steps correspond to the Channel states:

- **Requested:** The Channel was created by the ApplicationGroup controller (as a consequence of being part in an SWM Application Model that was requested by ACM). This triggers a review of logical resources to establish the Channel, like e.g. required IP addresses.
- **Reviewed:** The logical resources are available. In this state, physical resources are checked (still from a local perspective). This can be e.g. checking the available resources on the required network links as reported by the NetworkTopology CR.
- **Implementing:** Physical resources are deemed sufficient and the Channel is requested from the corresponding Network Manager. For intra-cluster channels, this is the local NetMA instance. **For cross-cluster channels in FC operation, SWM-L1 additionally requests the Hub's NetMA instance to establish the required inter-cluster L2S-M link between the relevant NEDs before the local channel segments are activated..**

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- **Implemented:** Once the requested Channel is acknowledged by the external Network Manager, CNI metadata (network annotations) are attached to the pods at both ends of the Channel (sending and receiving end).
- **Acknowledged:** Once the pods are successfully annotated, the ApplicationGroup controller creates the K8s services and endpoints, that allow the application to make use of the Channel using DNS name resolution.
- **Running:** The Channel is ready to be used to transfer data.

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Figure 51: Channel state diagram.

6.6.2.3 QoS Model

The SWM QoS model consists of two parts: the *Application Model* and the *Infrastructure Model*. The *Application Model* describes distributed, modular applications, that consist of workloads that communicate via interfaces. The attributes of an application are expressing the QoS requirements of the application. The *Infrastructure Model* describes the hardware entities that form the execution environment for the applications. It consists of compute and network infrastructure, particularly compute nodes, network nodes, and network links. The attributes of the Infrastructure Model express the resources and capabilities of the infrastructure. In FC operation, the Infrastructure Model is extended with a **cluster node type** that represents a remote cluster as an abstract node in the placement graph. A cluster node carries aggregated capacity (sum of node resources across the cluster) and maximum per-node capacity, but exposes no internal topology — node names, link names, and internal paths remain private to each cluster. The latency and bandwidth of the link to a cluster node reflect the inter-cluster NED link characteristics. This abstraction allows the Workload Placement Solver to reason about cross-cluster placement without violating cluster privacy.

Further data may be required to define the decision objective, i.e., the criteria that are optimized or at least used as guidance to prioritize and finally select a placement of the workloads of an application. A generic extension mechanism has been implemented, that allows to define weights (called node recommendations) for each workload as part of the *Application Model*. These node recommendations can be used to express any combination of criteria to influence the scheduling. The node recommendations are considered by the *Workload Placement Solver* to place workloads on the suggested nodes, as far as the constraints given by the *Application Model* (e.g. compute capacity, network requirements) can be fulfilled.

Regarding network QoS, SWM implements two service classes, ASSURED and BESTEFFORT. The BESTEFFORT service class uses the ordinary K8s overlay network to communicate over the dedicated *Channels* requested in the *Application Model*. *Channels* with the service class ASSURED are implemented using the overlay network provided by NetMA. For this, dedicated L2S-M Vlinks are requested from NetMA for each Channel.

6.6.2.4 QoS Scheduler Extension Mechanisms

As described above, a generic extension mechanism has been implemented to influence the behaviour of the SWM QoS scheduler without having to change the implementation. For each Workload, so-called node recommendations can be defined in the Application Model. They define weights where to place this Workload, which serve as the primary optimization criterion for the placement decision, after fulfilling all QoS constraints.

6.6.2.5 Workload Placement Solver

The SWM solver works with a set of applications each having a set of workloads. There are channels connecting two workloads. This logical description of an application is mapped to a set of (compute) nodes connected by network paths, i.e., the physical infrastructure of a Kubernetes cluster. A workload and a channel specify criteria that a node or network path must support.

The SWM solver considers for each workload the set of nodes it may be assigned to (e.g., with respect to node resources such as CPU and RAM) and for each channel the set of network paths it may use (with respect to network resources such as bandwidth and latency). For each workload and channel there is a decision variable defining the set of options available.

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There is a single list with all decision variables. Variables for workloads are ordered so that workloads with few options are checked first. The variable for a channel is inserted right after the variables for its two workloads. Consider two workloads A and B checked in this order. The variable for a channel connecting these workloads follows directly the variable for workload B. When the workloads were placed, the Solver can select a suitable path between the nodes.

The Solver then traverses the list of decision variables to find a solution. If the currently selected set of nodes and paths is not suitable, the Solver tries another set until a solution is found. The Solver may not be able to place all applications in a cluster. In this case it drops the last application and tries again.

6.6.2.5.1 Sequence Diagram

The target environment for the SWM Solver is currently a K8s cluster where Solver returns a solution for an assignment problem to the SWM QoS Scheduler. Figure 52 shows the interaction between Solver and Scheduler. In this setup only the Solver’s component “solved” is involved. Component “solve” is not used. To keep the figure simple, the user talks directly with Scheduler to request a deployment. In a real cluster the user talks to Kubernetes’ API that reaches out to Scheduler as appropriate.

Figure 52: Interaction between the SWM QoS Scheduler and Solver.

In a development setting Solver’s components “solve” and “solved” are used as shown in Figure 53. The user uses component “solve” to send requests to component “solved” running as a background process. In this setup the server can be located on the same machine or on another machine. The user installs the command-line applications of “solve” and “solved” as appropriate. The first part in the figure below shows how an assignment problem given in “native” form (e.g., as a JSON file) is handled. The user passes the file to solve that sends it to solved via the gRPC interface. solved computes a solution for the assignment and returns the solution via the gRPC interface to solve that displays it to the user. The second part shows how solve handles an assignment problem given in Solver’s special text format for assignment problems. An assignment problem is easier to specify in this format.

If the Solver talks to a server in this way the server can be running as a background process or in a Kubernetes cluster. The user passes the process’ address on the command-line when invoking solve.

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Figure 53: Interaction between the SWM Solver’s components.

For testing purposes, it is sometimes convenient to “just” determine a solution for an assignment problem, as represented in Figure 54. If solve is not given an address of a server to talk to, it solves the given assignment problem itself using exactly the same algorithm as solved.

Figure 54: SWM Solver computing a solution itself.

6.6.2.5.2 Solver’s Backtracking Algorithm

When a user deploys an application group in a cluster, Solver is the component that decides which workload is assigned to which worker node. The task of placing workloads in a cluster corresponds to an *assignment problem*. This section is about the algorithm Solver uses to find a solution to an assignment problem. The SWM Solver follows the principles below when assigning pods to nodes. In contrast to the K8s standard scheduler, the SWM Solver considers applications and not only workloads and knows about the network within a cluster. It is not necessary to specify network requirements for an application:

- The SWM Solver tries to assign all workloads of all applications in an application group to a cluster’s worker nodes considering both computing and network resources.

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- The Solver places as many pods as possible in the cluster. An application is handled in its entirety.
- The Solver distributes workloads using the same rules as Kubernetes (i.e., it computes the same node priority). The set of rules is simplified with respect to Kubernetes as Solver does not consider for instance node or pod affinity.
- The Solver does not try to find the “best” solution for a set of applications but finds a suitable solution (the first is encountered).

6.6.2.5.3 Network Communication

A path describes how two nodes can communicate and defines bandwidth and latency between the two nodes on this path. If the protocol requires to acknowledge messages there is also a path in the reverse direction needed. The reverse path must have sufficient resources for the acknowledgement information. It is not necessary that the path in the reverse direction is the reversed path. Currently, the Solver assumes that the traffic forwarding can be configured with respect to the channels. If there are two channels between two nodes, it is assumed that the traffic moves on the appropriate channel. If the network does not support channel-based forwarding, the assignment might not work properly as network requirements might be violated due to “unexpected” forwarding.

Especially any communication in the “reverse” direction might be problematic. For some network types it may not be possible to specify a particular path for the reverse direction (e.g., for automatic acknowledgements) as they always “reverse” the path of the incoming traffic. In this case, it will be necessary to extend Solver’s model so that different network types are supported. This applies not only to traffic forwarding but also to how a network type makes use of its bandwidth. Collision detection might eat some bandwidth due to the delays it introduces. For properly routing traffic it might be important to know a channel’s chunk size. Using small chunks for a given bandwidth may decrease the available bandwidth by more than the required bandwidth due to the delay introduced by the chunks. Solver does not take this into account.

6.6.2.5.4 Workload Representation

A workload is currently represented by a tuple with the workload requirements: resources, e.g., CPU, RAM, and required and forbidden labels. This is sufficient to solve the assignment problem but has a problem as the SWM Solver is not able to take advantage when there are identical workloads. If two workloads have the same set of requirements, they still may be different workloads as they may use different images. Adding an image identifier to workloads tuple allows Solver to avoid visiting of identical combinations.

6.6.2.5.5 Workload Placement Solver Algorithm

The current algorithm is based on Knuth’s Algorithm B [23], which has been adapted to assign the workloads of a set of applications to nodes while respecting the application networking requirements. The example here provided considers latency and bandwidth as examples of such requirements.

A network is defined by links between two nodes having a given latency and bandwidth. There may be network nodes (i.e., nodes that do not run workloads) to build a certain topology. A network path consists of one or more links and connects two compute nodes. A path’s bandwidth is the minimum bandwidth of its links and its latency the sum of the latency of all links. There may be more than one path between two nodes. A set of nodes may be connected by more than one network. Network paths do not span networks, i.e., all links in a path are of the same network “type”.

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The domains D_k for algorithm B are subsets of the compute nodes for workloads and subsets of the network paths for channels. These subsets are not static as they change (i.e., get smaller) as workloads are assigned to nodes and channels to paths. A property P_l is fulfilled if for all nodes the workloads assigned to the node do not exceed its capacity and for all paths the channels using it do not exceed its bandwidth.

Visiting an assignment means that a solution was found that fulfils all workload and channel requirements. No further checks are necessary to accept this solution.

The algorithm does *not* traverse all assignments. It stops at the first suitable solution found. There is no optimization with respect to the number of total workloads assigned to the cluster. If it is not possible to assign the workloads of all applications, the algorithm reduces the set of applications considered.

Algorithm B (Basic backtrack). Given the domains D_l (set of nodes suitable for a workload and path suitable for channels between workloads) and properties P_l (all workloads or channels W_i placed so far do not exceed nodes or paths' capacities), visit all sequences $x_1 x_2 \dots x_n$.

1. [Initialize] Set $l \leftarrow 1$. Initialize auxiliary data structures:
 - For all channels determine the set of possible paths. Go to step 6 if there is a channel without any path.
 - Determine the network requirements for all workloads.
 - For all workloads determine the set of nodes. A node is available for a workload if the workload's compute and network requirements are satisfied. For each node keep the list of nodes that the workload talks to when assigned to this node. Go to step 6 if there is a workload without nodes.
 - Sort the list of workloads with respect to the number of available nodes. This assigns workloads with few possible nodes early and leads to a fast failure.
 - Insert the variables for channels into the list of variables for workload so that a channel is inserted when its two workloads were placed.
2. [Enter level l .] (Now $P_{l-1}(x_1, \dots, x_{l-1})$ holds.) If $l > n$, visit $x_1 x_2 \dots x_n$ and stop if the solution is suitable or go to step 5. Otherwise (i.e., $l \leq n$) set D_l to the set of nodes or network paths that can currently host W_l . If the set of nodes or channels is empty, go to step 5. Sort nodes in D_l with respect to Kubernetes' node priority or sort channels with respect to latency. Set $j_l \leftarrow 1$ and $x_l \leftarrow D_l[j_l]$, the node with the highest priority in D_l or the path with the lowest latency.
3. [Try x_l .] If $P_l(x_1, \dots, x_l)$ holds, assign W_l to node x_l or to path x_l , set $l \leftarrow l + 1$, and go to step 2.
4. [Try again.] Unassign W_l to node or path x_l . If $j_l < |D_l|$, set $j_l \leftarrow j_l + 1$, $x_l \leftarrow D_l[j_l]$, and go to step 3.
5. [Backtrack.] Set $l \leftarrow l - 1$. If $l > 0$, go to step 4.
6. [Reduce problem size.] If there is more than one application, remove the last application, and go to step 1. (Otherwise stop without a solution).

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6.6.3 Single Cluster Operation

Figure 55: Event sequence diagram for single cluster operation.

The operation of SWM starts when ACM, via the CODECO operator, sets up all components. The steps are the following, being the sequence diagram presented in Figure 55:

- Via ACM/CAM, user DEV describes the application requirements.
- SWM relies on this file to create the description of the desired deployment, considering the CRs ApplicationGroup and Application (including Workloads, Channels, and all relevant attributes).
- Once the minimum number of Applications that are part of the ApplicationGroup is created, the ApplicationGroup custom controller collects all information required for the placement (QoS Model).
- Both the SWM Application and Infrastructure Models are compiled based on the CODECO Application Model, obtained via ACM.
 - The Application Model considers the CRs: Applications, Workloads, Interfaces.
 - The Infrastructure Model is compiled by retrieving information from the related infrastructure custom resources: Node, Endpoint, NetworkLink, NetworkNode, NetworkPath. Basic node capabilities are retrieved using the K8s information. Information about the network (L2S-M overlay) is regularly updated by NetMA (using the NetworkTopology CR).
- The ApplicationGroup custom controller calls the Workload Placement Solver, handing over the QoS Model.

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- The Workload Placement Solver determines a placement for the workloads of the applications, considering all constraints and (if it is an optimizing solver) optimized according to the defined objective. Basic node capabilities are retrieved using the K8s information. Information about the network (L2S-M overlay) is regularly updated by NetMA (using the NetworkTopology CR). The result is returned and placed in the CR AssignmentPlan.
- For each Workload that could be placed, a pod is created, the preferred node for the pod is set according to the placement decision. However, deployment of the pods is still held back.
- For each Channel between Workloads that could be placed, a CR Channel is created. Channels between Workloads that are placed on the same node are tagged as “*loopback channels*” (they do not require connections over the network).
- For all other Channels, the respective network controller (watching the creation of the Channel) will react accordingly. Depending on the network technology and implementation of the network controller, a reaction could be keeping track of occupied bandwidth for the Channel, and/or reserving/establishing an end-to-end channel through the network. In any case, success, or failure of the establishment of an end-to-end channel needs to be reported via the state of the CR Channel.
- Once all Channels of an Application are in state “ACKNOWLEDGED”, the deployment of the pods of the Application will be kicked off.
- K8s will deploy the pods, resulting in downloading and starting the appropriate containers in the selected nodes, and the Applications will become operational.

A so-called QoS deployment works as outlined in Figure 55 To keep the event sequence diagram readable, it shows components (e.g., ACM and SWM) and does not show all controllers involved.

The operation outlined so far starts with a user deploying an application. SWM can also reconsider a deployed application when “the environment” changes. When PDLC (rf. to section 6.3) determines a changed node recommendation for an application already deployed to and running in a cluster, PDLC considers the current deployment and computes node recommendations for the application workload(s) due to certain criteria (e.g., energy efficiency of node or network usage), and sends them to SWM, i.e., it updates SWM’s CRs as appropriate. SWM uses the changed application description to determine a new assignment plan and implements it. In this case the set of workloads running in a cluster does not change but workloads are relocated from one node to another. The event sequence diagram derived from node recommendations triggered changes is provided in Figure 56.

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Figure 56: Event sequence when node recommendations are changed.

Triggers for re-scheduling relate with PDLC and may also be derived from other aspects. For instance, if a node goes down, or if a network link or path does not longer meet the expected QoS level, then SWM is expected to, in the future, consider information provided to reschedule the application workload(s).

6.6.4 Federated Operation

SWM-FC extends SWM's single-cluster scheduling to a federated cluster environment in which application workloads may be distributed across multiple administratively distinct clusters. The fundamental task remains unchanged: assign workloads to nodes and establish network paths for the channels connecting them. The essential difference is that **SWM-FC may now place workloads across a bounded set of clusters, i.e., a CODECO neighbourhood**, rather than within a single cluster, and must do so without exposing the internal structure of any individual cluster to the others.

Network model. SWM-FC operates over the L2S-M overlay network provided by NetMA, or by a similar approach. As illustrated in Figure 57, each cluster in the neighbourhood designates one node as NED, which aggregates all inter-cluster traffic. The inter-cluster network is defined as a set of links between NEDs; this network is not required to be fully connected. If no direct link exists between two clusters, no channel can be established between workloads in those clusters, regardless of path length. SWM-FC supports multiple co-existing inter-cluster networks distinguished by service class, allowing best-effort and QoS-assured channels to coexist within the same neighbourhood.

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Figure 57: A neighbourhood with three clusters connected by an L2SM network

Application model extensions. SWM-FC reuses and extends the CRDs of the single-cluster SWM. The *ApplicationGroup* resource gains a *neighbourhood* field specifying the ordered list of target clusters and a *single-cluster* flag constraining all workloads to a single cluster if set. Individual *Application* and *Workload* resources gain a *cluster* field that pins the application or workload to a specific cluster, which SWM-FC enforces but which reduces scheduling flexibility. The *Cluster* resource is a new type used exclusively by the Hub-level SWM-FC instance to track cluster reachability and aggregate resource availability. The *NetworkTopology* resource, already used for intra-cluster network description, is reused to represent inter-cluster networks, with clusters treated as nodes in the topology graph. An application's workloads are not required to reside in the same cluster, as illustrated in Figure 58. SWM-FC does not manage secondary Kubernetes objects such as ConfigMaps, Secrets, or Volumes; these are assumed to be pre-configured or created dynamically as part of the deployment lifecycle managed by ACM-FC.

Figure 58: An application with workloads in two clusters.

Two-layer deployment. SWM-FC runs one instance per cluster: one in the Hub cluster (SWM-L1) and one in each MC (SWM-L2). The deployed software is identical across instances, but their roles differ. SWM-L1 is the sole orchestrator of federated placements: it receives multi-cluster *ApplicationGroup* specifications, coordinates the sequential L2 problem-solving process across Managed Clusters, tracks the evolving placement state, and executes

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the final implementation phase. SWM-L2 instances forward any multi-cluster specification or change they receive to the Hub, perform node-level placement within their own cluster when requested by SWM-L1, and maintain a continuous reachability signal toward the Hub. Cluster internal properties or resources, e.g., node names, link names, resource availability, remain private to each cluster and are never transmitted outside it.

Federated scheduling algorithm. Placement of a new ApplicationGroup proceeds in three sequential steps, as illustrated by the event-sequence diagram in Figure 59. Failure at any step causes a full rollback; no resources are committed until all steps succeed.

Figure 59: Event-sequence diagram for a placement of an application

Step 1: Cluster ordering. SWM-L1 orders the neighbourhood's clusters into a sequence S that determines the order in which placement is attempted. The ordering function considers three factors: the number of PDLC node recommendations already available for a cluster (clusters with more recommendations are preferred as they carry more contextual signal), the number of workloads already running in a cluster (preferring loaded clusters reduces inter-cluster communication), and the latency of inter-cluster links (preferring faster links between clusters placed consecutively in S). This ordering heuristic avoids cross-cluster communication in the common case where a single cluster can absorb the full application.

Step 2: Sequential L2 problem-solving. SWM-L1 constructs an **L1 problem** that tracks which workloads are assigned to which cluster but does not track node-level placement, which remains private to each cluster. SWM-L1 decomposes the L1 problem into a sequence of **L2 problems**, one per cluster in S . Each L2 problem is a single-cluster scheduling problem augmented with abstract representations of the other clusters in the neighbourhood: each remote cluster is modelled as a special virtual node with unconstrained resources and fast internal connectivity, reflecting the intentional opacity of remote cluster internals. The first cluster in S greedily assigns as many workloads as it can, placing the remainder tentatively on remote cluster nodes. Its solution, which workloads it hosts, on which nodes, and with what intra-cluster channel latency, is returned to SWM-L1, which embeds it into the L2 problem given to

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the next cluster. This continues sequentially until all workloads are assigned or all clusters have been visited. If workloads remain unassigned after visiting all clusters, SWM-FC attempts a second reconsideration round with relaxed placement restrictions; if the second round also fails, the placement is abandoned.

Step 3: Implementation. Once all L2 problems are solved, SWM-L1 instructs each participating Managed Cluster to implement its portion of the assignment: creating pods for workloads and establishing channel paths in the corresponding L2S-M networks. Intra-cluster channels are handled locally by each SWM-L2 instance. Inter-cluster channel segments are coordinated by SWM-L1, which instructs the Hub-level NetMA instance to establish the required inter-cluster network links. Resource reservation for workloads is performed only at this final step and not during problem-solving, which means the infrastructure state may have changed between solving and implementation. If any implementation step fails, all allocations across all clusters are atomically reverted.

Cross-cluster channel latency. A channel connecting workloads in two different clusters has three additive latency components, as shown in Figure 60: the intra-cluster latency in the source cluster (from the workload's node to that cluster's NED), the inter-cluster link latency (between the two NEDs), and the intra-cluster latency in the destination cluster (from the destination cluster's NED to the workload's node). SWM-FC propagates the first cluster's intra-cluster latency contribution into the L2 problem of the second cluster, ensuring that the final channel assignment can guarantee the full end-to-end latency requirement. SWM-FC explicitly minimises the latency in the first cluster's segment to preserve the maximum flexibility for the subsequent cluster's assignment. If the workload in the second cluster is later migrated to a third cluster with different inter- and intra-cluster latency, the propagated first-segment latency remains valid, allowing SWM-FC to re-verify the channel constraint without re-solving the first cluster's L2 problem.

Figure 60: A channel connecting workloads in two clusters has three parts as far as the latency is concerned.

PDLC-triggered migration. Workload migration in the federated setting follows the same three-step procedure as initial placement. PDLC triggers migration by modifying node recommendations in the application's CR within the MC where the workload currently runs. SWM-L2 detects this change and forwards it to SWM-L1 in an aggregated way so that node names are not exposed. SWM-L1 initiates a reconciliation cycle and re-evaluates placement for the affected workloads and, if a better valid placement is found, reserves resources at the destination before releasing those at the source. This reservation-before-release strategy ensures uninterrupted service availability and avoids the failure mode in which the source instance is terminated but the new instance cannot be scheduled. SWM-FC does not manage pod-internal state during migration, which is consistent with Kubernetes pod semantics.

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7 CODECO Answers to Federated Operation Challenges

Section 3 identified a set of open questions across four federated orchestration priority areas. This section provides CODECO's answers to each, grounded in the architectural design and component implementations documented in Sections 4–6.

7.1 Priority 1: Control Plane Decentralisation

At what granularity should autonomy be granted to Managed Clusters?

CODECO answers this at the **application level**. Autonomy is scoped to **application neighbourhoods**, bounded, per-application subsets of MCs rather than granted uniformly per cluster or globally per federation. This allows each application's coordination domain to be independently sized and managed. The CNC determines neighbourhood membership at deployment time, and once the neighbourhood is established, MCs within it can continue local scheduling and communication autonomously without Hub involvement, while clusters outside the neighbourhood remain unaffected. This per-application scoping avoids both the fragility of full cluster-level autonomy and the overhead of global federation-wide coordination.

How should conflicts from divergent local state be resolved when Hub connectivity is restored?

CODECO adopts the **reconciliation-driven model inherited from OCM**. The Hub's desired state expressed as ManifestWork and Policy CRs is authoritative. When connectivity is restored, ACM-FC agents in Managed Clusters reconcile their local state with the Hub's desired state, resolving divergence by converging toward the centrally defined intent. Node-level changes made autonomously during disconnection (e.g., local SWM-L2 rescheduling) are overridden if they conflict with the Hub's updated assignment plan. This provides eventual consistency without requiring a distributed consensus protocol across clusters. The model does not yet provide formal conflict resolution guarantees for concurrent conflicting updates from multiple Managed Clusters, which remains an open engineering item in the Eclipse KUDECO output.

What networking primitives are required for peer-level cluster communication independent of the Hub?

CODECO provides this through the **NED-to-NED inter-cluster overlay** managed by L2S-M and the IDCO distributed SDN control plane. Each cluster hosts a NED that terminates the intra-cluster L2S-M fabric and connects to peer cluster NEDs via IPsec/GENEVE tunnels. The IDCO provider instances deployed at Hub clusters and coordinated via Raft pre-establish the forwarding rules that allow microservices in different clusters to communicate without Hub involvement in the data path. Routing and path selection are computed at the Hub but installed into the NEDs in advance, so that data-plane traffic continues uninterrupted even during Hub outages. FIDO-based certificate rotation is similarly decoupled from real-time Hub availability.

To what extent can OCM's existing extension mechanisms support hybrid models?

CODECO demonstrates that **OCM's core mechanisms** such as ManifestWork, Placement, and Add-ons **provide a sufficient substrate for hybrid governance**, but require significant application-level extensions. ManifestWork is used to propagate CODECO component manifests and neighbourhood definitions to Managed Clusters. The Placement module is extended via CNC to incorporate application-aware criteria beyond label matching. OCM's native policy framework provides the governance baseline. However, the CODECO-specific coordination

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logic (neighbourhood composition, AI-assisted placement, cross-cluster channel management) required entirely new CRDs and controllers that sit above OCM rather than within it. OCM is therefore a necessary but not sufficient foundation for federated CEI orchestration.

7.2 Priority 2: Privacy-preserving Decentralised AI

How can inline training be integrated without requiring continuous central connectivity?

CODECO addresses this through the **MARL architecture of PDLC-DL**, in which each Managed Cluster hosts an independent RL agent that learns from local observations without requiring a central coordinator. The agent updates its policy continuously from locally observed state (CPU, memory, network, data metrics) and exchanges only encrypted model weight updates with peers within the same neighbourhood at configurable intervals. The auction-based algorithm for cross-cluster workload scoring operates on locally maintained estimates, allowing placement recommendations to be produced even when neighbourhood peers are temporarily unreachable. Full formal convergence guarantees under variable CEI connectivity remain an open research question.

How should the update frequency vs communication cost trade-off be calibrated?

CODECO makes this **user-configurable via the TIME_WINDOW parameter** in the monitoring pipeline (netma-nsm-mon) and via the PDLC training interval. The neighbourhood-scoped exchange boundary limits the communication overhead to the set of clusters participating in a specific application's neighbourhood, so the effective communication cost grows with neighbourhood size rather than federation size. The current implementation does not provide automatic calibration of the update interval based on bandwidth or privacy budget constraints; this is identified as a direction for KUDECO.

How can formal privacy guarantees be applied without degrading recommendation quality?

CODECO implements **layered privacy protection** rather than a single formal guarantee. At the data collection level, RBAC policies restrict CR access to authorised CODECO components only. At the storage level, InfluxDB access is token-gated with dynamically generated credentials managed via Kubernetes Secrets. At the inter-cluster exchange level, model weights are encrypted before transmission and prefixed with integrity-verification mechanisms that protect against man-in-the-middle tampering. The current implementation does not apply differential privacy or secure multi-party computation to model updates. These mechanisms are identified as the next layer of privacy protection for KUDECO, with the recommendation-enforcement separation providing a natural firewall between advisory AI outputs and deterministic scheduling enforcement.

How should learning components handle cluster topology changes without full model retraining?

The PDLC-DL GNN architecture uses **dynamic model selection** based on the current number of nodes in the federation, adapting to topology changes without requiring full model retraining. The PDLC-CA aggregation layer absorbs the impact of cluster membership changes by re-deriving performance scores from the updated metric set at each evaluation cycle. Node join/leave events are reflected in the next monitoring window's metrics without triggering a retraining pipeline; retraining is triggered only when the MAPE performance metric exceeds a configurable threshold.

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What is the minimum MARL communication required to avoid pathological equilibria?

CODECO's answer is an **auction-based coordination signal** carrying workload identifiers, aggregate cost indicators, and binary willingness-to-accept values thus without having to keep and to pass raw observations, or full model parameters. This minimal high-level signal is sufficient for the agents to avoid duplicate placement of the same workload and to prevent persistent oscillation between clusters. The neighbourhood boundary ensures that no agent is required to coordinate with clusters outside its application scope, bounding both the communication volume and the coordination complexity. The sufficiency of this signal for all pathological equilibria has not been formally proven and remains an open theoretical question.

7.3 Priority 3: Semantic Abstraction and Adaptive Networking

How should the inter-cluster topology map be constructed and maintained?

CODECO adopts a **distributed, P2P construction via Nemesys-FC**. Each cluster's Nemesys instance builds a local multi-metric graph from underlay metrics (via nsm-mon/nsm-npp) and overlay metrics (via L2S-M CR module), then exchanges its local view with peer Nemesys instances through the federated API. The ALTO Core in each cluster merges local and remote views into a federated graph, producing neighbourhood-scoped cost maps consumable by PDLC-FC and SWM-FC. Consistency is maintained through periodic peer exchange rather than strong synchronisation, accepting the possibility of momentarily stale remote views in exchange for resilience and low coordination overhead.

Which metrics must be exposed across cluster boundaries?

CODECO exposes **five cluster-level scalar aggregates** across boundaries: latency, packet loss rate, link failure time, network energy, and total bandwidth. These are produced by the nsm-controller's two-level aggregation pipeline (per-node then per-cluster) using either FAIR or WEIGHTED averaging. All node-level detail including individual node names, internal link names, per-node resource availability remains private to the cluster. This minimal exposure set is sufficient for SWM-FC to compute informed cross-cluster placement decisions and for Nemesys-FC to construct ALTO cost maps.

How should inter-cluster overlay connectivity be managed during workload migration?

SWM-FC coordinates network reconfiguration as an integral part of the migration process. When a migration is triggered, SWM-L1 instructs the Hub's NetMA instance to update the inter-cluster L2S-M links before the old pod instance is terminated. NED VxLAN tunnels are reconfigured by the IDCO control plane using the updated assignment plan from SWM-FC, and i-LPM monitoring of the affected tunnels provides immediate feedback on whether the new path meets the channel's QoS requirements. The three-phase migration procedure (reserve at destination → transfer → release at source) ensures that network connectivity to the workload is never interrupted.

How should inter-domain probing be handled?

CODECO addresses this through the **federated NSM passive pipeline**, in which netma-nsm-mon instances across clusters perform on-demand cross-cluster measurements via the NPP (Network Probing Plugin) architecture. Within each cluster, NPP instances operate in full mesh. Cross-cluster connections allow on-demand inter-cluster measurements to be issued before orchestration decisions are taken. The i-LPM component continuously measures VxLAN tunnel performance for established inter-cluster overlays, providing ongoing visibility

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without requiring active probing bursts. This design limits inter-domain probing overhead to the neighbourhood scope rather than the full federation.

Can KubeSlice-style slicing be integrated with Kubernetes scheduling workflows?

CODECO does not pursue KubeSlice integration. The analogous functionality is provided by the combination of **CAM (semantic application abstraction)** and **L2S-M (per-application virtual network instantiation)**. CAM allows tenants to specify logical service groupings and their communication requirements at the application level, which CNC uses to define the neighbourhood. L2S-M creates on-demand, isolated Layer 2 virtual networks for each application, with Vlinks instantiated only for clusters participating in the application's neighbourhood. This achieves the isolation and service-oriented federation that KubeSlice targets while remaining fully integrated with the CODECO placement and scheduling pipeline.

7.4 Priority 4: Federated Scheduling

What is the minimal sufficient aggregate cluster descriptor?

CODECO demonstrates that **five scalars** (aggregated latency, packet loss, failure time, network energy, and total bandwidth) together with a cluster reachability flag and PDLC node recommendation counts, constitute a sufficient cluster descriptor for SWM-FC's two-layer federated scheduling. In L2 problems, remote clusters are modelled as abstract nodes with aggregated total capacity (sum of node resources) and maximum per-node capacity, without exposing any internal topology. This abstraction is sufficient for SWM-FC to guarantee that channel latency and bandwidth requirements are met across cluster boundaries, as demonstrated by the three-part latency decomposition model.

How should global and local scheduler layers interact when constraints span inter-cluster channels?

SWM-FC resolves this through **latency propagation**: when a cross-cluster channel's first endpoint is placed in cluster C_1 , SWM-L2 in C_1 returns the intra-cluster latency contribution as part of the L2 solution. SWM-L1 injects this value into the L2 problem presented to the next cluster, allowing SWM-L2 in C_2 to verify the full end-to-end channel latency requirement without requiring any direct communication between the two clusters. SWM-FC explicitly minimises the first-cluster latency contribution to maximise flexibility for subsequent clusters.

To what extent can decentralised scheduling be made loop-free and convergent?

SWM-FC provides **loop-freedom by construction** through its sequential L2 problem-solving approach within a bounded neighbourhood. The ordered cluster sequence S ensures that each cluster is visited at most twice (once in the main round, once in the reconsideration round), and that workloads are never forwarded in a cycle — a cluster that has already been solved does not receive further workloads in the same placement attempt. Within the neighbourhood boundary, pure blind forwarding is prevented by the sequential handoff protocol in which each cluster's assignment is finalized before the next is attempted. Convergence is guaranteed within the neighbourhood scope: if no feasible placement exists after two rounds, the placement fails deterministically rather than looping indefinitely.

How should migration be treated relative to replication in constrained far Edge environments?

CODECO treats **migration as a first-class scheduling operation** and adopts a reservation-before-release strategy: SWM-FC reserves resources at the destination cluster before the source instance is terminated, ensuring service continuity at the cost of transient resource duplication. Migration is preferred over replication for mobile or context-sensitive workloads because it avoids the ongoing cost of maintaining inactive replicas. Migration decisions are

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triggered by PDLC-FC based on changes in infrastructure conditions or user-defined performance profile thresholds, providing a principled mechanism for determining when the operational cost of migration is justified by the improvement in placement quality.

How can scheduling decisions account for inter-cluster communication energy?

CODECO addresses this through **flow energy and link energy measurements** collected by netma-nsm-mon and exposed to PDLC-CA as inputs to the greenness performance profile. The Feeney-model-based energy estimates, applied at both link and flow granularity, allow PDLC-CA to score nodes and clusters with respect to the energy cost of cross-cluster data movement as well as local compute energy. SWM-FC consumes these scores when evaluating placement alternatives, allowing the scheduler to prefer placements that minimise inter-cluster traffic energy, for example, by co-locating communicating microservices in the same cluster when the cross-cluster energy penalty outweighs the benefit of distributing the compute load.

8 Summary, Key Takeaways and Directions for Future Work

This deliverable provides the complete architectural specification of the CODECO federated orchestration framework across its full design scope. Section 2 established the three foundational design principles of data-compute-network co-orchestration, hybrid layered governance, and application neighbourhood scoping, and positioned them against the heterogeneous, mobility-constrained, and energy-aware requirements of CEI continuum environments. Section 3 surveyed and comparatively assessed the state of the art across four priority areas, namely, control-plane decentralisation, privacy-preserving decentralised AI, semantic abstraction and adaptive networking, and federated scheduling, identifying open questions that guided the CODECO design. Section 4 presented the overall federated architecture, including the three-layer governance model, the OCM-based control structure, and the AI-driven decision flow. Section 5 illustrated the end-to-end framework through representative deployment and runtime workflow examples. Section 6 provided the operation of all five CODECO components in both single-cluster and federated-cluster configurations. Section 7 returned to the open questions of Section 3 and answered each one based on the implemented architecture.

8.1 Key Takeaways

Data-compute-network co-orchestration is both necessary and achievable. The simultaneous consideration of computational resources, network metrics, and data observability in placement and rescheduling decisions produces materially better-informed outcomes than compute-centric scheduling alone. The PDLC-CA performance profiling mechanism, which aggregates cross-layer metrics into compact node scores calibrated to user-defined objectives such as greenness and resilience, provides an extensible and practically deployable realisation of this principle.

Application neighbourhoods are an effective and generalisable scalability mechanism. Constraining the coordination scope to a semantically defined, application-specific subset of Managed Clusters avoids the global state dissemination that would otherwise make federated orchestration prohibitively expensive. The neighbourhood concept addresses a gap not filled by any existing Kubernetes federation framework reviewed in Section 3.

Separating recommendation from enforcement improves stability and auditability. The explicit decoupling between PDLC-FC (AI-based placement recommendations) and SWM-FC

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(deterministic scheduling enforcement) avoids oscillation and accountability problems, simplifies the independent evolution of each layer, and provides a natural integration point for future AI Act compliance mechanisms.

A hybrid governance model is the right response to far Edge constraints. CODECO's hybrid model integrating centralised governance via OCM, coordination scoped to application neighbourhoods, and autonomous execution within MCs provides the appropriate balance between consistency and resilience and has been shown to be realisable within the Kubernetes-native tooling ecosystem without replacing its core primitives.

8.2 Directions for Future Work

The open questions of Section 3 are partially answered, not fully closed. As documented in Section 7, CODECO provides concrete, implemented answers to the majority of the questions raised in the priority analysis. Formal convergence guarantees for the MARL recommendation loop, differential-privacy protection for model updates, and automatic calibration of inter-cluster communication overhead remain open and constitute the most consequential items for the KUDECO research agenda.

Multi-hub federation and cross-hub neighbourhood composition. The current design assumes a single Hub cluster per federation. Supporting multiple peering Hub instances raises unresolved questions around namespace consistency, policy reconciliation, and cross-hub neighbourhood definition. This is the most architecturally significant extension required for large-scale, multi-operator CEI deployments.

Inline and adaptive AI training. The current PDLC-FC architecture relies primarily on periodic batch training. For truly adaptive far Edge operation, inline learning considering continuously updating models from streaming observations without requiring connectivity to a central coordinator is necessary. Integrating online training into the scheduling workflow while providing formal convergence guarantees under variable CEI connectivity remains an open research problem.

Formal stability and privacy guarantees. The decoupling between PDLC-FC and SWM-FC mitigates oscillation risk but does not eliminate it formally. Similarly, the current privacy protection is layered and practical but does not apply differential privacy or secure multi-party computation to model updates. Both are consequential for safety-critical and regulated deployments and are identified as priority items for KUDECO.

Intent-driven orchestration. CODECO's current application model requires structured YAML input via CAM. Integrating intent-driven orchestration where application requirements are expressed at a higher level of abstraction and automatically translated into CAM specifications would lower the adoption barrier and aligns with the emerging industry consensus around intent-based networking and management.

AI Act compliance and safety-critical orchestration. As CODECO is applied to industrial, mobility, and critical infrastructure use-cases, compliance with AI regulations including the EU AI Act becomes a concrete requirement. This entails augmenting PDLC-FC with explainability mechanisms, audit trails for placement decisions, and risk-bounded decision envelopes. The architectural separation between recommendation and enforcement already present in CODECO provides a suitable foundation.

CODECO and KUDECO: continuity and community. The Eclipse KUDECO project is the designated vehicle for the continuation of CODECO development beyond the Horizon Europe project. KUDECO inherits the codebase, architecture, and open-source governance model, and provides the community infrastructure required for sustainable external participation. The directions listed above constitute the initial research agenda proposed for KUDECO, to be

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refined through community consultation. The long-term objective is for KUDECO to serve as a reference open-source framework for cognitive, federated container orchestration across the CEI continuum, extending CODECO's TRL 4–5 foundation toward production-grade deployment at Internet scale.

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Annex I – Metrics

This annex provides a revision of the CODECO cross-layer metrics presented in Deliverable D13. A description of the metrics presented is as follows:

- Table 7 presents the minimum subset of parameters considered in CODECO that define an application – [CAM parameters](#). Examples for CAM formulations are provided in the CODECO Eclipse GitLab. The [full schema](#) for the CAM is also provided in the GitLab, in [acm/config/crd/bases/codeco.he-codeco.eu_codecoapps.yaml](#).
- Table 8 describes the metrics collected in MDM, and available via Prometheus. The [schema for MDM](#) is available in the gitlab.
- Table 9 describes the metrics collected in NetMA, and available via Prometheus.

Table 7: CODECO Application Model Attributes, spec, and status, minimum subset of parameters.

Attribute	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
Spec				
Uid	UserId	<p>User ID (UID) typically refers to the Linux user ID under which a containerized process runs inside a Pod. This is a security-related setting, not a Kubernetes-specific user concept (like in RBAC), but rather the UID inside the container runtime environment.</p> <p>Available in K8s (runasUser), but should be provided by other CODECO components by ACM</p>	Positive integer; 0 not to be used (root); 1000, first regular user in UNIX; 1001 and above for non-root users.	n.a.
Gid	Usergroup	<p>When dealing with Kubernetes Role-Based Access Control (RBAC), user groups are used to define authorization rules for groups of users who interact with the Kubernetes API server. Identification of the group of user DEV</p>	Available in K8s (runasGroup), should be made available if required.	

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Attribute	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
performanceProfile	targetProfile	Desired performance profile for the application. CODECO defines greenness, resilience, UserDefined	Greenness, Resilience, UserDefined (string)	n.a.
qosClass	qos	Preferred QoS level. A scale 1-5 is provided to the user and converted to a desired QoS model, e.g., Diffserv codepoints.	ASSURED (L2SM), BestEffort string	n.a.
securityClass	securityClass	Desired level of security based on a scale of 1-5	High, Good, Medium, Low, None (string)	n.a.
appEnergyLimit	appEnergyLimit	Maximum desired level of energy expenditure for the overall K8s infrastructure associated with an application (percentage).		W (J/s)
complianceLevel	complianceclass	expected level of compliance, based on a scale of 1-5. Checked by MDM.	Positive integer, 1.5	n.a.
Status				
avgAppCpu	avgAppCPU	Aggregation of the CPU usage of all the services in the app (in vCPU units) Provided by ACM	String-encoded value in cores, e.g., 0.75	Millicores, vCPU = millicores / 1000
avgAppMemory	avgAppMemory	Aggregation of the memory usage of all the services in the app	String	MiB
numPods	numPods	The number of the pods instantiated for the application	Positive integer	n.a.
avgServiceCpu	avgServiceCpu	Average CPU usage per micro service pod	String-encoded value in cores, e.g., 0.75	Millicores, vCPU = millicores / 1000

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Attribute	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
avgServiceMemory	avgServiceMemory	Average memory usage per micro service pod	String	MiB
clusterName	n.a.	Cluster name (unique, assigned by K8s)	String	n.a.
nodeName	nodeName	Node name (unique, assigned by K8s)	String	n.a.
podName	podName	Pod name (unique, assigned by K8s)	String	n.a.
serviceName	serviceName	Service name, user assigned in the app model	String	n.a.
errorMsg	n.a.	CODECO application error message	String	n.a.
avgNodeCpu	avgNodeCpu	Avg CPU consumption of the application on this node	string-encoded value in cores, e.g., 0.75	Millicores, vCPU = millicores / 1000
avgNodeEnergy	avgNodeEnergy	Avg energy consumption of the node	string	mJ
avgNodeFailure	avgNodeFailure	Node failures averaged over time (EMA)	String (positive integer)	n.a.
avgNodeMemory	avgNodeMemory	Avg memory consumption of the application on this node	string	MiB

Table 8: CODECO metrics being collected by MDM

ID (attribute)	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
nodeName		identifier of the node in K8s	String	All

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ID (attribute)	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
freshness		Age of data since last change	String (numeric between 0 and 1)	n.a.
Compliance_state	Compliance	<p>The <code>compliance_state</code> schema describes the compliance status of a resource (like a Pod or Deployment) within a system. It includes the source system and regulation under evaluation, the name and type of the resource, and an overall status (e.g., "compliant", "non-compliant"). It also lists detailed controls, each with an ID, status (like "passed" or "failed"), and optional severity and description.</p> <p>All fields are textual—there are no numeric values or units. The schema is designed to represent qualitative compliance information, not metrics.</p>	String	n.a.

Table 9: CODECO metrics being collected by NetMA.

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ID (attribute)	Former (D10)	Description	Values	Units
nodeName		Identifier of the node in K8s	String	n.a.
name (inside link)		Identifier of the link of a node	String	n.a.
NSM: netma-nsm-mon (underlay metrics at a node level)				
uLinkFailure		Number of failures of a link	String (integer)	n.a.
uPacketLoss		<u>Amount of packet losses in a connection.</u>	String (float)	
uNodeNetFailure		Sum of elink_failure and link_failure	String (integer)	n.a.
uNodeBandWidth		Egress bandwidth for a node - sum of bw for all Egress links on that node	String (integer)	Bytes, e.g., KB, MB
uNodeDegree		In a network, the degree of a node is defined as the sum of all edges connected to it (later, ingress and egress links)	String (integer)	n.a.
uLatencyNanos		Latency (EMA) for all egress links of a worker node	String (float)	ns
uLinkenergy		The average expenditure of energy over a time window (EMA) for a specific link	String (float)	W (J/s)
NSM (netma-nsm-npp) and Secure Connectivity				
oNodeBand-Width		Ingress bandwidth for a node - sum of bw for all ingress links on that node	String (integer)	B, KB, MB
oNodeDegree		Sum of all Channels for a source node	String (integer)	n.a.
oLatencyNanos/		average latency derived from elink latency; can be based on RTT	String (integer)	ns
uPathLength		Number of hops traversed; Average Shortest Path Length	String (integer)	n.a.

